

Third Edition

Proceedings of International Conference on Emerging Trends in Electronics & Telecommunications (ICETET - 2015)

ISBN : 978-81-952481-7-9

Dr. T. Anil Kumar

AIRA-GSPG;2021

29th to 31th May., 2015
Kualalumpur, Malaysia.

International Conference on Emerging Trends in Electronics & Telecommunications **ICETET - 2015**

About Conference

ICETET is a prestigious platform for academicians, researchers and professionals with particular interest related to all engineering and applied science topics. It helps to share knowledge, experience and foster collaborations across industry and academia, and evaluate emerging technologies across the globe.

This conference is dedicated to encourage researchers to publish their original research work, which can ultimately benefit the community development and research quality enhancement. Through this conference we motivate international scholars to exchange ideas and technologies, so as to explore opportunities through network and academic excellence.

Important Dates

Paper Submission Deadline	:	March 25th, 2015
Registration Closes by	:	April 7th, 2015
Acceptance Notifications	:	April 8th, 2015
Camera Ready Presentations	:	May 19th, 2015
Conference Dates	:	May 29th to 31st, 2015
Conference Venue	:	Kualalumpur, Malaysia

Advisory, Technical and Organizing Committees

Dr.Haci Ilhan (Turkey)	Dr. A. Prasada Raju (India)
Vangala Harish (Australia)	Dr. P. Niranjan (India)
Naga Prasad (Australia)	Dr. K. Prakash (India)
Ravula Samrat (Ireland)	Dr. K. Ravinder (Ethiopia)
Gajjala Sai Rahul (USA)	Dr. P. Prasada Rao (India)
Bejjanki Santhosh Kumar (USA)	Dr. K. Srinivasa Rao (India)
Yeturi Nagaraju (Canada)	Dr. V. Raja Gopal (India)
Bobbala Sunil Kumar (Singapore)	Dr. Habibullah Khan (India)
Dr. T. Nanda Kumar (Malaysia)	Dr. Suresh Pabboju (India)
Dr. S. Raghavan (India)	Dr. M. Sadanandam (India)
Dr. Tipparti Anil Kumar (India)	Kadarla Vineel (Sweden)
Dr. Srirama Srinivas (India)	Samuel Dinakar Ganta (London)
Dr. P. Chandra Sekhar (India)	Bandi Srikanth Reddy (London)
Dr. P. Vinay Kumar (India)	Dr. S. Shoban Babu (India)

P. Krishna (India)

Perumandla Lohitha (USA)

Ram Mohan (Switzerland)

Rajinikanth Reddy (USA)

Jyothirmai Bandi (New Zealand)

K. Mahender Sharma (India)

Jayshree Upadyay (USA)

Lalitha Susarla (Singapore)

[Call for papers and proposals](#)

ICETET 2015 provides a leading forum for the presentation of new advances and research results in the fields of Engineering, Technology and Innovations. The conference will bring together leading researchers, engineers and scientists in the domain of interest from around the world.

Accordingly, Topics of interest for submission include, but are not limited to:

- VLSI and Embedded systems
- Mobile Computing
- Security in Network, Systems, and Applications
- Wireless Sensor Networks
- Information Technologies and Systems
- Applied Sciences
- Control Theory and Application
- Manufacturing Science and Technology
- Mechatronics
- Robotics
- Chemical Engineering

- Power Systems, Energy Management
- Marine Engineering
- Material Sciences
- Mechanics
- Geomatics and Geof ormation Technologies
- Cloud Computing
- Bio-Technology
- Nanotechnology

Conference Proceedings

All submitted conference papers will be blind peer reviewed by three competent reviewers. The conference proceedings book and certificate of presentation will be distributed to the conference participants at the conference registration desk.

[Contact Us](#)

All the papers can be submitted to icetet15@gmail.com

INDEX

S. No	Title of paper	Paper ID
49	Web Enabled Light Using Arduino	MT0CS002
50	A Frame Work For Solving Identity Disclosure Problem In Collaborative Data Publishing	MT0CS003
51	Survey On Cloud Computing Technologies And Security Threats	MT0CS004
52	A Novel Quality Assessment Algorithm Based Internal Generative Mechanism	MT0EC042
53	In Audible Watermarking Based on Wavelets	MT0EC043
54	Resolution Enhancement And Denoising of Magnetic Resonance Images Using SWT	MT0EC044
55	VLSI Implementation of Low Complexity MIMO Detection Algorithms	MT0EC045
56	Network centric collaborative navigation for target localization using PSO tuned UKF	MT0EC046
57	Quality index assessment for digital media based on SSIM and NSS approaches	MTOEC047
58	A novel approach for power reduction & image enhancement by using multi scale RETINEX for emissive display	MT0EC048
59	An high equipped data hiding algorithm based on secret fragment visible mosaic images and pixel color transformations for secure image transmission	MT0EC049
60	High Performance Implementation of FIR Filter for DSP Applications based on FPGA	MT0EC050
61	Outage Probability Analysis of Multipath Fading Channels in Long Term Evolution-LTE	MT0EC051
62	Capacity Limits and Estimation of Massive MIMO Systems	MT0EC052
63	Performance of LTE Channel Estimation Algorithms for Different Interpolation Methods and Modulation Schemes	MT0EC053
64	Image Compression Algorithms using DCT Based Motion Recovery using 14-Bit Addition Techniques	MT0EC054
65	Energy efficient resource allocation in OFDM systems signals with sign adjustment	MT0EC055
66	Survey on energy efficiency protocols in wireless network	MT0EC056
67	Design and modeling of intelligent traffic light controller on FPGA	MT0EC057
68	Cooperative Spectrum Sensing Technique using Multiple Energy Detectors for Cognitive Radio Networks	MT0EC058

INDEX

69	Enhancement the security of AES algorithm for high speed fault detection	MT0EC059
70	A comparative study of channel estimation for multicarrier system for QAM/QPSK modulation techniques	MT0EC060
71	A DC/DC Converter with Voltage Boost-Up Using Zero Voltage Switching Technique	MT0EE006
72	Performance Study of PAPR Reduction Techniques in OFDM	MT0EC061
73	Analytical Performance of Peak Spectral Efficiency in LTE systems	MT0EC062
74	Scaling Based Power Saving for Maximum Communication Path Lifetime in Wireless Sensor Networks	MT0CS005
75	Relay Selection For Coded Cooperative Networks Over Nakagami-M Fading Channels	MT0EC063
76	OFDM Channel Estimation using Wiener Filtering and its Implementation	MT0EC064
77	Study and Implementation of Energy Detection Algorithm for WLAN and WiMAX	MT0EC065
78	VLSI Implementation of real time Image Processing System Designs	MT0EC066
79	A Robust Technique for Adaptive Noise Cancellation and its Implementation	MT0EC067
80	Design of Modulo $2n-2k-1$ Adder for Residue Number System	MT0EC068
81	A Robust Technique for Adaptive channel estimation	MT0EC069
82	VLSI implementation of OFDM specified FFT architecture for software defined radio	MT0EC070
83	A Survey on Advances in Solar Energy: Nanotechnology	MT0EC071
84	VLSI implementation of FFT architecture optimization in MIMO OFDM Trans receivers	MT0EC072
85	Multiuser Detection using Particle Swarm Optimization over GK Fading Channels in Laplace Noise	MT0EC073
86	Ultrasonic Signal Coding and PIR Sensors to Enhance the Sensing Reliability of an Embedded Surveillance System	MT0EC074
87	Internet of Vehicles: From Intelligent Grid to Autonomous Cars and Vehicular Clouds	MT0EC075
88	Power Sensor Tag with Interference Reduction for Electricity Monitoring of Two-Wire Household Appliances	MT0EC076
89	Tracking limbs motion using wireless network of inertial measurement units	MT0EC077
90	FPGA Implementation of High Speed Pipelined Log Multiplier for DSP MAC unit Applications	MT0EC078

INDEX

91	A Novel Data Embedding Method Using Adaptive Pixel Pair Matching	MT0EC079
92	Application of RFID Technology and the Maximum Spanning Tree Algorithm for Solving Vehicle Emissions in Cities on Internet of Things	MT0EC080
93	An Adaptive Noise Canceller for DS-CDMA Systems	MT0EC081
94	Optimum Channel Estimation Technique for SCFDMA Systems	MT0EC082
95	Robust frequency estimation for sampled sinusoidal signals without iteration	MT0EC083
96	Multiplexing Efficiency and Capacity limits of MIMO Systems	MT0EC084
97	Optimum Design of Heat Sink for Natural Convection	MT0ME002
98	Multiuser Detection in Gaussian Channels	MT0EC085
99	Image Acquisition, Noise removal, Edge Detection Methods In Image Processing Using Mat Lab for Prawn Species Identification	MT0CS006

Best Paper Award

In this conference the paper titled
“A Framework for Solving Identity Disclosure Problem in
Collaborative Data Publishing”
got the best paper award out of 150 articles.

ICETET-2015

WEB ENABLED LIGHT USING ARDUINO

V. Thirupathi ¹, CH. Sandeep ² and G. Madhusri ³

^{1,3} Assistant Professor, ² Associate Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Computer Science & Engineering, ³ Department of Informatics,

^{1,2} SR Engineering College (Autonomous), Warangal, Telangana, India - 506 371.

³ University college for Women, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India – 506 009.

³ Research Scholars, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India-500 007.

¹ thirulu629@gmail.com, ² sandeep892@gmail.com, ³ madhu.gsr@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Web enabled light is the PHP web based application which controls the home appliances like light fan etc. The main aim of this paper refers to the use of computer and information technology to control home appliances and features (such as windows or lighting). Systems can range from simple remote control of lighting through to complex computer/micro-controller based networks with varying degrees of intelligence and automation. Home automation is adopted for reasons of ease, security and energy efficiency.

Keywords: PHP, Arduino, Microcontroller, Home automation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Imagine being able to control all the electrical appliances of your home from virtually any place you are in the world! For example, say one cold winter day, you are stuck in traffic on the motorway after a long day at work. By pressing a few keystrokes on your mobile phone, you activate a macro which turns on the heating, prepares your Jacuzzi, and switches on your electrical fireplace and lava-lamps at your premises.

Using the cybernetic concept of action space, we in fact extend the action space of the human with the computer, enabling the subscriber to talk to another subscriber and thus exchange information, issue or receive commands.

The system specification shows the description of the function and the performance of system and the user. The scope of our project “Web enabled light” is immense. The future implications of the project

are very great considering the amount of time and resources it saves. The project we have undertaken can be used as a reference or as a base for realizing a scheme to be implemented in other projects of greater level such as weather forecasting, temperature updates, device synchronization, etc. The project itself can be modified to achieve a complete Home Automation system which will then create a platform for the user to interface between himself and the household.

The project “Web Enabled Light” at the title suggests is aimed to construct a control system that enables the complete control of the interface on which it is based. General objectives are, to coordinate appliances and other devices through computer.

To eliminate the need of being physically present in any location for tasks involving the operation of

appliances within a household/office. Minimize power and time wastage. The control system will include two separate units: the computer or a laptop and the control unit. There will therefore be two operating environments. Computer or laptop will operate indoors and outdoors whereas the control unit will operate indoors within the temperature and humidity limits for proper operation of the hardware.

This system is aimed toward all the average users who wish to control their household/office appliances remotely from their computer or laptop that the appliances are electrically controllable. Example of feasible appliances and applications under consideration include; enable/disable security systems, fans, lights, kitchen appliances, and adjusting the temperatures settings of a heating/ventilation/air conditioning system.

Certain assumptions have to be made in order to implement our project. The list of assumptions for our project is

- The user and control unit will establish communication using computer.
- The computer and processing software will support enabling light commands.
- The user is familiar with the web page buttons for controlling light on their computer.
- The controlled appliances can and will have to have an electrical interface in order to be controlled by the microcontroller.

Methods

The following is a list of constraint Considerations

1. The controlled appliances will need an electrical control interface. This system is only capable of controlling electrical devices.
2. The control module will need to be shielded against electrostatic discharges. This will increase the reliability of the system.
3. Battery backup for controlling unit can be implemented in case of power disruption.

The considerations for this system will include a choice of networks, communication protocols and interfaces.

- LAN Networks: The widely available networks are based on LAN for maintain the connections with the Processing software. This network provides local area coverage and can be utilized effectively for this project.
- Softwares: The available software that we have used is Processing 2.0. This software is the most efficient because this project requires a communication and limited data to be sent.
- I/O interfaces between microcontroller and devices: Serial I/O is considered as options for connection between the computer and the microcontroller. Using the microcontroller, a control circuit will be implemented to control the electrical appliances.

PHP (HYPERTEXT PREPROCESSOR):

PHP is a script language and interpreter that is freely available and used primarily on Linux Web servers. PHP originally derived from Personal Home Page Tools, now stands for PHP: Hypertext Pre-processor.

PROCESSING 2.0, SOFTWARE:

Processing is an open source programming language and integrated development environment (IDE) built for the electronic arts, new media art, and visual design communities with the purpose of teaching the fundamentals of computer programming in a visual context, and to serve as the foundation for electronic sketchbooks. The project was initiated in 2001 by Casey Reas and Benjamin Fry, both formerly of the Aesthetics and Computation Group at the MIT Media Lab. One of the stated aims of Processing is to act as a tool to get non-programmers started with programming, through the instant gratification of visual feedback. The language builds on the Java language, but uses a simplified syntax and graphics programming model.

Arduino UNO:

Arduino is a single-board microcontroller, intended to make the application of interactive objects or environments more accessible. The hardware consists of an open-source hardware board designed around an 8-bit Atmel AVR microcontroller, or a 32-bit Atmel ARM. Pre-programmed into the on-board microcontroller chip is a boot loader that allows uploading programs into the microcontroller memory without needing a chip (device) programmer.

ATmega328

The ATmega328 microcontroller is the current top of the line in the 28-pin ATmega x8 series. The ATmega328 has 32kB flash memory, 2kB RAM, and 1kB EEPROM. The ATmega328 can be considered a step up from the ATmega8.

Pin Description

VCC: Digital supply voltage.

GND: Ground.

Port B (PB7:0) XTAL1/XTAL2/TOSC1/TOSC2:

Port B is an 8-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-up resistors (selected for each bit). The Port B output buffers have symmetrical drive characteristics with both high sink and source capability. As inputs, Port B pins that are externally pulled low will source current if the pull-up resistors are activated. The Port B pins are tri-stated when a reset condition becomes active, even if the clock is not running.

Depending on the clock selection fuse settings, PB6 can be used as input to the inverting oscillator amplifier and input to the internal clock operating circuit.

Depending on the clock selection fuse settings, PB7 can be used as output from the inverting Oscillator amplifier

If the Internal Calibrated RC Oscillator is used as chip clock source, PB7...6 is used as TOSC2...1 input

for the Asynchronous Timer/Counter2 if the AS2 bit in ASSR is set

Port C (PC5:0):

Port C is a 7-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-up resistors (selected for each bit). The PC5...0 output buffers have symmetrical drive characteristics with both high sink and source capability. As inputs, Port C pins that are externally pulled low will source current if the pull-up resistors are activated. The Port C pins are tri-stated when a reset condition becomes active, even if the clock is not running.

PC6/RESET:

If the RSTDISBL Fuse is programmed, PC6 is used as an I/O pin. Note that the electrical characteristics of PC6 differ from those of the other pins of Port C. If the RSTDISBL Fuse is unprogrammed, PC6 is used as a Reset input. A low level on this pin for longer than the minimum pulse length will generate a Reset, even if the clock is not running.

Port D (PD7:0):

Port D is an 8-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-up resistors (selected for each bit). The Port D output buffers have symmetrical drive characteristics with both high sink and source capability. As inputs, Port D pins that are externally pulled low will source current if the pull-up resistors are activated. The Port D pins are tri-stated when a reset condition becomes active, even if the clock is not running.

AVCC:

AVCC is the supply voltage pin for the A/D Converter, PC3:0, and ADC7:6. It should be externally connected to VCC, even if the ADC is not used. If the ADC is used, it should be connected to VCC through a low-pass filter. Note that PC6...4 use digital supply voltage, VCC.

AREF:

AREF is the analog reference pin for the A/D Converter
ADC7:6 (TQFP and QFN/MLF Package Only):

In the TQFP and QFN/MLF package, ADC7:6 serve as analog inputs to the A/D converter. These pins are powered from the analog supply and serve as 10-bit ADC channels.

Features:

High Performance, Low Power Atmel®AVR® 8-Bit Microcontroller Family, Advanced RISC Architecture, 131 Powerful Instructions – Most Single Clock Cycle Execution, 32 x 8 General Purpose Working Registers, Fully Static Operation, Up to 20 MIPS Throughput at 20MHz

On-chip 2-cycle Multiplier, Atmel® QTouch® library support, capacitive touch buttons, sliders and wheels, QTouch and QMatrix® acquisition Up to 64 sense channels.

Peripheral Features:

Two 8-bit Timer/Counters with Separate Prescaler and Compare Mode, One 16-bit Timer/Counter with Separate Prescaler, Compare Mode, and Capture Mode, Real Time Counter with Separate Oscillator, Six PWM Channels 8-channel 10-bit ADC in TQFP and QFN/MLF package.

Temperature Measurement
6-channel 10-bit ADC in PDIP Package
Temperature Measurement
Programmable Serial USART
Master/Slave SPI Serial Interface
Byte-oriented 2-wire Serial Interface (Philips I2 C compatible)
Programmable Watchdog Timer with Separate On-chip Oscillator
On-chip Analog Comparator
Interrupt and Wake-up on Pin Change
Special Microcontroller Features

Power-on Reset and Programmable Brown-out Detection, Internal Calibrated Oscillator, External and Internal Interrupt Sources
Six Sleep Modes: Idle, ADC Noise Reduction, Power-save, Power-down, Standby, and Extended Standby

- I/O and Packages

23 Programmable I/O Lines

28-pin PDIP, 32-lead TQFP, 28-pad QFN/MLF and 32-pad QFN/MLF

- Operating Voltage:

1.8 - 5.5V

- Temperature Range:

-40° C to 85° C

- Power Consumption at 1MHz, 1.8V, 25° C

- Active Mode: 0.2mA
- Power-down Mode: 0.1µA

Relay:

The relay driver is used to isolate both the controlling and the controlled device. The relay is an electromagnetic device, which consists of solenoid, moving contacts (switch) and restoring spring and consumes comparatively large amount of power. Hence it is possible for the interface IC to drive the relay satisfactorily. To enable this, a driver circuitry, which will act as a buffer circuit, is to be incorporated between them. The driver circuitry senses the presence of a “high” level at the input and drives the relay from another voltage source. Hence the relay is used to switch the electrical supply to the appliances.

NO: - Normally Open

COM: - Common

NC:- Normally Closed

2, 5 - Relay Coil connection

1 - Common

3 - NO 4 - NC

From the figure when we connect the rated voltage across the coil the back emf opposes the current flow but after the short time the supplied voltage will overcome the back emf and the current flow through the coil increase. When the current is equal to the activating current of relay the core is magnetized and it attracts the moving contacts.

Now the moving contact leaves from its initial position denoted “(N/C)” normally closed terminal which is a fixed terminal. The common contact or moving contact establishes the connection with a new terminal which is indicated as a normally open terminal “(N/O)”.

Whenever, the supply coil is withdrawn the magnetizing force is vanished. Now, the spring pulls the moving contact back to initial position, where it makes a connection makes with N/C terminal. However, it is also to be noted that at this time also a back emf is produced. The withdrawal time may be in microsecond, the back emf may be in the range of few kilovolts and in opposite polarity with the supplied terminals the voltage is known as surge voltage. It must be neutralized or else it may damage the system.

Sample algorithm for processing software:

Serial port;

Serial. List () prints all serial ports connected with the microcontroller.

First we should identify all the ports have connected with microcontroller by calling the above method.

Load the text file which stores the status of button. It may be either 1 or 0. And these values for either first bulb or second bulb or fan and so on.

If the user wants turn on first light he has to choose light number from the text file and either 1 or 0.

If the status is 1 his/her intention is to turn on the light, so 1 will be written on to arduino microcontroller.

If the status is 0 his/her intention is to turn off the light, so 0 will be written on to arduino microcontroller.

Algorithm for Arduino:

Any one of the pin that the LED is attached to - change this if you have a separate LED connected to another pin

Make the pins to OUTPUT mode.

Read the response from web page, and according to the response appliances can controlled.

If the response is 1 light will turn On, and if the response is 0 light will turn Off.

RESULTS

Web page

Enabling light1 to turn ON

Enabling two lights to turn ON.

CONCLUSIONS

The home automation system has been experimentally proven to work satisfactorily by connecting sample appliances to it and the appliances were successfully controlled from a wireless mobile device. The Bluetooth client was successfully tested on a multitude of different mobile phones from different manufacturers, thus proving its portability and wide compatibility. Thus a low-cost home automation system was successfully designed, implemented and tested.

FUTURESCOPE

A useful feature would be to add support for remotely controlling an infrared transmitter. This transmitter can be placed within range of an infrared enabled appliance such as an air conditioner. The user would then be able to control more advanced features of the appliance such as temperature control, fan speed, etc.

The project itself can be modified to achieve a complete Home Automation System which will then create a platform for the user to interface between himself and his household

REFERENCES

1. PHP page:
www.w3school.com/php
2. Processing 2.0 software:
www.processing.org/tutorials
www.processing.org
3. Arduino:
www.arduino.cc
www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/arduino

A Framework for Solving Identity Disclosure Problem in Collaborative Data Publishing

Guguloth Vijaya ¹, A.Devaki ² and Dr. Shoban Babu Sriramoju ³

^{1,2} Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

^{1,2} Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India -500 007.

³ Software Developer, ³ SR Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana, India – 506 001.

¹gvijaya2005@gmail.com, ² a.devaki2008@gmail.com, ³ babuack@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Identity disclosure has been a problem in data publishing. When it comes to data publishing in collaboration with multiple parties, this problem is more. There might be insider attacks meant for obtaining identity of objects in the given data sources provided by data providers. Sensitive details are to be protected when data is being published. Many anonymization algorithms came into existence. One such good algorithm is m-privacy proposed by Goryczka et al. In this paper we build a framework that solved identity disclosure problem in collaborative data publishing. We build a prototype application that uses m-Privacy concept which is applied to horizontally partitioned data and also set-valued data. Experimental results revealed that the prototype is useful for collaborative data publishing without allowing identity disclosure attacks.

Key Words – Data mining, privacy preserving data mining, collaborative data publishing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data mining has been around for more than a decade to analyze data and make decisions which are useful to enterprises. Data mining is used in all domains. For instance banking, insurance, healthcare etc. are using data mining techniques to make expert decisions. In health care domain valuable information can be exchanged or shared among hospitals across the globe. This will allow collaborative computing as well. When data is published for mining activities, it is important to take care of privacy. The datasets in health care domain have data pertaining to patients. However, identity of the patients needs to be kept confidential. There are many possibilities that the identity is disclosed by the published data. Though the sensitive data is anonymized, it is possible that the data is matched with external data and establish identity of records. Therefore it is a challenging problem to achieve privacy preserving data publishing. Privacy preserving data analysis has been given much attention recently and many approaches as explored in [1], [2], [3] came into existence.

Collaborative data publishing is the approach in which multiple data providers share their data for data mining tasks. In this case the anonymized data is given by each provider. Still the insider attacks might be possible to establish identity of patients. Collaborative data publishing has been explored in [4], [5] and [6]. Another concept came into existence is known as secure multi-party computations [7], [8].

Figure 1 – Illustrates a scenario for distributed data publishing [9]

As can be seen in Figure 1, it is evident that (A) represents data publishing individually while (B) represents distributed or collaborative data publishing. The integrated data utility will not be lost in case of (B). Figure 2 shows the data tables which are considered as input for collaborative data publishing.

T_1				T_2			
Name	Age	Zip	Disease	Name	Age	Zip	Disease
Alice	24	98745	Cancer	Dorothy	38	98701	Cancer
Bob	35	12367	Asthma	Mark	37	12389	Flu
Emily	22	98712	Asthma	John	31	12399	Flu

T_3				T_4			
Name	Age	Zip	Disease	Name	Age	Zip	Disease
Sara	20	12300	Epilepsy	Olga	32	12337	Cancer
Cecilia	39	98708	Flu	Frank	33	12388	Asthma

Figure 2 – Sample input data [9]

As seen in Figure 2, the data is multiple tables. This data is considered for processing. The m-Privacy results as explored in [9] are presented in Figure 3. The data is given provider wise and there are sensitive columns in the table that can disclose identity of patients.

Provider	Name	T_b^*		
		Age	Zip	Disease
P_1	Alice	[20-40]	*****	Cancer
P_2	Mark	[20-40]	*****	Flu
P_3	Sara	[20-40]	*****	Epilepsy
P_1	Emily	[20-40]	987**	Asthma
P_2	Dorothy	[20-40]	987**	Cancer
P_3	Cecilia	[20-40]	987**	Flu
P_1	Bob	[20-40]	123**	Asthma
P_4	Olga	[20-40]	123**	Cancer
P_4	Frank	[20-40]	123**	Asthma
P_2	John	[20-40]	123**	Flu

Figure 3 – Provider wise data [9]

As seen in Figure 3, it can be understood that insider can match the data with some external data available in order to infer the identity of the records. Secure multi-party protocols explored in [5] can be used in order to preserve privacy. However it cannot detect

the insider attacks made by providers. To overcome this problem m-Privacy [9] approach came into existence. In m-Privacy algorithm was built in order to preserve privacy of shared data by multiple parties for collaborative data publishing.

In this paper we build a prototype application that uses the concepts of m-Privacy in order to achieve privacy preserving collaborative publishing. Healthcare domain is considered as an example for the application. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II provides review of literature on anonymization techniques and privacy preserving data publishing and distributed data publishing. Section III provides details about the prototype application. Section IV presents experimental results while section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Privacy preserving data mining has been around for many years. This kind of mining is meant for mining data without disclosing identity of the records in the data source. Many anonymization techniques came into existence. They include k-anonymity [10], [11], l-diversity [12] and t-closeness [13]. An unconditional privacy guarantee approach is differential privacy [1], [3], [14], [15], [16]. These privacy preserving techniques operate on various data sets and ensure that the data is published for mining with anonymization. The anonymized data is the data where sensitive fields are not disclosed. It does mean that identity of the records cannot be disclosed. All these techniques have improved the art of anonymization to some extent. With increased anonymization it is difficult for adversaries to perform identity disclosure attacks on data given for data mining.

Recently in [9] Goryczka et al. introduced the notion of m-Privacy that guarantees privacy and avoids privacy disclosure. Moreover the m-Privacy works well for collaborative data publishing. The anonymized data satisfies given privacy constraint. Heuristic algorithms were presented by them for checking m-privacy efficiently. The provider-aware algorithm provided by them was able to anonymize data for collaborative data publishing. M-privacy is able to provide better utility for privacy preserving collaborative data publishing.

III. PROTOTYPE APPLICATION

We built a prototype application that demonstrates the concepts introduced in m-privacy [9]. The application works with both horizontally partitioned data and also the data with set of values. The environment used to build the application is a PC with 4 GB RAM, core 2 dual processor running Windows 7 operating system.

Figure 4 – UI for registration of four data providers

As can be seen in Figure 4, it is evident that there is provision for four data providers for demonstrating privacy preserving collaborative data publishing. The four data providers register themselves and provide various data that is used for publishing after applying m-privacy.

Figure 5 – UI for patient registration

Each data provider application allows registration of new patients. This will help in generating synthetic dataset that can help in testing the concept of

privacy preserving collaborative data mining. The UI in figure 5 shows form that captures all details of patients including the disease with which he/she is suffering.

Figure 6 – Provision for collaborative data publishing

As shown in Figure 6, the prototype application has provision for applying m-privacy for the data provided by four hospitals. The m-privacy concept is applied on the collaborative data and the publishing ensures that the identity of the records is not disclosed. It also ensures that no one can launch collusion attack or identity disclosure attack on the data.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed application demonstrates m-privacy concept with four data providers. The data collected from the data providers is collectively anonymized before using it. The anonymization is done using m-privacy. The m-privacy guarantees that the identity disclosure attack is prevented. The results of the experiments are presented in Fig 7.

Figure 7 – Results showing disease distribution

As shown in Figure 7, it is evident that the disease distribution is mined and presented in privacy preserving fashion. The result of mining is presented which shows that Asthma is prevailing in the society as more number of people is affected by this. Besides the prototype application also ensures that the data that has been published for mining does not disclose identity information.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we studied privacy preserving collaborative data publishing. The notion of m-privacy proposed in [9] has been studied used it in our prototype implementation. Moreover, we adapted it for set-valued data. The prototype application is built to support multiple data providers and collaborative data publishing with privacy constraints. The application is built with user-friendly interface. The application demonstrates the privacy preserving data publishing of data taken from multiple data providers. The empirical results revealed that the application is very useful in the real world. The application works with horizontally partitioned data and also the data with set of values. In future it can be improved to work with other kind of data such as uncertain data.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Dwork, "Differential privacy: a survey of results," in Proc. of the 5th Intl. Conf. on Theory and Applications of Models of Computation, 2008, pp. 1–19.
- [2] B. C. M. Fung, K. Wang, R. Chen, and P. S. Yu, "Privacy-preserving data publishing: A survey of recent developments," ACM Comput. Surv., vol. 42, pp. 14:1–14:53, June 2010.
- [3] C. Dwork, "A firm foundation for private data analysis," Commun. ACM, vol. 54, pp. 86–95, January 2011.
- [4] N. Mohammed, B. C. M. Fung, P. C. K. Hung, and C. Lee, "Centralized and distributed anonymization for high-dimensional healthcare data," ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data (TKDD), vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 18:1–18:33, October 2010.
- [5] W. Jiang and C. Clifton, "Privacy-preserving distributed k-anonymity," in Data and Applications Security XIX, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 2005, vol. 3654, pp. 924–924.
- [6] W. Jiang and C. Clifton, "A secure distributed framework for achieving k-anonymity," VLDB J., vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 316–333, 2006.
- [7] O. Goldreich, Foundations of Cryptography: Volume 2, Basic Applications. Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- [8] Y. Lindell and B. Pinkas, "Secure multiparty computation for privacy-preserving data mining," The Journal of Privacy and Confidentiality, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 59–98, 2009.
- [9] Slawomir Goryczka, Li Xiong and Benjamin C. M. Fung, "m-Privacy for Collaborative Data Publishing", IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering vol:pp no:99 year 2013, p1-10.
- [10] L. Sweeney, "k-anonymity: a model for protecting privacy," Int. J. Uncertain. Fuzz., vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 557–570, 2002.
- [11] P. Samarati, "Protecting respondents' identities in microdata release," IEEE T. Knowl. Data En., vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 1010–1027, 2001.
- [12] A. Machanavajjhala, J. Gehrke, D. Kifer, and M. Venkatasubramanian, "l-diversity: Privacy beyond k-anonymity," in ICDE, 2006, p. 24.
- [13] N. Li and T. Li, "t-closeness: Privacy beyond k-anonymity and l-diversity," in In Proc. of IEEE 23rd Intl. Conf. on Data Engineering (ICDE), 2007.
- [14] K. Lefevre, D. J. Dewitt, and R. Ramakrishnan, "Mondrian multidimensional k-anonymity," in ICDE, 2006.
- [15] R. Burke, B. Mobasher, R. Zabicki, and R. Bhaumik, "Identifying attack models for secure recommendation," in In Beyond Personalization: A Workshop on the Next Generation of Recommender Systems, 2005.
- [16] K. LeFevre, D. J. DeWitt, and R. Ramakrishnan, "Incognito: efficient full-domain k-anonymity," in Proc. of the 2005 ACM SIGMOD Intl. Conf. on Management of Data, 2005, pp. 49–60.

SURVEY ON CLOUD COMPUTING TECHNOLOGIES AND SECURITY THREATS

Sumalatha Bandela¹, Ramesh Gadde² and Dr. Suresh Pabboju³

¹ Research Scholar, ¹²Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

¹ Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India -500 007.

³ Professor & Head, Department of Information Technology,

³ Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology (Autonomous),

³ Gandipet, Hyderabad, Telangana, India - 500 075.

¹ sumalatha1511@gmail.com, ² gadde.ramesh@gmail.com, ³ plpsuresh@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cloud Computing is one of the emerging technologies in the world. It is a computing technology that provides sharable computing resources like software, platform, storage, applications etc as a service to the customers on demand over the internet. Cloud computing is a Pay-per-Use-On-Demand model that can conveniently access shared IT resources through internet. Its advantages include cost savings, scalability, high availability, resilience, flexibility, efficiency and outsourcing non-core activities. Cloud computing offers an innovative business model for organizations to adopt IT services without upfront investment. Despite the potential gains achieved from the cloud computing, the organizations are slow in accepting it due to security issues and challenges associated with it. Security is one of the major issues which hamper the growth of cloud. In this paper, we aim to pinpoint the Threats and Security Issues of Cloud computing. This paper first discusses about various cloud based services, use of virtualization in Cloud Computing and then the relation of cloud computing with SOA and Grid computing paradigms. Finally it discusses security threats to cloud computing services.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Service Oriented Architecture, Virtualization, Grid Computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud Computing is an internet based computing technology. It is a technology that delivers sharable, dynamically scalable and virtualized resources as a service to the users on-demand over the internet through large data centers. Users consume resources as a service by just paying for what they use. It is a new type of utility computing that provides virtual servers to the users and IT departments on demand. Globalization of computing assets is the biggest contribution the cloud has made to date. The majority of cloud computing infrastructure consists of reliable services delivered through data centers and built on

servers with different levels of virtualization technologies. For users, the cloud appears as a single point of access for all their computing needs. Cloud-based services are accessible anywhere in the world as long as internet connection is available.

As with any new technology, the definition of cloud computing is changing with the evolution of technology and its services. No standard definition for cloud computing has yet been agreed upon, In the simplest of terms, cloud computing is basically internet-based computing. The term "cloud" is used as a metaphor for the Internet.

According to Buyya et. al. [1] a cloud is a type of parallel and distributed system consisting of a collection of interconnected and virtualized computers that are dynamically provisioned and presented as one or more unified computing resources based on service-level agreement.

According to U.S National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), "Cloud computing[2] is defined as a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and delivered with minimal managerial effort or service provider interaction". It follows a simple "pay as you go" model.

Cloud Computing is based on five attributes. They are

Multitenancy: Cloud Computing is based on a business model in which resources are shared (i.e., multiple users use the same resource) at the network level, host level, and application level. Virtual environments are used in Cloud to achieve multi-tenancy.

Massive scalability: It provides the ability to scale to tens of thousands of systems, as well as the ability to massively scale bandwidth and storage space.

Elasticity: Users can rapidly increase and decrease their computing resources as needed, as well as release resources for other uses when they are no longer required.

Pay per use: Users pay for only the resources they actually use and for only the time they require them.

Self-provisioning of resources: Users self-provision resources

The main feature of Cloud Computing is that computation is done in the "cloud".

Benefits of Cloud Computing

- Infrastructure used in cloud computing environment to provide resources is owned and managed by the cloud service provider

and need not be purchased by the customer. So infrastructure cost is reduced.

- Since computing resources are shared among multiple users, utilization rates are minimized. It reduces the infrastructure cost and increases the speed of application development.
- It increases computer capacity dynamically.
- Greater availability of increased high speed band width.
- Agility (increased speed of deployment; faster to market)
- Reduced in-house IT staffing (reduced maintenance costs)
- Enables adoption of latest technology
- Encourages standardization
- Reliability is often enhanced as service providers use multiple redundant sites which support business continuity and disaster recovery.

Cloud providers

A Cloud Provider can be a person or entity or an organization responsible for making a service available to cloud consumers.

- Builds the requested Software/Platform/Infrastructure services.
- Owns and manages the infrastructure used in cloud computing environment for provide the services.
- Providing the services at agreed-upon service levels.
- Provides security and privacy for the services.

Fig 1:Key Cloud Providers

Many companies are delivering services from the cloud. Some notable examples are depicted in fig 1:

Google -- Has a private cloud that it uses for delivering many different services to its users, including email access, document applications, text translations, maps, web analytics, and much more.

Microsoft — Has Microsoft SharePoint online service that allows for content and business intelligence tools to be moved into the cloud, and Microsoft currently makes its office applications available in a cloud.

Salesforce.com — runs its application set for its customers in a cloud, and its Force.com and Vmforce.com products provide developers with platforms to build customized cloud services.

II. CLOUD BASED SERVICES

As shown in Fig 2 Cloud services are offered in terms of Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS), Platform-as-a-service (PaaS), and Software-as-a-service (SaaS).

Fig 2: Cloud Service Stack

Software-as-a-Service (SaaS): It is the most widely known and widely used form of cloud computing. It delivers applications to thousands of users via web interface. For a customer, there are no up-front investment costs in server or software licensing. In a SaaS model, the customer does not purchase software, but rather rents it for use on a subscription or pay-per-use model. It is most often implemented to provide business software functionality to enterprise customers at a low cost. SaaS eliminates customer worries about application servers, storage, and application development.

Examples of SaaS providers:

- Salesforce.com is the best know example of SaaS computing which delivers enterprise application via simple website.
- Google Apps provide online access to the most common office and business applications used today via a web browser.
- Yahoo and Google, VoIP from Vonage and Skype etc

Key benefits of a SaaS model

- Applications delivery uses the one-to-many delivery approach, with the Web as the infrastructure.
- Management of a SaaS application is supported by the vendor from the end user perspective, whereby a SaaS application can be configured using an API, but SaaS applications cannot be completely customized.

The SaaS model is a multitenant architecture model, which means the physical backend hardware infrastructure is shared among many different customers, but logically is unique for each customer.

Platform as a Service (PaaS): It is a variation of SaaS. It delivers development environment as a service to the developers who use it to develop, test, deploy, host and manage custom web based applications. PaaS solutions are used for in-house (proprietary) development or for special software or applications on that platform. With PaaS, developers can often build web applications without installing any tools on their computer, and can then deploy those applications without any specialized system administration skills.

Examples of PaaS providers:

- Google App Engine makes it easy to build an application that runs reliably, even under heavy load and with large amounts of data.
- Microsoft's Azure
- Salesforce's.com,
- ADP Payroll processing, US Postal Service offerings etc

Key benefits of a PaaS model

- No maintenance in setting up and running platform and its tools
- Development by (geographically distributed) teams possible

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): It delivers computer infrastructure consisting of computer servers, storage, and networking hardware etc are delivered as a service. This infrastructure hardware is often virtualized, so virtualization, management and operating system software are also part of IaaS as well. It allows users to access the underlying infrastructure through the use of virtual machines. Users acquire computing resources such as hardware, processing power, memory and data storage, network bandwidth from an IaaS provider and use the resources to deploy and run their applications

Examples of IaaS service providers include

- Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2)
- Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3).
- Eucalyptus
- Open Nebula
- Nimbus

Key benefits of an IaaS model

- No maintenance for setting up and running the infrastructure
- Redundant data storage

III. CLOUD DEPLOYMENT MODELS

Cloud Computing model has three main deployment models which are depicted in Fig 3:

Fig 3: Cloud Deployment Models

Private Cloud: Private cloud refers to a highly virtualized cloud data center located inside the company's firewall. This model is suitable for transmitting classified information like Confidential, Proprietary or Personal information. It is used for critical performance requirements with high availability. The cloud infrastructure is operated solely within a single organization, and managed by the organization or a third party regardless whether it is located premise or off premise. The motivation to setup a private cloud within an organization has several aspects.

- To maximize and optimize the utilization of existing in-house resources.
- Security concerns including data privacy and trust also make private cloud an option for many firms.
- Data transfer cost from local IT infrastructure to a Public Cloud is still rather considerable.
- Organizations always require full control over mission-critical activities that reside behind their firewalls. .
- Academics often build private cloud for research and teaching purposes.

Public Cloud: Public Cloud makes the resources, such as applications and storage, available to the general public over the Internet on pay-per-use or free. It offers wide range of capabilities at reduced cost. Many popular cloud services are public clouds including Amazon EC2, S3, and Google App. Engine.

Community Cloud: It shares infrastructure between several organizations from a specific community with common concerns such as security, compliance, jurisdiction, etc. The costs are spread over fewer users than a public cloud (but more than a private cloud), so only some of the cost savings potential of cloud computing are realized.

Hybrid Cloud: It is a composition of two or more clouds (private, community, or public)

offering the benefits of multiple deployment models. It is a multiple cloud systems that are connected in a way that allows programs and

data to be moved easily from one deployment system to another.

TABLE 1 : COMPARISION OF CLOUD DEPLOYMENT MODELS

Feature	Private cloud	Public cloud	Community cloud
Cost effectiveness	High costs due to single ownership	Low costs due to multi-tenancy	Moderate cost savings
Examples	e-Bay	Google.com, Windows azure, Amazon.com, Microsoft	Oracle
Applications	Large Business units	Small Business units, Academic & Govt. Organizations	Health and financial institutions
Infrastructure located at	On /Off premises	Off premises	On / Off premises
Infrastructure owned by	Organization/Third party provider	Third party provider	Organizations/Third party provider
Infrastructure managed and maintained by	Organization/Third party	Third party provider	Organization/Third party
Infrastructure accessible and consumed by	Trusted	Un trusted	Trusted
Regulatory authority	Organization	Service Provider	Community
Security risks	Low risk	High risk	Moderate risk
Organizations Control over security architecture	More	Less	Moderate
Nature of sensitivity of data	Can store and process high sensitive data	Less confidential data	Community Data

IV. SERVICE ORIENTED ARCHITECTURE (SOA) AND CLOUD COMPUTING

Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) [4, 17] is a technology architecture which focuses on building systems based-on services.

A) Definition:

SOA is a design pattern which is composed of loosely coupled, discoverable, reusable, inter-operable platform agnostic services in which

each of these services follow a well defined standard. Each of these services can be bound or unbound at any time and as needed.

A Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) is intended to define

- Loosely coupled and interoperable services/applications
- A process for integrating these interoperable components.

A service is a function that is well defined, self-contained, and does not depend on the context or state of other services. Services generally communicate using standard protocols, which allows for broad interoperability. New services can be added or created without effecting existing services. In essence, SOA adds the agility aspect to architecture, allowing us to deal with system changes using a configuration layer rather than constantly having to redevelop these systems.

B) Primary benefits of an SOA

- Reuse of services and behaviors. In other words, SOA enables use of the same application functionality (behavior) over and over again without having to port the code, leveraging remote application behavior as if it existed locally.
- The ability to change business processes on top of existing services and information flows, quickly and as needed, to support a changing business.
- Monitoring points of information and points of service, in real time, to determine the well-being of an enterprise or trading community. Moreover, SOA provides the ability to change and adjust processes for the benefit of the organization in real time.
- The ability to expose certain enterprise processes to other external entities for the purpose of inter-enterprise collaboration or shared processes.

C) Relation between SOA and Cloud Computing

SOA can be used as a key technology-enabling approach to leverage cloud computing. As part of enterprise architecture, SOA provides the framework for using cloud computing services. Cloud architecture attached to grid computing ensure that the SOA applications take advantage of the elasticity of the cloud (and also grid computing) to process a service within a finite amount of time. The true success of SOA application depends widely on its deployment in the cloud and taking advantage of its elasticity.

Cloud computing and SOA are different concepts, but they are related. SOA is a pattern of architecture, whereas cloud computing is an instance of architecture, or an architectural option. SOA is more holistic and strategic, meaning it deals with the complete enterprise including the business drivers, whereas cloud computing is more tactical and is a way of solving a problem.

V. VIRTUALIZATION IN CLOUD COMPUTING

Virtualization is the technology that hides the physical characteristics of a computing platform from the users, instead presenting an abstract, emulated computing platform [16]. This emulated computing platform for all practical purposes behaves like an independent system, but unlike a physical system, can be configured on demand, and maintained and replicated very easily. The computing infrastructure is much better utilized, leading to lower upfront and operational costs.

IT organizations have increasingly used virtualization technologies to create a different kind of separation.

A) Definition

Virtualization refers to the logical creation of an IT resource that doesn't physically exist.

It is a method of running multiple independent virtual operating systems on a single physical computer.

Examples of virtualization include the creation of virtual application servers and virtual storage devices like hard drives etc.

Fig 4: Virtualization Mechanism

B) Different types of Virtualization

There are many different types of virtualization, including hardware, software, desktop, memory, storage, data and network virtualization. Hardware virtualization is one of the most common types of virtualization.

- Platform virtualization refers to creation and management of virtual machines. It is the logical partitioning of physical computing resources into multiple execution environments, including servers, applications, and operating systems. Virtualization is based on the concept of a virtual machine running on a physical computing platform. Virtualization is controlled by a Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM), known as a hypervisor. Xen, an open-source hypervisor, is widely used for cloud computing.

- Desktop virtualization is also another widely used type of virtualization that creates and stores a client’s desktop on a server that can be remotely accessed by the client over a network.
- Software virtualization allows different versions of an operating system to coexist and run on the same physical machine, providing the ability to run applications in different environments without the need to invest in additional hardware.

C) Reasons for Companies to move into Virtualization

Reason	Benefit
Server Consolidation	Savings in hardware, environmental costs, management, and administration.
Legacy Applications	Ability to run legacy applications that will not run on newer hardware and/or OS.
Build Secure Computing Platforms	Provides secure, isolated sandboxes to run untrusted applications.
Create Operating Systems	Resource limits and guarantees
Simulate hardware and hardware configuration	The illusion of running multiple processors and to simulate networks of independent computers.
Task Management	System migration, backup, and recovery

D) Advantages

Some of the key benefits of virtualization [15] that are indigenous to cloud computing are as follows:

- Security is provided by compartmentalizing environments with different security requirements in different virtual machines and one can select the guest operating system and tools that are more appropriate for each environment. A security attack on one virtual machine does not compromise the others because of their isolation
- reduction in energy consumption
- Provides cost reductions by consolidation smaller servers into more powerful servers. Cost reductions stem from hardware cost reductions, operations cost reductions in terms of personnel, floor space, and software licenses etc.
- Maximizes return on investment for the computer
- Facilitates the smarter and more efficient use of IT resources within an enterprise
- Billing based on usage (utility pricing) and not fixed hardware capacity
- Rapid deployment of additional servers

- Promotion of economies of scale
- Separation of the customer from physical server locations
- Usage based on service-level agreements
- Alternative sourcing supported
- Fault tolerance
- Application mobility among servers and data centers
- Reliability and availability: A software failure in a virtual machine does not affect other virtual machines

The key enabling characteristics of virtualization are low system overhead for optimum performance and integrated management capabilities in order to deploy cloud application components quickly and flawlessly

E) Relation between Virtualization and Cloud Computing

Cloud computing relies heavily on virtualization. Virtualization serves as the basis for Cloud computing architecture the services are built on top of a virtualization layers which help the service providers to manage the service and offer standardized platform to the users. Virtualization is in fact another key element of cloud computing, it enables the service provider to offer the homogeneous service simultaneously to all customers, something that cannot be achieved, for example, in grid computing.

F) Some Terms related to Virtualization :

- *Host*: Virtualization platform running hypervisor software.
- *Hypervisor Software*: A central program used to manage virtual machines (guests) within a simulated environment (host).
- *Hypervisor*
 - Primary component of a server virtualization platform.
 - Often referred to as the virtual machine monitor (VMM).
 - Central nervous system within a virtual infrastructure.
 - Manages the host's underlying hardware resources and handles all guest-initiated

operating system and application requests for CPU, memory, I/O, and disk resources.

- *Virtual Machine(VM)* : A VM is a group of files that represents a hardware-based computing platform, complete with storage, memory, and configuration components

G) Challenges introduced by Virtualization

1) Tracking of virtual-to-physical mapping & vice versa

Large-scale virtualization by CSPs allows higher resource utilization and adaptation to peaks and troughs in users' demand for computation and storage. However, the addition of virtualized layers also means that accountability requires the identification of events not only on the virtual server, but also the physical server. Currently, there are only tools (e.g. HyTrust []) which are able to log virtual-level logs and system health monitoring tools for Virtual Machines (VMs). There is still a lack of transparency of (1) linkages between virtual and physical servers, (2) relationships between virtual and physical server locations, and (3) how files are written into both virtual and physical memory addresses. Such information is currently not available as a single-point-of-view for the customers.

2) Multiple operating system environments to track

Many different operating systems are available for VMs, and this potentially introduces the need to manage the logging of machines in the cloud which uses a large number of different operating systems. Enforcing a single operating system for all VMs would solve this issue, but it would make the provider less competitive.

VI. GRID COMPUTING AND CLOUD COMPUTING

Grid computing [6] combines computers from multiple administrative domains to reach a common goal, to solve a single task.

A) Definition

Grid computing [7] is a form of distributed computing that involves coordinating and

sharing computing, application, data and storage or network resources across dynamic and geographically dispersed organization. In grid computing, servers, storage, and networks are combined to form powerful computing resource nodes that can be dynamically provisioned as needed.

B) Grid Characteristics

Large scale, Geographical distribution, Heterogeneity, Resource sharing, Multiple administrations, Resource coordination,

D) Differences between Grid and Cloud Computing[9,10,11,14]

transparent access, Dependable access, Consistent access, Pervasive access.

C) Similarities between Grid and Cloud Computing[8]

- To reduce the cost of computing
- increase reliability,
- increase flexibility by transforming computers from something that we buy and operate our-selves to something that is operated by a third party

TABLE 3 : GRID COMPUTING VS. CLOUD COMPUTING

	Grid Computing	Cloud Computing
Means of utilization	Allocation of multiple servers onto a single task or job	Virtualization of servers; one server to compute several tasks concurrently
Typical usage pattern	Typically used for job execution, i.e. the execution of a program for a limited time	More frequently used to support long-running services
Level of abstraction	Expose high level of detail	Provide higher-level abstractions
Task Size	Single Large	Small and medium
ComputationService	Maximum computing	On-demand
Accessibility	Offers dependable, consistent, pervasive, and inexpensive access to high-end computational capabilities.	Offers customized, scalable and QoS guaranteed computing environments for users with an easy and pervasive access.
Infrastructure	A decentralized system, which spans across geographically distributed sites and lack central control. It normally contains heterogeneous resources, such as hardware/software configurations, access interfaces and management policies.	A central computer server with single access point and spans several computing centers, like Google and Amazon, in general contain homogeneous resources, Operated under central control.
Middleware	Full-fledged middleware with well-defined industry standards	still underdeveloped and lacks of standard
Virtualization	Virtualization of data and computing resources	Virtualization of hardware and software platforms

VII. SECURITY THREATS

The biggest challenge in cloud computing is Security. Following are the threats in cloud computing [18].

Attack	Description	Counter measure
DOS	Hackers overflow a network server or web server with frequent request of services thus making them unavailable to legitimate client requests. The occurrence of a DoS attack increases bandwidth consumption besides causing congestion, making certain parts of the clouds inaccessible to the users.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reduce the privileges of the user that connected to a server. 2) Using an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is the most popular method of defense against this type of attacks. Each cloud can be loaded with separate IDS. And different intrusion detection systems work on the basis of information exchange.
Phishing Attack	Hacker attacks by allowing users to access fake web link. It affects the privacy of user's sensitive information that should not be revealed.	By identifying the spam mails.
Wrapper attack	Attacker can duplicate a fragment of XML signature and add additional codes to control the computer to do what he wants to do.	Use the digital certificate e.g. X.509 authorized by third party such as certificate authorities and also uses the mixture of WS-security with XML signature to a particular component.
Man in the Middle Attack	Data communication between two parties could be hacked by the middle party. Ex. attacker intercepts messages in a public key exchange and then retransmits them, substituting his own <u>public key</u> for the requested one, so that the two original parties still appear to be communicating with each other. Man in the middle attacks is sometimes known as fire brigade attacks.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) SSL should properly install and it should check before communication with other authorized parties. 2) Set up an intrusion detection system. 3) Implementing dynamic host configuration protocol (DHCP) snooping on switches can limit or prevent ARP spoofing. This in turn can help you prevent man in the middle attacks.
Backdoor Channel Attack	Hacker by comprising valid user's virtual machines provides rights for accessing victim's resources. This attack can affect the service availability and data privacy. It is a Virtual Machine level attack, Hypervisor level attack.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Perform better authentication and authorization 2) Provide strong isolation between virtual machines.
Network Sniffing	During communication, unencrypted data are hacked through network like passwords that are not properly encrypted	Use Encryption methods for securing the data.
Port Scanning	Attacker scans for the open ports and sends packets to the machine varying the destination port. It helps in knowing the services being run in your machine and about the OS	Firewall help to secure the data from port attacks.

<p>SQL Injection Attack</p>	<p>SQL Injection is one of the highest possibilities in a SaaS application. It is a method of attack where an attacker can exploit vulnerable code and the type of data an application will accept, and can be exploited in any application parameter that influences a database query like parameters within the URL itself, post data, or cookie values. If successful, SQL Injection can give an attacker access to backend database contents, the ability to remotely execute system commands, or in some circumstances the means to take control of the server hosting the database.</p>	<p>1) SQL Injection arises from an attacker's manipulation of query data to modify query logic. The best method of preventing SQL Injection attacks is thereby to separate the logic of a query from its data. This will prevent commands inserted from user input from being executed. 2) Properly validating user input for both type and format. 3) Use Stored Procedures that require a very specific parameter format, which makes them less susceptible.</p>
<p>Cross Site Scripting</p>	<p>User enters right URL of a website and hacker on the other site redirect the user to its own website and hack its credentials. It can provide the way to buffer overflows, DOS attacks and inserting spiteful software into the web browsers for violation of user's credentials.</p>	<p>1) Most cross-site scripting attacks occur either with error pages or with parameter values. Therefore the product needs to look for cross-site scripting signatures either within parameter values or within requests that return error messages. To look for signatures in parameters values the product must parse the URL correctly and retrieve the value part and then search for the signature on the value while overcoming encoding issues. To look for signatures in pages that return error messages the product needs to know that the specific URL returned an error code 2) To prevent these attacks, dangerous characters must be filtered out from the web application inputs. These should be filtered out both in their ASCII and HEX values. 3) Disabling scripting languages in the Web browser as well as the HTML-enabled e-mail client -- provides the most protection but has the side effect of disabling functionality. 4) By following links from the main Web site for viewing will significantly reduce a user's exposure while still maintaining functionality.</p>

IP Spoofing	<p>IP spoofing, also known as IP address forgery or a host file hijack, is a <u>hijacking</u> technique in which a <u>cracker</u> obtains the <u>IP address</u> of a legitimate host and alters <u>packet</u> headers so that the legitimate host appears to be the source.</p>	<p>1)Implementing hierarchical or one-time passwords and data</p> <p>2)Use of <u>encrypted protocols</u></p> <p>3) By installation and implementation of firewalls that block outgoing packets with source addresses that differ from the IP address of the user's computer or internal network.</p> <p>4) Ingress filtering which uses packets to filter the inbound traffic.</p>
Service Injection Attack	<p>Hacker injects malicious service through accessing service identification files and provides this service to users instead of valid service. This attack affects service integrity. It is an Application level attack, Virtual Machine level attack</p>	<p>1)Use secure web browsers and API's</p> <p>2)Use hash function to check service integrity</p> <p>3)Provide strong isolation between virtual machines</p>
DNS Poisoning	<p>It is corruption of an Internet server's <u>domain name system</u> table by replacing an Internet address with that of another, rogue address. When a Web user seeks the page with that address, the request is redirected by the rogue entry in the table to a different address. At that point, a <u>worm</u>, <u>spyware</u>, or other <u>malware</u> can be downloaded to the user's computer from the rogue location.</p>	<p>Populate the etc/hosts file with DNS entries of important servers. This file should be updated through a secure procedure.</p>
ARP Poisoning	<p>It is a form of attack in which an attacker changes the Media Access Control (MAC) address and attacks an Ethernet LAN by changing the target computer's ARP cache with a forged ARP request and reply packets. This modifies the layer -Ethernet MAC address into the hacker's known MAC address to monitor it. Because the ARP replies are forged, the target computer unintentionally sends the frames to the hacker's computer first instead of sending it to the original destination. As a result, both the user's data and privacy are compromised.</p>	<p>Use static ARP tables</p>

IX.CONCLUSION

Cloud computing is a combination of several key technologies that have evolved and matured over the years. Cloud computing changes the way in which IT services are delivered. Minimal investment, cost reduction, and rapid deployment are the main factors that drive industries to utilize. This paper discussed the key benefits of various cloud based services, benefits of using virtualization in cloud computing, Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) and its relation with Cloud Computing and key differences between Grid and Cloud Computing. It also discussed threats to cloud computing and suggested solutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Buyya, C. S. Yeo, S. Venugopal, J. Broberg, and I. Brandic, "Cloud computing and emerging it platforms: Vision, hype, and reality for delivering computing as the 5th utility, Future Gener", *Computer Systems*, 25(6), pp. 599-616, 2009
- [2] Peter Mell, Timothy Grance., "The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing", Sep 2011.
- [3] F. Sabahi, "Security of Virtualization Level in Cloud Computing," in Proc. 4th Intl. Conf. on Computer Science and Information Technology, Chengdu, China, 2011, pp. 197-201.
- [4] Yi Wei and M. Brian Blake, "Service-Oriented Computing and Cloud Computing: Challenges and Opportunities", *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 72-75, Nov-Dec. 2010.
- [6] K. Krauter, R. Buyya, and M. Maheswaran, "A Taxonomy and Survey of Grid Resource Management Systems for Distributed Computing", *Jr.of Software Practice and Experience*, 32, (2), pp. 135-164, 200.
- [7] M.Chetty and .Buyya,"Weaving Computational Grids: How Analogous Are They with Electrical Grids?" *Computing in Science and Engineering (CiSE)*, 4, pp. 61-71, 2002.
- [8]I. Foster's. (2008).
<http://ianfoster.typepad.com/blog/2008/01/theres-grid-in.html>
- [9] I. Foster, Y. Zhao, I. Raicu and S. Lu, "Cloud Computing and Grid Computing 360-Degree Compared", *Proc. IEEE Grid Computing Environments Workshop*, pp. 1-10, 2008.
- [10] L. M. Vaquero, L. R. Merino, J. Caceres, M Lindner. (2009). "A Break in the Clouds: Towards a Cloud Definition".
<http://portal.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1496091.1496100>.
- [11] Members of EGEE-II. "An egee comparative study: Grids and clouds - evolution or revolution. Technical report, Enabling Grids for E-Science Project, June 2008. Electronic version available at <https://edms.cern.ch/document/925013/>.
- [12] Mark Bowker, *Virtualization and Cloud Computing Move the SMB Market Forward*, June 2012.
- [13] *Virtualization Overview*, www.vmware.com.
- [14] Members of EGEE-II. An egee comparative study: Grids and clouds - evolution or revolution. Technical report, Enabling Grids for science Project, June 2008. Electronic version available at <https://edms.cern.ch/document/925013/>.
- [15] eremy Geelan. Twenty one experts define cloud computing. *Virtualization*, August 2008. Electronic Magazine, article available at <http://virtualization.sys-con.com/node/612375>.
- [16] M.A. Vouk, *Cloud computing issues, research and implementations*, *Journal of Computing and Information Technology* 16 (4) (2008) 235–246.
- [17] Michael Bell, "Introduction to Service-oriented Modeling", *Service-oriented modeling: Service Analysis, Design, and Architecture*. Wiley & Sons, 3. ISBN 978-0-470-14111-3, 2008.
- [18] "Top Threats to Cloud Computing V1.0", *Cloud Security Alliance*, March 2010. <http://www.cloudsecurityalliance.org/>.
- [19] "Detecting Service Violations and DoS Attacks". Ahsan Habib, Mohamed M. Hefeeda, and BharatK.Bhargava.
<http://www.isoc.org/conferences/ndss/03/papers/12.pdf>.

A Novel Quality Assessment Algorithm Based On Internal Generative Mechanism

Nalla Nanditha¹ and Ch Rajendra Prasad²

¹M.Tech Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
²Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering
^{1,2} SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.
¹nanditha.nalla617@gmail.com , ²chrprasad20@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Digital image quality evaluation is the area of concern from last several decades and to evaluate the image quality there are two acclaimed approaches namely subjective quality evaluation and Objective quality evaluation approach which are recognized as standard approaches by International Telecom Union (ITU). The conventional reported works based on these acclaimed standard approaches are failed to achieve the accuracy. Existing approaches like structural similarity index matrix (SSIM) is an innovative approach which performs well on the content dependent distortions (content dependent in the sense variation in color, shape, texture) but not as efficient as Peak to Signal Noise ratio. A novel algorithm is presented in this paper which provides an accurate performance to evaluate the quality of digital quality measurement. Mostly the conventional approaches fails to yield accurate results because most of the techniques relies on human visual data not on the residual distortion data which is termed as hidden distortion by most of the researchers. An innovative auto aggressive based on internal generative mechanism (IGM) which is successful to get Mean Square error both on distorted portion and residual portion as well. In order to yield the better result we have to combine the both residual distortion and visual distorted portion MSE's. The experimental results yield the better performance as well as accuracy too.

Key Words – Similarity index matrix (SSIM), internal generative mechanism (IGM), MSE.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sensing the sensory information plays a important role in the area of digital image processing. In the advance arena of technological era sensory information is acquired by using the advance devices namely Sensors, Satellites, Radar, Camera, Mobile so on. But since from the starting of the human existence Human Visual System (HVS) is most effective and naturally adapted mechanism to view the sensory information in digital form and as well as natural form. Digital image quality assessment approach plays a prominent role in image processing applications such as segmentation, object recognition, security related frameworks like

steganography. The process of acquiring the image information termed as sensory information role in areas like compression, transmission, restoration and acquisition. All these areas are strictly depends on the Human Visual System (HVS) mechanism so that we can find the variations in different parameters such as brightness, resolution, contrast levels so on.

A. IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Although Digital image processing is considered as application oriented domain but it too has some drawbacks such image quality assessment. In last 60 years so many works are reported by noted researchers and organizations to resolve the issue of quality evaluation of an digital image. But till now an accurate algorithm is not proposed in the

conventional works. The conventional works main drawback is that they keep on doing research on visual data but ignorance residual data stops to get the accurate result. The internal generative mechanism is one of such approach which yields the high end result.

Figure 1 Digital Image Quality Assessment Methods

B. MOTIVATION

In literature so many theories and algorithms are reported on Internal Generative Mechanism and its advantages to resolve the different types of distortions and its impact on both digital signal processing as well as digital image processing. Initially it is reported that the Internal Generative Mechanism approach is applied on the brain related issues i.e. in order to view visual sensual processing of the brain we first applied on the brain and it is termed as Internal generative mechanism of the brain.

The main advantage of the internal generative mechanism is to analyze the different types of distortions and its impact to degrade the image or signal from normal to abnormal behavior. The basic and most used approach from early days of human existence is the Human Visual System mechanism to understand the image behavior and to view the distortion related changes in digital image. To understand the effective image perception and to recognize the respective object in a digital image is done efficiently by human visual system. The accurate system to view the outside world and to perceive its internal behavior the basic system which we follow from stating of human existence is human eyes which

are quite effective and efficient to distinguish between the noise free image and noise effected image.

II. PROPOSED IQA SCHEME

A. AR BASED IMAGE PREDICTION

In this paper, inspired by the IGM theory about the visual perceptual process, we try to decompose an image into predicted and disorderly portions for quality evaluation. Since the Bayesian brain theory indicates that the brain performs as an active inference procedure.

$$x' = \sum_{x_i \in \chi} C_i x_i + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where x' is the predicted value of pixel x , $C_i = \frac{I(x;x_i)}{\sum_k I(x;x_k)}$ being the normalized coefficient, and ε is white noise. In this paper, we set χ as a 21×21 surrounding region. With the predicted model (1), an input image (I) is decomposed into two portions, the predicted image (I_p) and the disorderly image (I_d), as shown in Fig. 2

Figure 2 Flowchart of the proposed model with respect to reference and test image

B. VARIATIONS IN SENSITIVITIES

Since the distortion of the disorderly portion is independent of the original image content, the PSNR is adopted to evaluate the quality of this portion.

Therefore the uncomfortable sensation variation is computed as follow

$$P(I_d^r, I_d^t) = \frac{1}{C_1} \text{psnr}(I_d^r, I_d^t) = \frac{1}{C_1} 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{\text{MSE}(I_d^r, I_d^t)} \right) \quad (2)$$

where I_d^r and I_d^t are the disorderly portions of the reference and test images, respectively; $\text{PSNR}(I_d^r, I_d^t)$ is the PSNR value between I_d^r and I_d^t , and $\text{MSE}(I_d^r, I_d^t)$ is the mean squared error between I_d^r and I_d^t (the minimal value of MSE (such as 1) is set to avoid infinite psnr); C_1 is a constant parameter which is used to normalize the PSNR value into the range [0 1], for this purpose, we set $C_1 = 10 \log_{10}^{255^2}$

c. Visual information Degradation

The degradation on the edge between the predicted portions of the reference image (I_p^r) and the test image (I_p^t) is computed as their edge height similarity,

$$g(x_p, y_p) = \frac{2E_p^r(x_p) E_p^t(x_p) + C_2}{E_p^r(x_p)^2 + E_p^t(x_p)^2 + C_2} \quad (3)$$

Where x_p and y_p are the corresponding pixels from the predicted portions of the reference and test images (I_p^r and I_p^t), respectively; $g(x_p, y_p)$ is the edge similarity between x_p and y_p , E_p^r and E_p^t are the edge height maps of I_p^r and I_p^t , respectively, C_2 is the small constant to avoid the denominator being zero and is set as $C_2 = (0.03 \times L)^2$ [6], and L is the gray level of the image.

$$E_p^r(x) = \max_{k=1, \dots, 4} \text{Grad}_k(x_p) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Grad}_k = |\varphi \nabla_k * I_p^r| \quad (5)$$

where ∇_k are four directional filters, as shown in Fig. 3, $\varphi = 1/16$, and symbol * denotes the convolution operation.

$$s(x_p, y_p) = \frac{2\sigma_{x_p y_p} + C_3}{\sigma_{x_p}^2 + \sigma_{y_p}^2 + C_3} \quad (6)$$

$$\vartheta(x_p, y_p) = g(x_p, y_p) s(x_p, y_p) \quad (7)$$

d. Image quality measurement

On the other hand, the distortion on the predicted portion changes the original visual content and affects image understanding. Therefore, we combine the evaluation of the two portions, (2) and (7), to acquire the perceptual quality score

$$Q = P^\alpha V^\beta \quad (8)$$

Recently in [9] Goryczka et al. introduced the notion of m-Privacy that guarantees privacy and avoids privacy disclosure. Moreover the m-Privacy works well for collaborative data publishing. The anonymized data satisfies given privacy constraint. Heuristic algorithms were presented by them for checking m-privacy efficiently. The provider-aware algorithm provided by them was able to anonymize data for collaborative data publishing. M-privacy is able to provide better utility for privacy preserving collaborative data publishing.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

Every distortion occurs with four energy distortion levels based on the intensity levels of the digital image. When the digital image is distorted by white noise or the impulse noise then the respective distorted image makes the perception of its content difficult to the human visual system mechanism.

Figure 3 Noisy image

Figure 3 Original image $igm_value = 0.9787$

IV. CONCLUSION

A novel algorithm is presented in this paper which provides an accurate performance to evaluate the quality of digital quality measurement. Mostly the conventional approaches fail to yield accurate results because most of the techniques relies on human visual data not on the residual distortion data which is termed as hidden distortion by most of the researchers. An innovative auto aggressive based on internal generative mechanism (IGM) which is successful to get Mean Square error both on distorted portion and residual portion as well. In order to yield the better result we have to combine the both residual distortion and visual distorted portion MSE's. The experimental results yield the better performance as well as accuracy too.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Wang and A. C. Bovik, "Mean squared error: Love it or leave it?" IEEE Signal Process. Mag., vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 98–117, Jan. 2009.
- [2] Q. Huynh-Thu and M. Ghanbari, "Scope of validity of PSNR in image/video quality assessment," Electron. Lett., vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 800–801, Jun. 2008.
- [3] N. Ponomarenko, V. Lukin, A. Zelensky, K. Egiazarian, M. Carli, and F. Battisti, "TID2008—a database for evaluation of full-reference visual quality assessment metrics," Adv. Modern Radioelectron., vol. 10, pp. 30–45, May 2009.
- [4] H. R. Sheikh, A. C. Bovik, and G. de Veciana, "An information fidelity criterion for image quality assessment using natural scene statistics," IEEE Trans. Image Process., vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 2117–2128, Dec. 2005.
- [5] N. Damera-Venkata, T. D. Kite, W. S. Geisler, B. L. Evans, and A. C. Bovik, "Image quality assessment based on a degradation model," IEEE Trans. Image Process., vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 636–650, Apr. 2000.

IN-AUDIBLE WATERMARKING BASED ON WAVELET PACKETS

Naushin Urooj¹ and B Saritha²

¹M.Tech Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

²Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

^{1,2} SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.

¹uroojnaushin@gmail.com, ²banalasarita@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Although tremendous progress has been made on the Audio Watermarking on the past years, still there are lots of problems. In conventional approach usage of the Empirical mode decomposition (EMD) based on Synchronization Codes (SCs) and Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs) is done to watermark the desired content in lossless behavior, observing somewhat low performance like high Bit Error Rate (BER) is the major limitation in this approach. In this paper, a new algorithm based on wavelet packets has been proposed which produces the low BER giving high performance all together and the proposed algorithm embedding rate is 90% increased than that of 46.9–58.3 b/s, which is for conventional EMD approach. Finally, we show the robustness efficiency of the hidden watermark for additive noise re-quantization, MP3 compression, filtering, cropping and re-sampling. A comparison analysis shows that our proposed framework has high end performance than the other watermarking schemes proposed recently in the literature.

Key Words – Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs), Synchronization Code (SC).

I. INTRODUCTION

In digital media, the embedding of watermarking in audio is for copyrights protection and authentication. Here, a watermark is embedded in the original audio signal. Main requirements of digital audio watermarking are imperceptibility, robustness and data capacity. Digital watermarking has been proposed as a means to identify the owner or distributor of digital data. Watermarking is the process of encoding hidden copyright information in digital data by making small modifications to the data samples. A watermark is usually designed to permanently reside in the host data. When the ownership of a digital work is in question, the information can be extracted to completely characterize the owner.

An effective audio watermarking scheme must satisfy the following basic requirements:

- A. In-Audible Watermarking
- B. Imperceptibility
- C. Security
- D. Robustness
- E. Payload

Previously, different methods have been proposed for audio watermarking but some problems like robustness, Imperceptibility and data capacity aroused. In his paper, audio watermarking for the copyright protection is proposed. EMD decomposes the spatial frequency components into a set of IMFs (Intrinsic Mode Functions) where the highest spatial frequency component of each spatial position is in the first IMF and the second highest spatial frequency component of each spatial position is in the second

IMF, etc. An IMF is defined as a function in which the number of extrema points and the number of zero crossings are the same or differ by one.

Figure 1 Audio signal Decomposition by EMD.

In the two-dimensional case this demand is relaxed. The upper and lower envelope of the IMF are symmetric with respect to the local mean, which is used to define the IMF instead of the number of extrema points and zero crossings. There are many possibilities to define extrema, each one yielding a different decomposition in two-dimensional case. In this paper, we simply extract the extrema points by comparing the candidate data point with its nearest 8-connected neighbors. Approaches like, Empirical Mode Decomposition are totally data-driven method that recursively breaks down any signal into a reduced number of zero-mean with symmetric envelopes “Intrinsic Mode Functions” (IMFs). The starting of decomposition starts from finer scales to coarser ones. Any signal $x(t)$ is expanded by EMD as follows:

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^z IMF_i(t) + r_z(t) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where z is the number of IMFs and $r_z(t)$ denotes the final residual. The IMFs are orthogonal to each other and total IMFs are near to zero means and are fully described by their local extrema and thus can be recovered using these extrema. Lower frequency components can be altered. Whereas, higher order IMFs are signal dominated and their alteration modes can lead to degradation of the signal.

Sync-Code	Watermark Bits	Sync-Code
-----------	----------------	-----------

Figure 2 Data Stretcher.

This proposed watermarking is only based on EMD method and without domain transforms (unlike previous methods of EMD with Pulse Code Modulation), where a watermarking technique in the category of Quantization Index Modulation (QIM) is considered, for the reason to its good robustness and blind nature. All the Parameters of QIM are selected to guarantee that the embedded watermark is present in the last IMF, is in-audible. Finally, the watermark is associated with a synchronization code to facilitate its location.

II. Motivation

Watermarking an audio file in an image is motivated by several features. First and foremost it allows secret transfer of an audio file and prevents illegal transfer of multimedia content providing copyright protection. Moreover, HAS is more sensitive than HVS [4]. Therefore, transferring a secret audio file using image file as a medium instead of an audio file exploits the feature of HVS weakness providing a better degree of concealment. Robustness and transparency of digital watermarking are two basic and most important requirements of the digital image watermarking technique. In order to make the watermark robust, its strength is to be increased and it is to be placed in the significant parts of the image that can stand low-pass filtering or noise, however, that makes it less transparent and results in the degradation of the host image. Therefore the requirements of robustness and transparency are contradictive to each other. The need of the hour is to strike a balance between both the parameters to achieve maximum of both without trading off either of them.

III. PROSED ALGORITHMS

The idea of the proposed watermarking system is to hide the data into the original audio signal with a watermark (secret data) along with a Synchronized Code (SC) in the time domain format. The input signal which is original audio signal is first segmented into samples after that algorithm EMD is

conducted on every sample to extract the associated IMFs (Figure 1). Then all the samples are converted into binary data sequence consisted of SCs and informative watermark bits (Figure 2) is embedded into the extrema of consecutive last-IMFs. All bits (1 or 0) are inserted per extrema.

The number of IMFs and their number of extrema depend on the amount of data of each sample. The number of bits to be embedded varies from last-IMF of one frame to the following. Watermark and Synchronized Code (SC) are not all embedded in extrema of last IMF of only one samples. In general, the number of extrema per last-IMF (one sample) is very small compared to length of the binary sequence to be embedded in audio signal.

This also depends on the length of the sample. If we design by the M_1 and M_2 the number of bits of SC and watermark respectively, the length of binary sequence to be embedded is equal to $2M_1 + M_2$ then these bits are spread across several last-IMFs in extrema of the consecutive samples, providing an effective use of the data stretcher.

Finally, inverse transformation function is applied to the modified extrema to recover the watermarked audio signal by superposition of the IMFs of each sample followed by the concatenation of the sample (Figure 3). For data extraction process, the watermarked audio signal is split into the no. of samples and EMD applied to each sample (Figure 1) after that convert into the Binary data sequences are extracted from each last-IMF by searching for SCs, because we are embedding the data into last-IMF, shows that the last IMF before and after watermarking. This figure shows that there is small difference in terms of amplitudes between the two modes. The EMD being full data adaptive, thus it is very necessary to guarantee that the number of IMFs will be same as before embedding the data and after embedding the watermark data (Figure 1), (Figure 4) respectively. However, if the numbers of IMFs are totally different from original signal, there is no guarantee that the last IMF always contains the watermark (secret data) information to be extracted. These are the basically three steps those are:

- a. Synchronization code
- b. Watermark Embedding
- c. Watermark Extraction
- d. Performance Analysis

a. Synchronization Code:

For the hidden the secret data in the original audio signal synchronization code is used. This code is unaffected (non-degradation) by shifting attacks and cropping. Let P be the original SC and Q be an unknown sequence of the same length. If only the number of different bits between P and Q, when compared bit by bit, is less or equal than to a predefined threshold τ , When Sequence Q is considered as a SC.

b. Audio Signals Embedded:

In the watermark embedding process, synchronization of code are efficiently combined with watermark bits from a obtained binary sequence Before embedding, then after it is denoted by $n_j \in \{0, 1\}$ bit of watermark (Figure 2).

The Steps for embedding are as follows:

1. In step Divide the original host signals to the no. of samples.
2. Each sample is decomposed into IMFs (Intrinsic Mode Function)
3. Embed T times the binary sequence $\{n_i\}$ into extrema of the last IMF (IMF_z) by QIM.

$$e_j^* = \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{e_j}{H} \right\rfloor * H + \text{sgn} \left(\frac{3H}{4} \right) \text{ if } n_j = 1 \\ \left\lfloor \frac{e_j}{H} \right\rfloor * H + \text{sgn} \left(\frac{H}{4} \right) \text{ if } n_j = 0 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where e_j is the extrema of IMF_z of the original audio signal and e_j^* is the watermarked signal.

If “Sgn” function is equal to “[+]” then it is a maxima, and equal to “[-]” then it is a minimal. Denotes the floor function, and S denotes the embedding strength chosen to maintain the inaudibility constraint.

4. Reconstruct the samples by using inverse EMD modified IMF_z and concatenate the watermarked frames to retrieve the watermarked signal.

c. Steps for Watermark Extraction:

Host signal is split into samples and EMD is performed on each one as in embedding for the watermark extraction .extract binary data using rule given by (3).then find out the SCs in the extracted

data. This procedure is continuously repeated by shifting the selected segment one sample at time until a SC is found. With the position of SC determined, after that we can extract the hidden data i.e. information bits, which can be explained as in further steps.

- i. Divide the watermarked signal into no. of samples.
- ii. Decompose each and every sample into IMFs.
- iii. Extract the extrema e_j^* of IMF_2
- iv. Extract n_j^* from e_j^* using the following rule [3]

$$e_j^* = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } e_j^* - \left[\frac{e_j^*}{H}\right] \cdot H \geq \text{sgn}\left(\frac{H}{2}\right) \\ 0 & \text{if } e_j^* - \left[\frac{e_j^*}{H}\right] \cdot H \leq \text{sgn}\left(\frac{H}{2}\right) \end{cases}$$

..... (3)
- v. Set the start index of the extracted data, y , to $I=1$ and select samples $L=N1$ (sliding window size).
- vi. Evaluate the similarity between the extracted segment $V= y (I: L)$ and U bit by bit. If the similarity value is $\geq \tau$, then is taken as the SC and go to Step 8. Otherwise proceed to the next step.
- vii. Increase by 1 and slide the window to the next samples and repeat Step vi.
- viii. Evaluate the similarity between the second extracted segments $V' = y(I + N_1 + N_2 : I + 2N_1 + N_2)$ and bit by bit.
- ix. $I \leftarrow I + N_1 + N_2$. Of the new value is equal to sequence length of bits, go to Step 10 else repeat Step vii.
- x. Extract the P watermarks and make comparison bit by bit between these marks, for correction, and finally extract the desired watermark. Watermarking embedding and extraction processes are summarized.

d. Performance Analysis:

Watermark accuracy is evaluated by calculating BER as below,

$$BER(C, \hat{C}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^A \sum_{j=1}^B C(i, j) \oplus \hat{C}(i, j)}{A \times B}$$

..... (4)

Where $\oplus$ is XOR operator, $A \times B$ is binary watermark image, $C, \hat{C}$ are original and recovered audio signal respectively. The Signal should be

maintained more than 20dB SNR, Signal to Noise Ratio.

To understand the similarity between original and extracted watermark, consider Normalized Correlation (NC), can be given as,

$$NC(C, \hat{C}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^A \sum_{j=1}^B C(i, j) \hat{C}(i, j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^A \sum_{j=1}^B C^2(i, j)} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^A \sum_{j=1}^B \hat{C}^2(i, j)}}$$

..... (5)

NC greater value indicates the presence of watermark, while the lower value indicates lack of watermark

In this paper, the added advantage is that we make use of wavelet packets to get much more desired result than the EMD. Usage of wavelets packets gives low sub bands and a high sub band in place of IMF's which reduces the complexity.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 5 Watermarked Signal obtained from Audio Signal.

Figure 6 Watermarked and Extracted Logo.

Figure 7 IMF of Wave Files.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, Audio signals which are used for watermarking technique are divided into number of samples each sample is further decomposed adaptively by the method of new Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD). Those decomposed samples are called as an Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs), in this Intrinsic Mode Function, the low frequency is considered under different attacks which is presented and then after audio perceptual quality of the original audio signal is preserved. Finally, in our proposed algorithm we show the robustness efficiency of the hidden watermark for additive noise re-quantization, MP3 compression, filtering, cropping and re-sampling. A comparison analysis by using wavelet packets in this paper shows that our proposed framework has high end performance than the other watermarking schemes proposed recently in the literature.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. N. K. Zaman, K. M. I. Khalilullah, Md. W. Islam, and Md. K. I. Molla, "A robust digital audio watermarking algorithm using empirical mode decomposition," in *Proc. IEEE CCECE*, 2010, pp. 1–4.
- [2] K. Khaldi, A. O. Boudraa, M. Turki, T. Chonavel, and I. Samaali, "Audio encoding based on the EMD," in *Proc. EUSIPCO*, 2009, pp. 924–928.
- [3] K. Khaldi and A. O. Boudraa, "On signals compression by EMD," *Electron. Lett.* vol. 48, no. 21, pp. 1329–1331, 2012.
- [4] K. Khaldi, M. T.-H. Alouane, and A. O. Boudraa, "Voiced speech enhancement based on adaptive filtering of selected intrinsic mode functions," *J. Adv. in Adapt. Data Anal.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 65–80, 2010.
- [5] V. Bhat, K. I. Sengupta, and A. Das, "An adaptive audio watermarking based on the singular value decomposition in the wavelet domain," *Digital Signal Process.* vol. 2010, no. 20, pp. 1547–1558, 2010.

QUALITY INDEX ASSESSMENT FOR DIGITAL MEDIA BASED ON SSIM AND NSS APPROACHES

Asma Juveria¹ and M. Sampath Reddy²

¹M.Tech Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

²Assoc. Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

^{1,2} SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.

¹ asma.juveria@gmail.com, ²sampath_reddy_m@srecwarangal.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Conversion of High dynamic range images to Low dynamic range images is still area of concern in Image processing domain. The Tone mapped Operators are one such operators used to convert HDR to LDR for better visualization in practical Standard LDR displays. There is wide variety of Tone mapped images for wide variety of practical applications, so which Tone mapped operator (TMO) is best, so without an appropriate analysis and quality measurement, comparison of Tone mapped operators cannot be done. In order to perform this comparison, subjective rating approach is best assessment method, though its performance is outstanding its quite expensive and more time consuming one, moreover, precisely when come to optimization frameworks its quite difficult to embedded .Here, the proposed Algorithm proposes a novel Quality measurement Algorithm for TMOs i.e. Objective quality assessment algorithm by combining the Modified structural similarity index values and natural images statistics values. The proposed tone-mapped image quality index (TMQI) has good correlation as in subjective ranking score.

Key Words -Structural Similarity Index Matrix (SSIM), Natural Scene Statistics (NSS), Tone Mapped Operator

I. INTRODUCTION

From the last 60 years lot of development happened in image processing domain and in its applications criteria. One such application criteria is HDR (high dynamic range) images, whose intensity levels are very high, naturally in the range of 10000 to 1. The accurate depiction of luminance difference in real scenes allows by HDR images, for example range between absolute sun light to swoon starlight. HDR images are always area of research in the field of image processing and graphical tools, by this availability of HDR images are quite easy now a day. Normally a problem arises when visualizing the HDR images in Standard displays that gives scope to

design of LDR images, which makes the visualization an ease to human visual system. The conversion of HDR images to LDR is not an easy task ,high intensity values should change to low intensity values in order to perform this task in innovative way, lot of Tone mapping operators are came into existence.

An innovative and alternative to Subjective analysis is proposed in this algorithm i.e. Objective quality assessment approach, when compare the experimental results based on the Objective approach both test and reference show good dynamic range intensity values. Only few Objective quality assessment methods are proposed till now for HDR images. In order to visualize the super

threshold distortion and sub threshold distortion a predictor named HDR visible difference prediction method (VDP) is proposed. HDR VDP is designed to compare the two HDR images but not for the comparison of HDR images to LDR images.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

a. Contour let in Image Quality Assessment:

In this project, it first studies Contour let transform in IQA. Contour let is employed to decompose image into different scales and direction sub bands, and then contrast sensitivity function (CSF) masking is applied to obtain same visual sensitivity information within an image. Thereafter, based on the properties of human vision systems (HVS), we define a rational sensitivity threshold, and, with this threshold, compute visual sensitivity coefficients in each sub band. Finally, evaluation measurement of distorted images is built by comparing the computed coefficients between original and distorted images. It is shown in

Figure 1 Image decomposition with the contourlet transforms

b. Assessment of quality:

During the process of conversion of HDR images to LDR images, Tone mapped operators cannot preserve all the information in HDR images because of sudden reduction in dynamic range. While viewing the particular LDR images by human visual system this loss of information can't be observed. For making the LDR images to human visual system in a pleasant way Structural similarity index matrix (SSIM) plays a critical role. On the later end, Structural fidelity does not give whole quality measurement; therefore it cannot alone sufficient to provide overall quality measurement. In order to

provide a visually good quality LDR image a unique combination of preservation of structural similarity statistics and naturalness' statistics must be needed, but combing these two critical factors (structural similarity statistics and naturalness statistics) is still a complex factor.

c. Structural similarity index matrix (Structural fidelity):

Measurement of structural similarities between two different images for accurate quality measurement needs novel techniques to in order to perform this innovative task, one such a technique is proposed in literature is Structural similarity index matrix (SSIM). Structural fidelity mainly applied on local features and the comparison between three main components mainly luminance, contrast and brightness. Since Toned mapped operators are intended to change the intensity of local features and contrast. So it is unacceptable to compare the intensity of local features and contrast. So let us consider the typical example of structural fidelity, let take two patches 'x' and 'y' from HDR image and as well as LDR image respectively. Then the structural fidelity measuring between these two patches is given as

$$S_{local}(x, y) = \frac{2\sigma'_x\sigma'_y + C1}{\sigma_x'^2 + \sigma_y'^2 + C1} \cdot \frac{\sigma_{xy} + C2}{\sigma_x\sigma_y + C2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where local standard deviations and the HDR image patches cross correlation with LDR image patches is given as $\sigma'_x\sigma'_y$ and σ_{xy} and C1 ,C2 are positive stabilizing constants. In order to know the difference between the significant image patches from the insignificant image patches, as shown in equation Sigma parameter and sigma transpose parameter we derive the significant values to 1 and insignificant values to 0. This particular process is called non linear mapping and the non linear mapping tends to visualize the fixed threshold in contrast feature, but Human visual system does not have any fixed threshold length for contrast feature in practical. Now in order to know the significant and insignificant image patches a detection probability is

needed and that detection probability is Psychometric function. This psychometric function evaluates the 50% of detection probability; most commonly used detection probability function is normal cumulative distribution function. The normal cumulative distribution function is given by

$$p(s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\theta_s} \int_{-\infty}^s \exp \left[-\frac{(x-\tau_s)^2}{2\theta_s^2} \right] dx \dots (2)$$

Where p is the function of detection probability, s is sinusoidal stimulus amplitude and τ_s is modulation threshold and θ_s is the standard deviation of normal distribution that controls the continuous variation is detection probability function, and the ratio is given as

$$k = \frac{\tau_s}{\theta_s} \dots (3)$$

According to the Crozier's law, the K term in equation represents a constant, and its range is in between 2.3 to 4, and if the value is 3 then the probability of occurrence of false detection is low and it is considerably low. Contrast sensitivity function is one function that collects all data which is psychological functions is used to know the visual contrast sensitivity.

$$A(f) \approx 2.6[0.0192 + 0.114f] \exp [-(0.114f)^{1.1}]$$

Where f denotes the spatial frequency, this function is normalized have peak value 1. thus provides the relative sensitivity function of frequency function. In our proposed framework usage of Kelly CSF measurement function combining the Kelly CSF function with above equation we get as follows

$$\tau_s(f) = \frac{1}{\lambda A(f)} \dots (4)$$

Visibility of image is depends on the distance between the image the resultant observer and this distance is calculated based on the sampling density of the image. Based on the capability of human visual system multi scale approach is introduced in order to evaluate the weighted SSIM values and the to down sampled the image by low pass filtering method and then create the pyramid structure .By

using the two different TMO's on HDR image and on LDR image local structural fidelity map is generated. In this process loss of information may attain in LDR image compared to the HDR image ,in some scenarios bright regions may miss, in some regions dark regions may miss, but it cannot be observed in LDR image. Then single score attain by pooling algorithm is as follows

$$S_l = \frac{1}{N_l} \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} S_{local}(x_i, y_i) \dots (5)$$

Where x_i and y_i are HDR and LDR image patches. Where N_l is the number of patches. Then overall structural fidelity is attained by combining the scalefidelity score is as follows

$$S = \prod_{l=1}^L S_l^{\beta_l} \dots (6)$$

Figure 2 Framework of multi-scale structural fidelity assessment

First the structural fidelity performance is measured. Second the fidelity is checked at each stage and then by using the window overall standard deviation is obtained. Third distance of image from resultant user is measured by applying the CSF. Fourth main intensity values are attained by setting the mean of dynamic range of LDR image values. Then by combing all this measures we get overall psychological experiments. In order to perform this on RGB image it has to convert to Yxy space using the Y component.

d. Statistical quality assessment (natural scene):

The high quality of LDR images does not mean that it has all information same as in HDR image. Subjective approach has more drawbacks regarding

cost of process and time consuming while processing on contrast ,brightness etc. By using Objective approach we can get better correlation than subjective it can be compared with subjective approach, in naturalness of scene in HDR to LDR is evaluated as follows

$$P_m(m) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_m} \exp \left[-\frac{m-\mu_m}{2\sigma_m^2} \right] \dots\dots (7)$$

Above equation the intensity and contrast values which is used for quality measurement of global contrast and intensity values of tone mapping images, Then HDR to LDR in natural scenes is evaluated as follows as

$$P_d(d) = \frac{(1-d)^\beta d^{-1} d^{\alpha d^{-1}}}{B(\alpha, \beta, d)} \dots\dots (8)$$

And the statistical measurement is as follows

$$N = \frac{1}{K} P_m P_d \dots\dots (9)$$

e. Quality assessment model:

In much wide variety of applications, users preferred the single score by combining the overall score, IQA (Image quality assessment) is measured as follows

$$Q = \alpha S^\alpha + (1 - \alpha) N^\beta \dots\dots (10)$$

Alpha and beta parameters play a crucial role in quality assessment. Quality assessment of images is quite different from quality assessment of videos, because image is a collection of pixels and moreover it's static in behavior, while videos are collection of frames and its motion in behavior. The proposed method proposes the quality of Image; extension can be done on quality assessment videos. Quality measurement of videos is a huge task as it includes frame rate, psnr values, frame separation, noise detection etc.

Assessment of videos is a time consuming process, as video size increases simultaneously time to read all frames in a video also increases. Till now assessment of videos is done on subjective approach,

which is quite expensive and time consuming, so in near future extension of proposed method done on videos in objective approach which is more reliable.

II. SIMULATION RESULTS

The Structural fidelity is done in multi scale approach as shown in following figures, here 'S' is total multi scale score and 's1''s2''s3''s4''s5' are number of multi scales used in Structural fidelity. 'Q' is total quality score and where as 'N' is scene naturalness. The objective approach mainly relies on structural fidelity "S" and Scene naturalness measurement "N".

Figure 3 Original Image

Figure 4 Multi Scale Scores 'S1', 'S2', 'S3', 'S4', 'S5'

Figure 5 Quality Assessment Result

Figure 6 Simulation Graph

III. CONCLUSION

The proposed method is proposed based on the objective quality assessment approach, basically objective quality approach is proposed on gray scale images but HDR images is taken in Color spaces. The objective quality assessment approach is mainly relies on two methods, first multi scale structural fidelity and second one is scene naturalness. First the structural fidelity performance is measured. Second the fidelity is checked at each stage and then by using the window overall standard deviation is obtained. Third distance of image from resultant user is measured by applying the CSF. Fourth main

intensity values are attained by setting the mean of dynamic range of LDR image values.

Then by combing all this measures we get overall psychological experiments. In order to perform this on RGB image it has to convert to Yxy space using the Y component. Every time we cannot process TMO's on after visualization, for example in medical images, images are often taken in HDR images, so in that we process before visualization. In order to apply TMO's in all applications, optimization methods are adapted for this type of scenarios. The proposed method gives good quality score compared to previous objective approach in grayscale images and it is more reliable than available subjective approach.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. J. Kuang, H. Yamaguchi, G. M. Johnson, and M. D. Fairchild, "Testing HDR image rendering algorithms," in Proc. IS T/SID Color Imag. Conf., 2004, pp. 315–320.
- [2] E. Reinhard, M. Stark, P. Shirley, and J. Ferwerda, "Photographic tone reproduction for digital images," in Proc. 29th Annu. Conf. Comput. Graph. Interact. Tech., vol. 21. 2002, pp. 267–276.
- [3] G. W. Larson, H. Rushmeier, and C. Piatko, "A visibility matching tone reproduction operator for high dynamic range scenes," IEEE Trans. Visual. Comput. Graph., vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 291–306, Oct.–Dec. 1997.
- [4] F. Drago, K. Myszkowski, T. Annen, and N. Chiba, "Adaptive logarithmic mapping for displaying high contrast scenes," Comput. Graph. For um, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 419–426, 2003.
- [5] R. Fattal, D. Lischinski, and M. Werman, "Gradient domain high dynamic range compression," in Proc. 29th Annu. Conf. Comput. Graph. Interact. Tech., 2002, pp. 249–256.
- [6] F. Drago, W. L. Martens, K. Myszkowski, and H.-P. Seidel, "Perceptual evaluation of tone mapping operators," in Proc. SIGGRAPH Conf. Sketches Appl., 2003, p. 1.

A Novel Approach for Power Reduction & Image Enhancement by Using Multi scale Retinex for Emissive Display

Divya Reguri¹ and S Srinivas²

¹M.Tech Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

²Assoc. Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

^{1,2} SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.

¹ divyareguri@gmail.com, ²srinu486@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a power-constrained contrast enhancement algorithmic program for organic semiconductor diode display based on multi scale retinex (MSR). In general, MSR, the key element of the planned algorithmic program, consists of power controllable log operation and sub band wise gain management. First, we decompose associate input image to MSRs of various sub-bands and figure a correct gain for every MSR. Second, we have a tendency to apply acoarse-to-fine power management mechanism that recomputes the MSRs and gains. This step iterates till the target power saving is accurately accomplished. With video sequences, the contrast levels of adjacent pictures are determined systematically using temporal coherence so as to avoid unsteady artifacts. Finally, we present many improvement skills for data processing. Experimental results show that the planned algorithmic program provides better visual quality than previous strategies and a consistent power-saving magnitude relation with no unsteady artifacts, even for video sequences

.Key Words - Power consumption, contrast enhancement, OLED, multi-scale retinex

I. INTRODUCTION

MODERN display panels are classified into emissive and non-emissive displays. The cathode-ray tube(CRT), the plasma board (PDP) and the organic light emitting diode (OLED) are major representative emissive displays that do not need external light sources, whereas the thin-film transistor liquid crystal display (TFT-LCD) is non-emissive. In general, Emissive displays have many benefits over non-emissive ones. First, since associate degree emissive display can close up individual pixels, it will specify complete darkness and win a high distinction quantitative relation. Second, emissive displays consume less power than non-emissive ones as a result of every component in associate degree emissive display driven and the power consumption of the pixel is proportional to its intensity level. Note that non-emissive displays ought to activate their backlight despite component intensity. Thus, the OLED is to be the foremost

promising display panel for the next-generation. Display modules consume most of the power in digital media devices. Therefore a technique to attenuate power consumption within the display square measure is inevitably needed.

Several image process techniques for power saving in show panels are projected, on the far side of circuit-level power savings. Unfortunately, such techniques specialize in reducing back light intensity for TFT-LCDs while maintaining the similar level of perceived quality. So that they cannot be applied to power saving in emissive show devices like OLED. Lee et al. projected a power-constrained contrast enhancement algorithmic rule (PCCE) for emissive displays based on histogram equalization (HE), They developed a power-consumption model for OLED displays and formulated an objective function that consists of the HE term and the power term. However, with HE-based distinction improvement there's associate degree inherent risk of

overstretching. Also, since their methodology depends on certain parameters it cannot mechanically, systematically and accurately provide the power-saving level desired by a user. On the opposite hand, numerous distinction improvement techniques have been developed for dozens of years. One of them retinex is a well-known non-linear improvement method used for distinction improvement as well as dynamic range compression. Single Scale Retinex utilizes Gaussian low pass filter (LPF) and log operation to intensify a selected wavelength of the image, Multi Scale Retinex offers an output image as the weighted total of there tinex output pictures by using many linear LPFs having different support regions. This paper proposes a power-constrained distinction improvement algorithm employing a sub-band decomposed MSR (SD-MSR) for OLED. First, we design modified log operation for dynamic power saving. Second we propose a coarse-to-fine power management mechanism based on SD-MSR, It achieves distinction enhancement and dynamic range compression using adaptation weighting strategy suitable for associate degree input image. Finally, we propose a power management theme for a constant power reduction ratio in video sequences by using temporal coherence in video sequences. Experimental results show that the projected algorithmic rule provides higher visual quality than previous ways, and a consistent power-saving quantitative relation with no flickering artifacts for video sequences.

II.SUB-BANDDECOMPOSEDMULTI-SCALERETINEX

MSR is an extended SSR with multiple kernel windows of different sizes. MSR output is a weighted sum of several different SSR outputs. The MSR output for a single spectral component can be represented as

$$R^{MSR}(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n \cdot R_n(x, y) \quad (1)$$

Where

$$R_n(x, y) = \log I(x, y) - \log (F_n(x, y) * I(x, y)) \quad (2)$$

Here $R_n(x, y)$, denotes a retinex output associated with the n-the scale for an input image $I(x, y)$. Note that gain w_n is determined so that it can satisfy the condition of $\sum w_n = 1$ The symbol "*" in Eq. (2) denotes the convolution operation and N is the number of scales. $F_n(x, y)$ Denotes a surround function and is given by

$$F_n(x, y) = K_n e^{-(x^2+y^2)/\sigma_n^2} \quad (3)$$

Where K_n is determined so that the sum of $F_n(x, y)$ for all x, y is equal to $1/\sigma_n^2$ can satisfy denotes the variance of the Gaussian kernel at then-th sub-band. Under the condition $\sigma_n > \sigma_{n-1}$ for every SSR, we can derive successive frequency sub-bands. Note that a small σ_n is suitable for enhancing fine details, where as a large σ_n is suitable for improving tonality. Thus, it is important to select an appropriate value of σ_n in the MSR. Based on this rationale, Jang et al. proposed an SD-MSR that consists of a modified logarithmic function, sub-band decomposition, space varying sub-band gain, and an automatic gain/offset control (see Fig. 1). The modified log (mlog) is defined as

$$mlog(I(x, y)) = \begin{cases} w_L \log(I(x, y) + 1) & I(x, y) \leq \tau \\ -w_H \log(D - I(x, y)) + \log D & I(x, y) > \tau \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where τ is a user-defined threshold and D denotes an image dynamic range. For example, D is 256 for an 8-bit image

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the conventional SD-MSR [16].

w_L And w_H denotes weighting parameters according to and are defined as

$$w_L = \frac{\tau - \log D}{D - 1}, w_H = \frac{(1 - \frac{\tau}{D}) \log D}{\log(D - 1)} \quad (5)$$

As a result, the mlog function of Eq. (4) enhances the contrasts of dark regions as well as bright regions. In

this way, we can enhance image details both in highlights and shadows. Another feature of SD-MSR is to decompose the modified retinex outputs into nearly non-overlapping spectral bands. The following equation accomplishes this sub-band decomposition

$$\bar{R}_1 = R_1 n = 1 \bar{R}_n = R_n - R_{n-1} \quad 2 \leq n < N \quad (6)$$

As n increases, R_n corresponds to the low frequency region more and more. Here, R_n is computed by replacing the log of Eq. (2) With the mlog of Eq. (4) Next, the space vary ing sub-band gain at then-the sub-band is defined as

$$g_n(x, y) = \left(\frac{1}{NR_n(x, y) + \epsilon_g} \right)^{1 - \frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_{max} + \epsilon_g}} \quad (7)$$

Where

$$\sigma_{max} = \max_{n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}} \sigma_n$$

$$NR_n(x, y) = \frac{|R_n(x, y)|}{R_{n,max}} \quad (8)$$

In a high spectral band of small n , they make the gain difference between pixels larger, especially for the pixels with low $NR_n(x, y)$. This is because this spectral band has large high-frequency components representing image details. Meanwhile, they lower the gain difference between pixels in a high spectral band of large n to maintain the characteristics of a natural scene. Thus, using Eq. (7), the final enhanced image I' is output as follows

$$I' = \sum_{n=1}^N g_n \bar{R}_n \quad (9)$$

. III.THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

We propose a power governable distinction enhancement algorithm for OLED show primarily based on SD-MSR. Fig.2 describes the projected formula that consists of threestages. the primary stage coarsely reduces the power of an input image nearer to the target powerwith distinction improvement, and the second stage finely controls the image power suchthat it is so near to

the target power. If the input is a video sequence, the ultimate stage adjusts the power of every image so that it islikely those of its neighbours by considering the temporal coherence of the input video sequence. The projected formula is differentiated from previousmethods in the following3 aspects. First, we controlthe target power level mechanically. Second, we avoid theflickering process by keeping the facility levels of adjacentimages constant for video sequences. Third, we achieve real timeprocess of the projected formula on a general purpose graphics process unit (GPU) even for full HD video sequences

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the proposed algorithm.

A

. Power Modelling in OLED Display

Before presenting an in depth clarification of the projected algorithmic program, we want to model power for associate OLED. Dong et al. conferred a pixel-based power model that estimates the ability consumption of OLED modules supported the red green-blue (RGB) specification of every pixel. the ability consumption of associate OLED with K pixels, i.e., P is

$$P_{OLED} = C + \sum_{i=1}^K (f_R(R_i) + f_G(G_i) + f_B(B_i)) \quad (10)$$

Also, we consider only the Y-component because it dominates the entire overall power. Note that the Y-component indicates the luminance component in YUV color format. So we use the Y-component power consumption (YP) of an OLED display with K pixels as

$$Y_p = \sum_{i=1}^K Y_i^\gamma \quad (11)$$

Where γ is a parameter for gamma correction for a given display device

B.The Coarse to Fine power control mechanism

This section details the proposed algorithm. In the coarse control stage, The mlog of conventional SD-MSR plays a role in enhancing the contrasts of highlights and shadow regions. In other words, contrast in the dark region becomes high by increasing the intensity level of the pixels in the region, and contrast in the bright region also becomes high by decreasing the intensity level of the pixels in the region. However, the increase of the intensity values in the shadow region results in the increase in power consumption for the OLED display. So, for low power consumption as well as contrast enhancement, even in the shadow region, we redefine a so-called power-constrained log (plog) from them log of Eq. (4) as follows

$$plog(I(x, y)) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau \log D \log(\alpha I(x, y) + 1)}{(D - 1) \log(\alpha \tau + 1)} I(x, y) \leq \tau \\ mlog(I(x, y)) I(x, y) > \tau \end{cases}$$

(12)

Therefore, the plog of Eq. (12) has the effect of controlling the increase in power consumption while partially lowering the contrast in the dark region. From Eq.(7) and MSR_s computed by plog, i.e., {R_n}, we can derive the following output image

$$\hat{R}_t = \sum_{n=1}^N g_n \hat{R}_n \quad (13)$$

On the other hand, basing YP on Eq. (11), the power reduction ratio of an input image and its output image is defined as follows

$$p_t = 1 - \frac{YP(\hat{R}_t)}{YP(I)} \quad (14)$$

In this paper, $\bar{R}_n$ can be computed with Eq. (15) as in Eq. (16)

$$f(X) = X^N = \frac{X - m}{M - m} (L - 1) + l \quad (15)$$

Let δ_t denote the difference between p_t and P

$$\delta_t = P - p_t \quad (16)$$

Eq. (17) because such a condition indicates an excess of power reduction over P.

$$\tau_{t+1} = \tau_t + \frac{(D - \tau_t)}{2} \quad (17)$$

we increase τ relatively small as in Eq. (18)

$$\tau_{t+1} = \tau_t + \frac{(D - \tau_t)}{4} \quad (18)$$

So we approach P by decreasing τ relatively small as in Eq. (19).

$$\tau_{t+1} = \tau_t + \tau_t/4 \quad (19)$$

So we rapidly approach P by decreasing τ significantly.

$$\tau_{t+1} = \tau_t + \tau_t/2 \quad (20)$$

In Fine control stage, Since p_t still cannot get close to P through the CCS, we require additional power control. Let δ_t^F denote the difference between the power reduction ratio at the t -th iteration of the fine control stage and P. Initially, δ_0^F is set to the final δ_0^C obtained from the CCS. If $|\delta_t^F| < e$ this FCS terminates. And the output image I is obtained by normalizing the final $\bar{R}_n$ from the previous stage. Here, e indicates the allowable tolerance. If $|\delta_t^F| > e$ a regular FCS begins. In general, the high frequency region of an image is highly involved in details of the image, but its impact on the power of the image is negligible. On the other hand, the low-frequency region is rarely related to image details, but it dominates image power as a whole. So we try to approach P by finely controlling the proportion of

the lowest-band MSR which may have most of the image power. In detail, we control the gain of $\bar{R}_n$ as follows:

$$R^{\wedge} = \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} g_n \bar{R}_n + (g_N + \lambda) \bar{R}_N \quad (21)$$

Where λ indicates a control parameter for the lowest-band MSR, which is updated according to Eq. (22) enables the FCS to approach the target power with little change of contrast

$$\lambda_{t+1} = \lambda_t - \delta_t^F \quad (22)$$

where λ_0 is set to 0. This entire FCS iterates until $|\delta_t^F| < \epsilon$ Finally, the output image I is obtained by normalizing $R^{\wedge}$.

If the input is a video sequence there would be another stage in this algorithm that is Power Control Stage for Video With image sequences, the τ parameter for the current image can be derived from that of the previous image because of high temporal correlation. So, if we know the power reduction ratio of the previous image in advance, we can determine the increase and decrease in τ for the current image. Based on this concept, we determine τ_0 of the next image, i.e., $\tau_{0,next}$ from τ_0 of the current image according to δ_0^E . This helps the CCS in rapidly converging with a reduced number of iterations for video sequences. Since a significant change of τ_0 between adjacent images may cause flickering artifacts due to contrast fluctuation, we limit $\tau_{0,next}$ to $[\tau_0-5, \tau_0+5]$.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation of the proposed algorithm for an image is given in figure(3). There we compared the proposed algorithm with a typical linear algorithm and a power-constrained contrast enhancement proposed in terms of qualitative visual quality. First, Fig (3) is the results of several algorithms for the caps image when P is 10%. Both the proposed algorithm and the PCCE achieve significant contrast enhancement compared to the linear algorithm.

However, the PCCE loses the details in the yellow cap and shows too darkened shadows as seen in Fig.3(c). The proposed algorithm can enhance details while effectively preserving the overall intensity level of the input image. Figure(5) represents the power reduction ratios for a video sequence. We can observe that the proposed algorithm shows consistent power reduction ratio values, irrespectively of frame numbers. On the contrary, the PCCE causes significant fluctuations. Figure(3) is The p log function according to α values in CCS

Figure (3)

Figure (4)

Figure (5)

Figure (6)

The number of iterations according to ϵ in FCS

CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an SD-MSR-based image processing algorithm for fine power management in OLED displays. We designed a power-constrained log perform for effective power saving in dark regions. Using the power-constrained log function for SD-MSR and an Adaptive weighting strategy proper for an input image, we projected a coarse-to-fine power control mechanism for still pictures. Finally, we present a power management theme for a constant power reduction ratio in video sequences by using temporal coherence in video sequences. Experimental results showed that the proposed algorithm provides higher visual quality than previous works, and a consistent power-saving magnitude relation with no the flickering artifact even for video sequences.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Young, "OLEDs—Promises, myths, and TVs" *Inform. Display*, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 14–17, Sep. 2009
- [2] C.-C. Lai and C.-C. Tsai, "Backlight power reduction and image contrast enhancement using adaptive dimming for global backlight applications" *IEEE Trans. Consume. Electron.* vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 669–674, May 2008.
- [3] C. Lee, C. Lee, Y.-Y. Lee, and C.-S. Kim, "Power-constrained contrast enhancement for emissive displays based on histogram equalization" *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 80–93, Jan. 2012.
- [4] D. J. Jobson, Z.-U. Raman, and G. A. Woodell, "A multistage retinex for bridging the gap between color images and the human observation of scenes," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.* vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 965–976, Jul. 1997.
- [5] J. H. Jang, B. Choy, S. D. Kim, and J. B. Ra, "Sub-band decomposed multiscale retinex with space varying gain," *import. IEEE ICIP*, Oct. 2008, pp. 3168–3171.
- [6] C.-H. Lee, L.-H. Chen, and W.-K. Wang, "Image contrast enhancement using classified virtual exposure image fusion," *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.* vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 1253–1261, Nov. 2012.
- [7] S. C. Nercessian, K. A. Panetta, and S. S. Agaian, "Non-linear direct multi-scale image enhancement based on the luminance and contrast masking characteristics of the human visual system," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 3549–3561, Sep. 2013.
- [8] R. Chouhan, R. K. Jha, and P. K. Biswas, "Enhancement of dark and low-contrast images using dynamic stochastic resonance," *IET Image Process.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 174–184, Sep. 2013.

An High Equipped Data Hiding Algorithm Based On Secret Fragment Visible Mosaic Images And Pixel Color Transformations For Secure Image Transmission

Kattam Ramya Rani¹ and G Renuka²

¹M.Tech Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
²Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering
^{1,2} SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.
¹ramyarani47@gmail.com, ²renucherry.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Hiding the data in digital images has been area of interest in the digital image processing domain. Although so much work has been carried out in the literature to resolve the issues like increasing the data capacity, creating the secret image alike of target image but most of the works fails to meet the practical requirements. This paper presents an approach where mosaic image generation has done by dividing the secret image into fragments and transforming their respective color characteristics into corresponding blocks of the target image. Usage of the Pixel color transformations helps to yield the lossless recovered image based on the untransformed color space values. Generation of the key plays an important role to recover the data from the secret image in lossless manner. Finally the same approach can be performed on videos also which helps to eliminate the flickering artifact to achieve the lossless data recovery in motion related videos. The experimental results shows good robust behavior against all incidental and Accidental attacks and compare to the conventional algorithms Performance Evaluation has been increased in a significant way.

Key Words - Color transformation, Mosaic image, Secure image transmission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, images from various sources are frequently utilized and transmitted through the internet for various applications, such as online personal photograph albums, confidential enterprise archives, document storage systems, medical imaging systems and military image databases. These images contain private or confidential information so that they should be protected from leakages during transmissions. Recently, many methods have been proposed for securing image transmission, for which two

common approaches are image encryption and data hiding. Image encryption is a technique that makes use of the natural property of an image, such as high redundancy and strong spatial correlation. The encrypted image is a noise image. However, the encrypted image is a meaningless file, which cannot provide additional information before decryption and may arouse an attacker's attention during transmission due to its randomness in form. An alternative to avoid this problem is data hiding that hides a secret message into a cover image so

that no one can realize the existence of the secret data, in which the data type of the secret message investigated in this paper, is an image.

A main issue of the methods for hiding data in images is the difficulty to embed a large amount of message data into a single image. Specifically, if one wants to hide a secret image into a cover image with the same size, the secret image must be highly compressed in advance. But, for many applications, such as keeping or transmitting medical pictures, military images, legal documents, etc., that are valuable with no allowance of serious distortions, such data compression operations are usually impractical. Moreover, most image compression methods, such as JPEG compression, are not suitable for line drawings and textual graphics, in which sharp contrasts between adjacent pixels are often destructed to become noticeable artifacts. In this paper, a new technique for secure image transmission is proposed which transforms a secret image into a meaningful mosaic image with the same size and looking like a preselected target image. The transformation process is controlled by a secret key, and only with the key a person can recover the secret image nearly losslessly from the mosaic image. The proposed method is inspired by Lai and Tsai, in which a new type of computer art image called secret fragment visible mosaic image, was proposed.

Figure 1 Result yielded by the proposed method. (a) Secret image. (b) Target image. (c)

Secret-fragment-visible mosaic image created from (a) and (b) by the proposed method.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

Since the color characteristics of T and B are totally different from one another, the way to amend their color distributions to form them look alike is that the main issue here color transfer theme in this face t, that converts the color characteristic of an image to be that of another within the $\alpha\beta$ color area. This idea is a solution to the difficulty and is adopted during this paper, except that the RGB color area rather than the $\alpha\beta$ one is employed to reduce the amount of the desired data for recovery of the original secret image. More specifically, let T and B be described as 2 pixel sets $\{p_1, p_2, p_3 \dots p_n\}$ and $\{p'_1, p'_2, \dots, p'_n\}$. Let the color of every p_i be denoted by $((r_i, g_i, b_i))$. which of every p'_i by (r'_i, g'_i, b'_i) . At first, we tend to work out the means and standard deviations of T and B, severally; in every of the 3 color channels R, G, and B by the subsequent formulas:

$$\mu_c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n c_i$$

$$\mu_c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n c'_i \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\sigma_c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (c_i - \mu_c)^2}$$

$$\sigma'_c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (c'_i - \mu'_c)^2} \dots \dots (2)$$

In which c_i and c'_i denote the C-channel values of pixels p_i and p'_i , severally, with and C=R, G, or B. Next, we have a tendency to compute new color values (r'_i, g'_i, b'_i) . For each p_i in T by

$$c_i'' = q_c(c_i - \mu_c) + \mu_c \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

In $q_c = \sigma_c / \sigma_c'$ is the standard deviation quotient and $c=(r, g, \text{ or } b)$. It can be verified easily that the new color mean and variance of the resulting tile image T' are equal to those of B, respectively. To compute the original color values $((r_i, g_i, b_i)$ of p_i from the new ones $((r_i', g_i', b_i')$, we use the following formula which is the inverse of (3)

$$c_i = \frac{1}{q_c} (c_i'' - \mu_c) + \mu_c \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Specifically, for every color channel we tend to enable each of the means of T and B to have 8 bits with its worth within the range of 0 to 255, and also the standard deviation quotient q_c in (3) to have seven bits with its worth within the range of 0.1 to 12.8. That is, each mean is modified to be the closest value within the range of 0 to 255, and each q_c is modified to be the closest value in the range of 0.1 to 12.8. We don't enable q_c to be zero 0 otherwise the first picture element worth cannot be recovered back by (4) for the reason that $1/q_c$ in (4) isn't outlined once $q_c=0$.

a. Choosing Appropriate Target Blocks and Rotating Blocks to Fit Better with Smaller RMSE Value:

In transforming the color characteristic of a tile image T to be that of a corresponding target block B as represented higher than, how to choose an appropriate B for every T is a problem. For this, we use the standard deviation of the colors within the block as a live to pick out the foremost similar for each T. Specially, we type all the tile pictures to make a sequence, S_{tile} , and every one the target blocks to make another, S_{target} , consistent with the typical I values of the quality deviations of the 3 color channels. Then,

we work the primary in S_{tile} into the primary in S_{target} , fit the second in S_{tile} into the second in S_{target} , and so on. Additionally, A further improvement on the color similarity between the resulting tile image T' and the target block B by rotating T' into one of the four directions, 0^0 , 90^0 , 180^0 , and 270^0 , which yields a rotated version of T' with the minimum root mean square error (RMSE) value with respect to B among the four directions for final use to fit T into B.

b. Embedding Information for Secret Image Recovery:

In order to recover the secret image from the mosaic image, we have to embed relevant recovery information into the mosaic image. For this, we adopt a way planned by Coltuc and Chassery and apply it to the smallest amount vital bits of the pixels within the created mosaic image to conduct information embedding. Not like the classical LSB replacement strategies, that substitute LSBs with message bits directly, the reversible distinction mapping technique applies simple integer transformations to pairs of pixel values. Specifically, the method conducts forward and backward integer transformations as follows, respectively, in which (x, y) are a pair of pixel values and (x', y') are the transformed ones

$$x' = 2x - y, \quad y' = 2y - x$$

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3}x' + \frac{1}{3}y' \\ \frac{1}{3}x' + \frac{2}{3}y' \end{bmatrix} \quad Y = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{3}x' + \frac{2}{3}y' \\ \frac{2}{3}x' + \frac{1}{3}y' \end{bmatrix}$$

so far the information required to recover a tile image T which is mapped to a target block B includes: 1) the index of B 2)the optimal rotation angle of T 3) the truncated means of T and B and the standard deviation quotients, of all color channels and 4) the overflow/underflow

residuals. These data items for recovering a tile image T are integrated as a five-component bit stream of the form

$$M = t_1 t_2 \dots t_m r_1 r_2 m_1 m_2 \dots m_{48} q_1 q_2 \dots q_{21} d_1 d_2 \dots d_k$$

In more detail, the numbers of required bits for the five data items in M are discussed below: 1) the index of B need sm bits to represent, with m computed by

$$M = \lceil \log [(Ws \times Hs) / N_T] \rceil$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 3 Original image

Figure 4 Secret image

Figure 5 before embedding mosaic image

Figure 6 after embedding mosaic image

Figure 7 Extracted image

Figure 8 Secret vs Extracted (RMSE)

Figure 9 Secret vs Extracted (Required bits)

Figure 10 Target vs Mosaic (RMSE)

The proposed method has been written on the digital images, in this work images are used as media to hide the secret image by using the an approach where mosaic image generation has done by dividing the secret image into fragments and transforming their respective color characteristics into corresponding blocks of the target image. Usage of the Pixel color transformations helps to yield the lossless recovered image based on the untransformed color space values. So in extension work we did the same algorithm on the digital videos. The approach towards videos is totally different from the images, so algorithm on videos is the contribution to the proposed work.

IV. CONCLUSION

Hiding the data in digital images has been area of interest in the digital image processing domain. This paper presents an approach where mosaic image generation has done by dividing the secret image into fragments and transforming their respective color characteristics into corresponding blocks of the target image. Usage of the Pixel color transformations helps to yield the lossless recovered image based on the untransformed color space values. Generation of the key plays an important role to recover the data from the secret image in lossless manner. Finally the same approach can be performed on videos also which helps to eliminate the flickering artifact to achieve the lossless data recovery in motion related videos. The experimental results shows good robust behavior against all incidental and accidental attacks and compare to the conventional algorithms performance evaluation has been increased in a significant way.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Xiao, X. Liao, and P. Wei, "Analysis and improvement of a chaosbased image encryption algorithm," *Chaos Solit. Fract.*, vol. 40, no. 5, pp. 2191–2199, 2009.
- [2] G. Chen, Y. Mao, and C. K. Chui, "A symmetric image encryption scheme based on 3D chaotic cat maps," *Chaos Solit. Fract.*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 749–761, 2004.
- [3] H. S. Kwok and W. K. S. Tang, "A fast image encryption system based on chaotic maps with finite precision representation," *Chaos Solit. Fract.*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 1518–1529, 2007.
- [4] J. Fridrich, "Symmetric ciphers based on two-dimensional chaotic maps," *Int. J. Bifurcat. Chaos*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1259–1284, 1998.
- [5] L. H. Zhang, X. F. Liao, and X. B. Wang, "An image encryption approach based on chaotic maps," *Chaos Solit. Fract.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 759–765, 2005.
- [6] S. Behnia, A. Akhshani, H. Mahmodi, and A. Akhavan, "A novel algorithm for image encryption based on mixture of chaotic maps," *Chaos Solit. Fract.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 408–419, 2008.
- [7] V. Patidar, N. K. Pareek, G. Purohit, and K. K. Sud, "A robust and secure chaotic standard map based pseudorandom permutation substitution scheme for image encryption," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 284, no. 19, pp. 4331–4339, 2011.

Figure 2 algorithmic flow

VLSI Implementation of Low Complexity MIMO Detection Algorithms

¹Vakulabharanam Ramakrishna and ²Tipparti Anil Kumar, SMIEEE

^{1,2}Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2}SR Engineering College (Autonomous), Warangal, Telangana., India

¹ramakrishna_bharan@yahoo.co.in, ²tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

This paper presents VLSI implementation of low complexity multiple input multiple output (MIMO) detection algorithms which are Maximum Likelihood and Zero Forcing. Initially, the MIMO system structure, the mathematical model and two receiver detection algorithms are presented. Then we investigated the characteristics and performance of typical algorithms and concentrated on VLSI implementation of the system architecture and the two detection algorithms, which can give good performance. Finally, simulation results have been compared with each other in terms of complexity and error performance.

Keywords: VLSI; MIMO, Detection Algorithms, ZF, ML, FPGA, BER, Low Complexity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) is used to describe the multi-antenna wireless communication system, an abstract mathematical model can take advantage of a plurality of transmitter antennas are each independently a transmission signal, and a plurality of antennas at the receiver receive and recover the original message. In MIMO communication system without increasing the transmission bandwidth channel capacity increases exponentially [1]. MIMO technology is the future wireless communication systems to achieve high data rate transmission, to improve transmission quality, an important way to improve the system capacity.

Zero Forcing (ZF) and Maximum Likelihood (ML) detection algorithms are used to separate the spatially multiplexed data units at the receiver [2]. Implementing the design using FPGA is very fast with lower development costs and takes less amount of time. VLSI implementation of the detection algorithms in the MIMO system will turn out to be a key methodology in the future wireless communication system.

This paper is arranged as follows: Section II gives brief overview of system model. Section III presents the detection algorithms like Zero Forcing and Maximum likelihood detection algorithms. Section IV shows the results of Bit Error Rates and also hardware implementation results and section V is conclusion of the paper. This paper investigates the applicability of FPGA system for low complexity MIMO Detection algorithms in effective and economical way.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

Here a MIMO with N_t transmit antennas and N_r receive antennas is considered. A block diagram of system is shown in figure 1.

Figure1. Basic MIMO System Model

Received signal

$$\mathbf{Z}_r = \mathbf{H}_r \mathbf{X}_r + \mathbf{n}_r \quad (1)$$

Where $r=1, 2, 3 \dots R$, R is the number of sub carriers and received signal vector $\mathbf{Z}_r = [\mathbf{Z}_{r1}, \mathbf{Z}_{r2}, \dots, \mathbf{Z}_{rN_t}]^T$, Transmit Signal vector $\mathbf{X}_r = [\mathbf{X}_{r1}, \mathbf{X}_{r2}, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{rN_t}]^T$, $\mathbf{n}_r = [\mathbf{n}_{r1}, \mathbf{n}_{r2}, \dots, \mathbf{n}_{rN_t}]^T$ is the additive noise vector and represents white gaussian noise of variance σ^2 . $\mathbf{H}$ indicates the $N_r \times N_t$ channel matrix. In order to identify the communicated data it would be best to use ML detector [3].

A couple of significant problems exist with planning channel estimators. First one is the preparation of pilot information, which is used as the reference signal handled by both transmitters and receivers. The second trouble is the strategy of an estimator by means of both low complexity as well as great channel tracking potential and also both of these issues are interconnected. MIMO Wireless communication systems require the low complexity and high precision detectors to achieve high data rates with low BER. The channel estimations are generally adopted in MIMO systems to achieve the trade-off between complexity and accuracy.

In the 2×2 MIMO channel model, the number of pilot signals may be 2 When the pilot signal $\mathbf{p}_2 = [1 \ 0]$,

$$\mathbf{r}_1 = \mathbf{H}_{11} \times \mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{H}_{21} \times \mathbf{p}_2 + \mathbf{n}_1 \quad (\mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{0}) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_2 = \mathbf{H}_{12} \times \mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{H}_{22} \times \mathbf{p}_2 + \mathbf{n}_2 \quad (\mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{0}) \quad (3)$$

This does not consider the effect of noise. There are

$$\mathbf{H}_{11} = \mathbf{r}_1 / \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{H}_{21} = \mathbf{r}_1 / \mathbf{p}_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{12} = \mathbf{r}_2 / \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{H}_{22} = \mathbf{r}_2 / \mathbf{p}_2 \quad (5)$$

When the pilot signal $\mathbf{p}_2 = [0 \ 1]$,

Therefore, using the guide structure, the receiving end can estimate the channel $\mathbf{H}$ is:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{11} & \mathbf{H}_{12} \\ \mathbf{H}_{21} & \mathbf{H}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Pilot-based methods [4] are extensively used to approximate the channel properties and extract the received signal. The pilot signal allocated to a specific block, which is directed periodically in time-domain, this type of pilot procedure is particularly appropriate for slow-fading radio

channels. Since the training block comprises all pilots, channel interpolation in frequency domain is not required. So, this kind of pilot scheme is reasonably unresponsive to frequency selectivity. Comb-type pilot system is provides better resistance to fast-fading channels. Since only some sub-carriers contain the pilot signal, the channel response of non-pilot sub-carriers will be estimated by interpolating neighboring pilot sub-channels. Thus the comb-type arrangement is sensitive to frequency selectivity when comparing to the block-type pilot arrangement system. In block-type pilot based channel estimation, OFDM channel estimation symbols are transmitted periodically, in which all sub-carriers are used as pilots [5]. If the channel is constant during the block, there will be no channel estimation error since the pilots are sent at all carriers. The estimation can be performed by using Zero Force, ML, LS, and MMSE.

Detection Algorithms

Maximum Likelihood Detection (MLD)

This is the theoretical optimum detection method can receive diversity gain full access. By the estimation theory, for $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Z}$, $\mathbf{H}$ estimation, maximum likelihood estimation method to construct a cost function $p(\mathbf{H} | \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X})$ so that the cost function to obtain the maximum value of $\mathbf{H}$ is the final estimate

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{H}} \{ p(\mathbf{H} / \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) \} \quad (7)$$

This paper is focused on the 4×4 MIMO system simulation, constellation map of QPSK, at the receiving end using the maximum likelihood detection algorithm is to investigate channel estimation algorithm performance, so when testing using the transmitted signal space uses exhausted search approach to maximum likelihood detection [6], in order to fully demonstrate channel estimation algorithm BER performance.

Zero Forcing Detection (ZF)

Zero forcing detection algorithm is a channel to the reception signal by the inverse matrix of the interference of other users it can be eliminated, but the noise is also multiplied by the inverse of the channel matrix, in general, the channel coefficient matrix is less than 1, then it the inverse is greater than 1, ie to the noise by a factor greater than 1, the noise must be amplified. The zero forcing detection multiplies the received symbol vector $\mathbf{y}$ by an equalization matrix $\mathbf{G}$ i.e.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{G}_{ZF} \mathbf{y} \quad (8)$$

Zero Forcing means that the mutual interference between the layers shall be perfectly suppressed [7].

This is derived from the Moore-Penrose Pseudo Inverse of H

$$G_{ZF} = (H^H H)^{-1} H^H \quad (9)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matlab Simulations

From Figure2 it can be seen that the detection of the ML, when the transmitting and receiving antennas are more, error rate is lower, so that the MIMO communication system can overcome the adverse multipath fading effects, to achieve the reliability of signal transmission, but also can increase the system capacity and hence improves the spectrum efficiency[8].

Figure2. Pilot estimated channel, ML Detection MIMO System 1x1, 2x2, 4x4 Antenna Performance

Figure3. Pilot sequence estimated channel, ZF Testing under, MIMO System 1x1, 2x2, 4x4 Antenna performance comparisons

From figure 3 and figure 4 it can be seen in ZF detection, when the transmitting and receiving antennas, the more the higher the bit error rate, is zero forcing detection algorithm to the reception signal by the inverse of the channel matrix, the other users of its the interference can be eliminated,

but the noise is also multiplied by the inverse of the channel matrix, in general, the channel coefficient matrix is less than 1, then its inverse is greater than 1, that is a noise by a factor of greater than 1, must be amplified noise. So the error rate will increase as the number of antennas increases.

Figure4. Ideal channel, ZF detection 1x1, 2x2, 4x4 MIMO antenna system error rate

From the results which are shown in figure 5 and 6 it can be seen, the use of ML detection, the ideal channel and the estimated channel error rate overall trend is same, but the ideal channel bit error rate than the estimated channel bit error rate is low, indicating that based on the pilot channel estimation in MIMO communication system is feasible.

Using ZF detection, ideal channel and estimated channel error rate overall trend the same, but the ideal channel bit error rate than estimated channel bit error rate is high, it is generally not recommended for pilot-based channel estimation using ZF detection algorithm[9].

Figure5. Estimate the channel,MLD And ZFTesting under 4x4Antenna MIMOComparative analysis of the bit error rate curve

It can be seen from the results of figure 5 and figure 6, when using the ideal channel, MLD algorithm error rate than the ZF algorithm is small, and the same general trend, but at high SNR part MLD algorithm BER than the ZF algorithm is obviously much lower , indicating that global search algorithm MLD excellent performance.

Figure6. Ideal channel, MIMO 4x4 antenna system MLD detection and ZF detection performance comparison

When using the estimated channel, MLD algorithm and the ZF algorithm BER less, where MLD algorithm is slightly lower SNR. From the computational point of view and run time, when the num = 256, loop = 1000, the use of a total of about MLD algorithm 1200s, the use ZF algorithm needs a total time of about 180s. MLD algorithm is much larger than the amount of computation ZF algorithm, the time is also longer than the ZF algorithm.

FPGA Implementation

The architecture was designed concentrated on great performance and low cost. The architecture was defined in Hardware Description Language and synthesized to Xilinx Virtex 4 FPGAs. The synthesis results demonstrate that the architecture is capable to accomplish processing at faster rates and attains the real-time requirements. The architecture is consuming fewer resources when compared to related works [10].

Figure7. ML device utilization summary for Virtex 4, 4vsx25ff668-12 Device

Figure8. ZF device utilization summary

4. CONCLUSION

Through this approach, we know that the multipath MIMO wireless channel with transmitter and receiver as a whole is optimized to achieve high communication capacity and spectrum utilization. This is a near-optimal joint airspace domain diversity and interference cancellation processing. This is started through the establishment of MIMO communication system, and based on pilot estimates the channel H, and then using the estimated channel respectively MLD and Zero-forcing signal detection, and finally the application of MATLAB on the system simulation, drawing, observation graphics, simulation results BER analysis. From the above process for the project, we further understand the performance of MIMO system outstanding advantages for the future laid the foundation for learning 4G communications.

REFERENCES

1. Andrea Goldsmith, Syed Ali Jafar, Nihar Jindal, and riram Vishwanath, "Capacity Limits of MIMO Channels" Proc.IEEE J. Selected areas in Comm., Vol.21, No.5, pp.684-702, Jun.2003.
2. G. Tsoulos, MIMO system technology for wireless communication CRC press, 2006,pp.105-123.
3. Christoph Windpassinger and Robert F.H.Fischer, "Low-Complexity Near-Maximum-Likelihood Detection and Precoding for MIMO Systems using Lattice Reduction," Proc. IEEE Information Theory Workshop, Paris, France, pp. 345–348, March 2003.
4. Ye. Li, Gordon. Stüber, Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing for Wireless Communications, Springer, 2006.pp119-126.
5. S. Coleri, M. Ergen, A. Puri, "Channel estimation techniques based on pilot arrangement in OFDM systems". Porc.IEEE Trans. Broadcasting, vol. 48, pp. 223-229, Sept. 2002.
6. K.-K. Wong and A. Paulraj, "Efficient near maximum-likelihood detection for underdetermined MIMO antenna systems using a geometrical approach," EURASIP J. Wireless Commun. and Networking, Oct.2007. doi.10.1155/2007/84265.
7. D. Shiu and J.M. Kahn. "Layered Space-Time Codes for Wireless Communications using Multiple Transmit Antennas". Proc.IEEE Int.Conf.Comm. (ICC'99), Vancouver, B.C. June 6-10 1999.
8. G.V.V.Sharma, V.Ganwani, U.B.Desai and S.N.Merchant, "Performance Analysis of Maximum Likelihood Detection for Decode and Forward MIMO Relay Channels in Rayleigh Fading", IEEE Trans.Wireless Comm.,Vol9,No.9,pp2880-2889, Sept 2010.
9. C. Wang et al., "On the performance of the MIMO zero-forcing receiver in the presence of channel estimation error," IEEE Trans. Wireless Comm., vol. 6, pp. 805–810, 2007.
10. Le Sun, Wei Yang and Hu Huang, "FPGA Implementation of V-BLAST Detection Algorithm In MIMO System," Proc.IEEE Youth Conf.(YC-ICT'09), pp. 134- 137,2009.

Multuser Detection using Particle Swarm Optimization over GK Fading Channels in Laplace Noise

Srinivasa Rao Vempati ¹, Habibulla Khan ² and Anil Kumar Tipparti ³

^{1,2,3}Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹KITS for Women, Kodad, India - 508206.

²KL University, Vaddeswaram, India- 522502

³SR Engineering College, Warangal, India- 506 371

¹ vsrao@ieee.org, ² habibulla@rediffmail.com, ³ tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

The direct sequence-code division multiple accesses (DS-CDMA) signals are transmitted over multipath channels that introduce fading and shadowing. Combined effect of multipath fading and shadowing along with multiple access interference (MAI) and inter-symbol interference (ISI) worsens the system performance. Further, experimental results have confirmed the presence of impulsive noise in wireless mobile communication channels. Hence, this paper presents a particle swarm optimization (PSO) based multuser detection technique for DS-CDMA systems over generalized- K (GK) fading channels in presence of impulsive noise modeled by Laplace distribution. Maximal ratio combining (MRC) receive diversity is also incorporated to mitigate the effects of fading and shadowing. Performance of proposed M -estimator based detector is also studied by evaluating average error rate. Simulation results reveal that the proposed M -estimator based detector performs better in the presence of fading, shadowing and heavy-tailed impulsive noise when compared to least squares, Huber and Hampel M -estimator based detectors.

Keyword:diversity combining, fading channel, GK distribution, Laplace noise, multuser detection, probability of error, particle swarm optimization, shadowing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has explored the potential benefits of multuser detection for code division multiple access (CDMA) communication systems with present multiple access interference (MAI) [1]. These optimal multuser detectors have led to the developments of the various linear multuser detectors with Gaussian noise though various experimental results have confirmed that many realistic channels are impulsive in nature [2], [3]. Lately, the problem of robust multuser detection in non-Gaussian channels has been addressed in the literature [4], [5], [6], which were developed based on the Huber, Hampel, and a new M -estimator (modified Hampel), respectively. Since CDMA transmissions are frequently made over

channels that exhibit fading, it is of interest to design receivers that take this fading behavior of the channel in to account [3]. Robust multuser detection for synchronous DS-CDMA system with maximal ratio combiner (MRC) receive diversity over Nakagami- m fading channels is presented in [7] by assuming that the modulation is binary PSK (BPSK). But, the simultaneous presence of multipath fading and shadowing leads to worsening the wireless channels [8]. Recently, the performance of M -decorrelator in simultaneous presence of fading and shadowing with impulsive noise is presented in [9] and by incorporating MRC diversity in [10]. Implementation of particle swarm optimization (PSO) based M -decorrelator in Nakagami- m fading

channels for the demodulation of DPSK signals is presented in [11]. The PSO-based multiuser detection for DS-CDMA system over generalized-K (GK) fading channels with impulsive noise, which is modeled by well known Gaussian mixture model, is presented in [12] by incorporating MRC receive-diversity. White Laplace noise model has found application in [13]. The interest in Laplace white noise has been renewed by recent research in ultra-wide bandwidth (UWB) wireless systems [13], due to the UWB multi-user interference rate selection criterion. Hence, in this paper, PSO-based MUD over GK fading channel in the presence of Laplace noise is considered.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows: DS-CDMA system over multipath fading channel in Laplace noise is presented in Section II. Section III presents the GK fading channel with MRC receive diversity. Influence function of the proposed M -estimator, derivation of an approximate closed-form expression for average probability of error of an M -decorrelator and PSO based M -decorrelator is presented in Section IV. Section V presents the simulation results to study the performance of proposed M -decorrelator in fading and shadowing with Laplace noise. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

An L -user CDMA system, where each user transmits information by modulating a signature sequence over a single-path Nakagami- m fading channel, is considered in this paper. The received signal over one symbol duration can be modeled as [3]

$$r(t) = \Re \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} b_l(i) \alpha_l(t) e^{j\theta_l(t)} s_l(t - iT_s - \tau_l) \right\} + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part, M is the number of data symbols per user in the data frame of interest, T_s is the symbol interval, $\alpha_l(t)$ is the time-varying fading gain of the l^{th} user's channel, $\theta_l(t)$ is the time-varying phase of the l^{th} user's channel, $b_l(i)$ is the i^{th} bit of the l^{th} user, $s_l(t)$ is the normalized signaling waveform of the l^{th} user and $n(t)$ is assumed as a zero-mean complex non-Gaussian noise. It is assumed that the signaling constellation consists of non-orthogonal signals given by [3]

$$s_l(t) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} a_l(t) e^{j(\omega_c t + \theta_l)} & \text{for } t \in [0, T_s] \\ 0 & \text{for } t \notin [0, T_s] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$, θ_l is the phase of the l^{th} user relative to some reference, ω_c is the common carrier frequency, and the spreading waveforms, $a_l(t)$, are of the form

$$a_l(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n^l u_{T_c}(t - (n-1)T_c) \quad (3)$$

where $\{a_n^l\}_{n=1}^N$ is a signature sequence of +1s and -1s assigned to the l^{th} user user, and $u_{T_c}(t)$ is a unit-amplitude pulse of duration T_c with $T_s = NT_c$. At the receiver, the received signal $r(t)$ is first filtered by a chip-matched filter and then sampled at the chip rate, $1/T_c$. The resulting discrete-time signal sample corresponding to the n^{th} chip of the i^{th} symbol is given by [3]

$$r_n(i) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{T_c}} \int_{iT_s + nT_c}^{iT_s + (n+1)T_c} r(t) e^{-j\omega_c t} dt, n = 1 \dots N. \quad (4)$$

For synchronous case (i.e., $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots = \tau_L = 0$), assuming that the fading process for each user varies at a slower rate that the magnitude and phase can taken to be constant over the duration of a bit, (4) can be expressed in matrix notation as [3]

$$\mathbf{r}(i) = \mathbf{A}\boldsymbol{\theta}(i) + \mathbf{w}(i) \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{r}(i) \square [r_1(i), \dots, r_N(i)]^T \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{w}(i) \square [w_1(i), \dots, w_N(i)]^T \quad (7)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}(i) \square \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [b_1(i)g_1(i), \dots, b_L(i)g_L(i)]^T \quad (8)$$

with $w_n(i)$ is a sequence of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) Laplace random variables with probability density function (PDF) of the form

$$f(x; c, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2c} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - \lambda|}{c}\right) \quad (9)$$

where λ is the location parameter and c is the shape parameter and is related to the variance of the variable as $c^2 = \sigma^2 / 2$. It is assumed that the l^{th} user employs binary phase shift keying (BPSK) modulation to transmit the data bits $b_l \in [-1, 1]$ with equal probability and a symbol rate $1/T_s$.

III. GK FADING CHANNEL WITH MRC DIVERSITY

It is assumed that the signal of each user arrives at the receiver through an independent, single-path fading channel. For the shadowed fading channels, $\alpha_l(i)$ are i.i.d. random variables with GK distribution given by [8]

$$p_{\alpha}(\alpha_l) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu} \alpha_l^{\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1} K_{m-\mu} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \alpha_l \right) \quad (10)$$

where, m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel, $K_{\xi}(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [10]. Assuming that the fading is mitigated through D -branch MRC, the output of maximal ratio combiner can be written as [8, 11]

$$R = \sum_{j=1}^D \alpha_j \quad (11)$$

where α are i.i.d. GK distributed random variables each having a PDF of the form (10). The PDF of R , with multipath fading and shadowing from branch to branch are distinct, is given by [8]

$$p_R(r) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m_m)\Gamma(\mu_m)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m_m+\mu_m} r^{\frac{m_m+\mu_m}{2}-1} K_{m_m-\mu_m} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_0}} r \right)$$

where

$$m_m = Dm + (D-1) \left[\frac{-0.127-0.95m-0.0058\mu}{1+0.00124m+0.98\mu} \right] \quad (13)$$

and

$$\mu_m = D\mu \quad (14)$$

IV. AVERAGE PROBABILITY OF ERROR OF M -DECORRELATOR

In this section, the proposed M -estimator is presented and the average probability of error is derived for a single-path shadowed fading channel.

A. M -estimator

An M -estimator is, a generalization of usual maximum likelihood estimates, used to estimate the unknown parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_L$ (where $\theta = Ab$) by minimizing a sum of function $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [4]

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathfrak{R}^L} \sum_{j=1}^N \rho \left(r_j - \sum_{l=1}^L s_j^l \theta_l \right) \quad (15)$$

where ρ is a symmetric, positive-definite function with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square and N is the processing gain. An influence function $\psi(\cdot) = \rho'(\cdot)$ is proposed (as shown in Fig. 1 along with other influence functions), such that it yields a solution that is not sensitive to outlying measurements, as [6]

$$\psi_{PRO}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{for } |x| \leq a \\ a \operatorname{sgn}(x) & \text{for } a < |x| \leq b \\ \frac{a}{b} x \exp \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{b^2} \right) & \text{for } |x| > b \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where the choice of the constants a and b depends on the robustness measures.

Fig. 1. Influence functions of (a) the linear decorrelating detector, (b) Huber estimator, (c) Hampel estimator, and (d) the proposed estimator.

B. Average probability of error

The asymptotic probability of error for the class of decorrelating detectors, for large processing gain N , is given by [4]

$$P_e^I \equiv \Pr(\hat{\theta}_l < 0 | \theta_l > 0) = Q \left(\frac{A_l}{v \sqrt{[\mathbf{R}^{-1}]_{ll}}} \right) \quad (17)$$

where $Q(x)$ is the Gaussian Q -function [11],

$$v^2 = \frac{\int \psi^2(u) f(u) du}{\left[\int \psi'(u) f(u) du \right]^2} \quad (18)$$

and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S}$ with $\mathbf{S}$ is an $N \times L$ matrix of columns a_l . Average probability of error can be obtained by averaging the conditional probability of error (17) over the PDF, (12), of maximal ratio combiner output as

$$\bar{P}_e^1 = F \cdot \int_0^\infty x^{\left(\frac{m_m + \mu_m - 1}{2}\right)} Q\left(\frac{x}{v \sqrt{\left[\mathbf{R}^{-1}\right]_{11}}}\right) K_{m_m - \mu_m}\left(2 \sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_0}} x\right) dx \quad (19)$$

where $F = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m_m) \Gamma(\mu_m)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_0}}\right)^{m_m + \mu_m}$. Using the well known upper-bound approximation, called Chernoff bound, to $Q(x)$, given by

$$Q(x) \leq \frac{1}{2} e^{-x^2/2} \quad (20)$$

the integral of (19) can be expressed as

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\left(\frac{m_m + \mu_m - 1}{2}\right)} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{v^2 \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1}\right]_{11}}\right) K_{m_m - \mu_m}\left(2 \sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_0}} x\right) dx$$

Now, by using [Eq. 6.631.3, 10] to evaluate the integral (21), the average probability of error can be derived as [9]

$$\bar{P}_e^1 = F \cdot \frac{1}{2} \xi^{-0.5} \beta^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{1+d+l}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1-d+l}{2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\beta^2}{8\xi}\right) W_{-0.5, d}\left(\frac{\beta^2}{4\xi}\right) \quad (22)$$

where $d = m_m - \mu_m$, $l = \frac{m_m + \mu_m}{2} - 1$, $\xi = \frac{1}{v^2 \left[\mathbf{R}^{-1}\right]_{11}}$

and $\beta = 2 \sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_0}}$ and $W_{\lambda, \gamma}(\cdot)$ is the Whittaker function [9].

C. PSO based M-decorrelator

PSO is a swarm intelligence method for global optimization modeled after the social behavior of bird flocking and fish schooling [15]. In PSO algorithm the solution search is conducted using a population of individual particles, where each particle represents a candidate solution to the optimization problem (15). Each particle keeps track of the position of its *individual best* solution (called as

pbest), $\mathbf{p}_d^{best} = [p_{d_1}^{best}, \dots, p_{d_L}^{best}]$ and the overall *global best* solution (called as *gbest*), $\mathbf{g}^{best} = [g_1^{best}, \dots, g_L^{best}]$ among *pbests* of all the particles in the population represented as $\mathbf{p}_d^i = [p_{d_1}^i, \dots, p_{d_L}^i]$, where $\mathbf{p}_d^i$ is the d^{th} particle in the i^{th} iteration, $d = 1, 2, \dots, N_p$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{max}$, N_p is the number of particles, and N_{max} is the maximum number of iterations. Corresponding to each position, the particle velocity is $\mathbf{v}_d^i = [v_{d_1}^i, \dots, v_{d_L}^i]$ [15], [16]. The steps involved in the PSO based M-decorrelating detector's implementation are [11], [15], [17]:

Step1: Compute the decorrelating detector output, $\mathbf{\theta}^0 = \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{r}$. Here, $\mathbf{R}(\square \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A} / N)$ is the normalized cross-correlation matrix of signature waveforms of all users.

Step 2: Initialization: The output of decorrelating detector is taken as input first particle $\mathbf{d}_1^0 = \mathbf{\theta}_1^0$.

Step 3: Fitness evaluation: The objective function (3) is used to find the fitness vector by substituting residuals. Local best position $\mathbf{p}_d^{best}$ is recorded by looking at the history of each particle and the particle with lowest fitness is taken as $\mathbf{g}^{best}$ of the population. (21)

Step 4: Update the inertia weight by using the decrement function $w^i = \beta w^{i-1}$, where $\beta < 1$ is the decrement constant.

Step 5: Update the particle velocity by using the relations

$$\mathbf{v}_d^{i+1} = w^{i+1} \times \mathbf{v}_d^i + c_1 \times \mu_1 \times (\mathbf{p}_d^{best} - \mathbf{p}_d^i) + c_2 \times \mu_2 \times (\mathbf{g}^{best} - \mathbf{p}_d^i) \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_d^{i+1} = \mathbf{p}_d^i + \mathbf{v}_d^{i+1}$$

where c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration constants representing the weighting of the stochastic acceleration terms to pull the particle to *pbest* and *gbest*. μ_1 and μ_2 are random numbers that are uniformly distributed between 0 and 1. Particle position is updated according to (6). Particle velocity is limited by the maximum velocity $\mathbf{v}^{\max} = [v_1^{\max}, \dots, v_2^{\max}]$.

Step 6: The individual best particle position is updated by following rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } F(\mathbf{p}_d^i) \leq F(\mathbf{p}_d^{best}) \\ \text{then } \mathbf{p}_d^{best} = \mathbf{p}_d^i \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Step 7: $\mathbf{g}^{best}$ is the global best particle position among all the individual best particle positions $\mathbf{p}_d^i$ at the i^{th} iteration such that $F(\mathbf{g}^{best}) \leq F(\mathbf{p}_d^i)$.

Step 8: The above steps are repeated until the maximum number of iterations has been reached.

The computed $\mathbf{g}^{best}$ value is used to evaluate average probability of error (22).

TABLE
PSO Parameters used for Simulation

Parameter	Value
Number of particles, N_p	20
Maximum number of iterations, N_{max}	100
Acceleration constants C_1 and C_2	2
Maximum velocity of the particles $ v_l^{max} $ for all users	2
Initial inertial weight, w	1
Decrement constant, β	0.99

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the performance of M -decorrelator is presented by computing (22) for different values of order of diversity i.e., $D = 2$ and $D = 4$. It is assumed that $m = 1.4$, $\mu = 2$ and $\Omega = 10$ dB in the simulations. Evolutionary behavior of M -decorrelator is presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 4. Performance of M -decorrelator with different influence functions is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5. In Fig. 3, the average probability of error versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to the user 1 under perfect power control of a synchronous DS-CDMA system with six users ($L = 6$) and a processing gain, $N = 31$ is plotted for Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.5$). In Fig. 5, the average probability of error is plotted for Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.95$). Simulation results show that the proposed M -estimator based detector performs well compared to linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors.

Fig. 2 .Evolution of objective function (15) with respect to number of iterations with linear decorrelating detector (least squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and Proposed M -estimator in Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.5$), $N = 31$.

Fig. 3. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear decorrelating detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in synchronous DS-CDMA channel with Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.5$), $N = 31$.

Fig. 4. Evolution of objective function (15) with respect to number of iterations with linear decorrelating detector (least squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and Proposed M -estimator in Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.95$), $N = 31$.

Fig. 5. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear decorrelating detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in synchronous DS-CDMA channel with Laplace noise ($\sigma = 0.95$), $N = 31$.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The PSO based multiuser detection technique for DS-CDMA systems over GK fading channels under Laplace noise environment is presented. An approximate closed-form expression for average probability of error of the M -decorrelator to detect BPSK signals are derived by incorporating MRC

receive diversity. An M -estimator based multiuser detector is proposed and its performance is analyzed by computing average probability of error using the expression derived. Simulation results show that the proposed multiuser detector offers significant performance gain over the linear multiuser detector and the minimax decorrelating detector with Huber and Hampel M -estimators, in Laplace noise.

REFERENCES

1. S. Verdú, *Multiuser Detection*, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, U.K., 1998.
2. A.M. Zoubir, V. Koivunen, Y. Chakhchoukh and M. Muma, "Robust Estimation in Signal Processing: A Tutorial-Style Treatment of Fundamental Concepts," *Signal Processing Magazine, IEEE*, vol.29, no.4, pp.61-80, Jul. 2012.
3. H. V. Poor and M. Tanda, "Multiuser Detection in flat fading non-Gaussian channels," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol.50, no.11, pp. 1769-1777, Nov. 2002.
4. X. Wang and H. V. Poor, "Robust multiuser detection in non-Gaussian channels," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 289-305, Feb. 1999.
5. T. A. Kumar, K. D. Rao and M.N.S. Swamy, "A robust technique for multiuser detection in non-Gaussian channels," in *Proc. 47th Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems*, vol. 3, pp. iii-247-50, vol. 3, 25-28, Jul. 2004.
6. T. A. Kumar and K. D. Rao, "Improved robust techniques for multiuser detection in non-Gaussian channels", *Circuits Systems and Signal Processing J.*, vol. 25, no. 4, 2006.
7. V. S. Rao, P. V. Kumar, S. Balaji, Habibulla Khan and T. A. Kumar, "Robust multiuser detection in synchronous DS-CDMA system with MRC receive diversity over Nakagami-m fading channel", *Advanced Engineering Forum Smart Technologies for Communications*, vol. 4, pp. 43-50, Jun. 2012.
8. P. M. Shankar, "Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC) in Shadowed Fading Channels in Presence of Shadowed Fading Cochannel Interference(CCI)," *Wireless Pers Commun J.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp.15-25, 2013.
9. V. S. Rao, Habibulla Khan and T. A. Kumar, "Multiuser detection in shadowed fading channels with impulsive noise", *Proc. of Int. Conf. on Emerging Trends in Engg. and Tech (ICETET 2014).*, vol. , pp. 36-40, 29-30 Sep. 2014.

10. V. S. Rao, Habibulla Khan and T. A. Kumar, "Multiuser Detection over Generalized-K Fading Channels with MRC Receive Diversity in Presence of Impulsive Noise", *Proc. of Int. Conf. on Emerging Trends in Electr. and Telecommun (ICETET 2014)*, vol. , pp. 17-24, 13-14 Dec. 2014.
 11. P. V. Kumar, V. S. Rao, Habibulla Khan and T. A. Kumar, "Multiuser Detection for DS-CDMA Systems over Nakagami- m Fading Channels using Particle Swarm Optimization", *Proc. of IEEE 9th Int. Colloq. on Signal Processing and its Applications (CSPA 2013)*, vol. , pp. 1-5, 08-10 Mar. 2013.
 12. V. S. Rao, Habibulla Khan and T. A. Kumar, "PSO based multiuser detection over GK fading channels with MRC receive diversity in impulsive noise", *Int. J. of Engg. and Tech.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 631-639, Apr/May. 2015.
 13. G. Bartoli, N. C. Beaulieu, R. Fantacci, and D. Marabissi, "Optimal Data Rate for Reliable Packet Communications in Laplace Noise", *IEEE Commun., Lett.*, vol. 18, no. 1, Jan. 2014.
 14. I. S. Gradshteyn and I. M. Ryzhik, *Table of Integrals, Series, and Products*, Academic Press, Boston, MA, 2007.
 15. K.K. Soo, Y.M. Siu, W.S. Chan, L. Yang and R.S. Chen, "Particle-Swarm-Optimization-Based Multiuser Detector for CDMA Communications," *IEEE Trans., Veh. Technol.*, vol.56, no.5, pp.3006-3013, Sep. 2007..
 16. J-C. Chang, "Robust blind multiuser detection based on PSO algorithm in the mismatch environment of receiver spreading codes," *Comput Electr Eng*, 2012, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2012.08.002>.
 17. X. Wu, T.C. Chuah, B.S. Sharif and O.R. Hinton, "Adaptive robust detection for CDMA using a genetic algorithm," *IEE Proc.-Commun.*, vol. 150, no. 6, pp. 437-444, Dec. 2003.
- currently working towards his Ph.D. in Electronics and Communication Engineering at KL University, AP, India. Mr. Vempati is a member of IEEE, a member of IEEE Signal Processing Society, a Fellow of IETE and also a Life member of ISTE. His research areas of interest include Multiuser Detection, Embedded Systems, and Digital Signal Processing.
2. Dr. H. Khan was born in India in 1962. He received his B.Tech., degree from Nagarjuna University, AP, India, in the year 1984, M.Tech., degree in 1987 from CIT, Coimbatore, India. Presently, Dr. Khan is working as Professor and Head of Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, KL University, AP, India. He has more than 40 National/International Journal/Conference papers in his credit. Dr. Khan is a Fellow of IETE, a Member of IE and a Member of SEMCE. He is also a member of ISTE. His research areas of interest include Antenna System Design, Microwave Engineering, Electromagnetics and RF System Design.
 3. Dr. Anil K. Tipparti was born in India in 1974. He received his B.E., degree from Osmania University, AP, India, in the year 1995, M.Tech., degree in 2002 from National Institute of Technology Kurukshethra, India. Presently, Dr. Tipparti is working as Professor of Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India. Dr. Tipparti is a Senior Member of IEEE, a member of IEEE Communications Society. He is also a member of ISTE. He has published more than 50 research papers in International Journals and Proceedings of International Conferences. He authored a book *Networks and Transmission Lines*, Pearson Education, New Delhi, 2004. His research areas of interest include Robust Statistics, Digital Communications, Multiuser Communications Theory, Digital Signal Processing, Detection and Estimation Theory, Statistical Signal Processing and Adaptive Signal Processing.

AUTHOR PROFILE

1. Srinivasa R. Vempati was born in India in 1969. He received his B.Tech., degree from Nagarjuna University, Guntur, India, in the year 1991, M.Tech., degree in 2004 from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad, A.P., India. Presently, Mr. Vempati is serving as Associate Professor of Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, KITS for Women, Kodad, Telangana, India. He is

Outage Probability Analysis of Multipath Fading Channels in Long Term Evolution-LTE

¹Patteti Krishna, ²Tipparti Anil Kumar and ³Kalitkar Kishan

^{1,2}Department of ECE, SVS Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana, India

³Department of ECE, Vaagdevi College of Engineering, Warangal, Telangana, India
kpatteti@gmail.com, tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in, prof_kkr@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

3rd Generation Partnership Projects Long Term Evolution (3GPP-LTE) is a new standard for mobile broadband access that will meet the throughput and coverage requirements of a fourth generation cellular systems. The key goals for this evolution are increased peak data rate, improved spectrum efficiency, improved coverage and reduced latency. There are two typical ways to improve and measure a wireless communication system performance, which are bit error rate (BER and P (e)) and outage probability (Pout). In this paper, we focus on reducing Pout to improve our system performance. The outage performance method is based on channel capacity and mutual information.

Keywords: LTE; BER; Fading Channels; Outage Probability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fourth generation (4G) Long Term Evolution-LTE wireless cellular communication systems must provide bandwidth-efficient, robust communication with low latency and supporting multiple users on broad band wireless channels. Since time varying channel conditions and thus time-varying channel capacity is an important features of 4G mobile communication systems and any future wireless communication systems, these systems should exhibit a high degree of adaptively on many levels in order to reach these goals. LTE is provides to improve throughput and spectral efficiency along with reducing the latency. The peak data rate requirement of LTE is 100Mbps for downlink and 50 Mbps for uplink. This can be achieved using a scalable bandwidth, multiple antenna elements and link adaptation. The bandwidth in LTE can vary from 1.4 MHz to 20MHz. LTE is also an Internet Protocol (IP)-packet based system with higher data

rates and lower packet delay than previous generations [1-3].

Outage Probability is a key performance metric of wireless communication systems under co-channel interference (CCI). Outage occurs when the channel capacity is less than the transmission rate R , i.e. $\log(1 + SNR|h|^2) < R$ hence, the main idea of the performance improvement is increasing the channel capacity, which can be achieved by several transmission techniques such as LTE.

In this paper organized as follows, Section II explains about the statistical modeling of different fading channels, outage Probability analysis of fading channels explained in Section III and conclusion in section IV.

2. STATISTICAL MODELLING OF FADING CHANNELS

To understand wireless communications, it is necessary to explore what happens to the signal as it travels from the transmitter to the receiver. One of

the important aspects of this path between the transmitter and receiver is the occurrence of fading. The RF (radio frequency) signals with appropriate statistical properties can readily be simulated. Statistical testing can subsequently be used to establish the validity of the fading models frequently used in wireless systems.

Capacity of communication channels is the maximum data rate that can be transmitted over the channels such that arbitrary tolerable small error probabilities can be achieved. The channel capacity concept was initially defined by Shannon. Shannon defined the capacity in terms of mutual information as the maximum mutual information that can be achieved between the input and output of the channel.

Now let us consider the system capacity of the faded channel in the channel model is

$$y[n] = h[n]x[n] + w[n] \quad (1)$$

Where $h[n]$ represents the fading gain in the channel. Fading gain is modeled depending on different fading channels. $x[n]$ Represent the transmitted signal and $w[n]$ a zero mean gaussian noise with variance and identically and independently distributed (iid) with respect to time.

The capacity of the AWGN Channel is

$$C_{awgn} = \log(1 + SNR) \text{ Bits/s/Hz} \quad (2)$$

In Rayleigh fading channels fading gain is assumed to be random but constant over time and delay constraint is small compared to the channel coherence time, the capacity of the channel can be written

$$C = \log(1 + |h|^2 SNR) \text{ Bits/s/Hz} \quad (3)$$

A system is said to be outage if the transmitter sends data rate R is larger than the Channel capacity. Hence outage Probability is defined as follow

$$P_{out} = \Pr[C < R] = \Pr[\log(1 + |h|^2 SNR) < R] \quad (4)$$

A. Rayleigh Fading

The mobile antenna, instead of receiving the signal over one line-of-sight path, receives a number of

reflected and scattered waves, as shown in Fig.1. Because of the varying path lengths, the phases are random, and consequently, the instantaneous received power becomes a random variable. In the case of an unmodulated carrier, the transmitted signal at frequency ω_c reaches the receiver via a number of paths, the i^{th} path having an amplitude a_i , and a phase ϕ_i . If we assume that there is no direct path or line-of sight (LOS) component, the received signal $s(t)$ can be expressed as

$$s(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \cos(\omega_c t + \phi_i) \quad (5)$$

The phase ϕ_i depends on the varying path lengths, changing by 2π when the path length changes by a wavelength. Therefore, the phases are uniformly distributed over $[0, 2\pi]$. When there is relative motion between the transmitter and the receiver, eqn. (5) must be modified to include the effects of motion induced frequency and phase shifts. Let the i^{th} reflected wave with amplitude a_i and phase ϕ_i arrive at the receiver from an angle ψ_i relative to the direction of motion of the antenna. The Doppler shift of this wave is given by

$$\omega_{d_i} = \frac{\omega_c v}{c} \cos \psi_i \quad (6)$$

where v is the velocity of the mobile, c is the speed of light (3×10^8 m/s), and the ψ_i 's are uniformly distributed over $[0, 2\pi]$. The received signal $s(t)$ can now be written as

$$s(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \cos(\omega_c t + \omega_{d_i} t + \phi_i) \quad (7)$$

Expressing the signal in phase and quadrature form, eqn. (3) can be written as

$$s(t) = I(t) \cos \omega_c t - Q(t) \sin \omega_c t \quad (8)$$

where the in phase and quadrature components are respectively given as

$$I(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \cos(\omega_{d_i} t + \phi_i) \quad (9)$$

$$Q(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \sin(\omega_{d_i} t + \phi_i) \quad (10)$$

The envelope R is given by

$$R = \sqrt{[I(t)]^2 + [Q(t)]^2} \quad (11)$$

When N is large, the in phase and quadrature components will be Gaussian [5]. The probability density function (pdf) of the received signal envelope, $f(r)$, can be shown to be Rayleigh given by

$$f(r) = \frac{r}{\sigma^2} \exp\left\{-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\}, \quad r \geq 0 \quad (12)$$

Fig.1. Mechanism of radio propagation in a mobile environment. A number of indirect paths and a line-of-sight path are shown

Varying the number of paths, it can be seen that the fading envelope in the absence of a line-of-sight path fits the Rayleigh distribution for as few as six paths. This was established by conducting chi-square tests for different values of N. Figure 2 shows the RF signals and envelopes for the case of a stationary mobile unit (N=10). The Rayleigh faded RF signal (Figure 2a) and envelope (Figure 2c) show that the signal strengths can fall below the average value (shown by the horizontal line in Figure 2c).

B. Rician Fading

The Rician distribution is observed when, in addition to the multipath components, there exists a direct path between the transmitter and the receiver. Such a direct path or line-of-sight component is shown in Fig.1. In the presence of such a path, the transmitted signal given in eqn. (3) can be written as

$$s(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} a_i \cos(\omega_c t + \omega_{d_i} t + \phi_i) + k_d \cos(\omega_c t + \omega_d t) \quad (13)$$

Where the constant k_d is the strength of the direct component, ω_i is the Doppler shift along the LOS path, and ω_{d_i} are the Doppler shifts along the indirect paths given by equation (2). The envelope in this case has a Rician density function given by [5]

$$f(r) = \frac{r}{\sigma^2} \exp\left\{-\frac{r^2 + k_d^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\} I_0\left(\frac{rk_d}{\sigma^2}\right), \quad r \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

Where $I_0()$ is the 0th order modified Bessel function of the first kind. The cumulative distribution of the Rician random variable is given as

$$F(r) = 1 - Q\left(\frac{k_d}{\sigma}, \frac{r}{\sigma}\right), \quad r \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

Where $Q(.)$ is the Marcum's Q function [4 &6]. The Rician distribution is often described in terms of the Rician factor K, defined as the ratio between the deterministic signal power (from the direct path) and the diffuse signal power (from the indirect paths). K is usually expressed in decibels as

$$K(dB) = 10 \log_{10}\left(\frac{k_d^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (16)$$

In equation (16), if k_d goes to zero (or if $k_d^2/2\sigma^2 \ll r^2/2\sigma^2$), the direct path is eliminated and the envelope distribution becomes Rayleigh, with $K(dB) = -\infty$.

To simulate the presence of a direct component, the received signal was modeled by eqn. (9). This meant that a term without any random phase needs to be added to the signal generated in the case of Rayleigh fading. The rest of the simulation was carried out as in the case of Rayleigh fading.

The RF signal and the envelope corresponding to N = 10 are shown in Figure 2b and Figure 2d. It is seen that the fluctuation in the envelope for Rician is much smaller than for the Rayleigh case (Figure 2c). The horizontal line in Figures (2c) and (2d) correspond to the mean value of the Rayleigh envelope.

The RF signals and demodulated envelopes for both Rayleigh and Rician cases for a mobile velocity of 25 m/s are compared in Figure 3. It is seen that the

signal envelope goes below the threshold (indicated by the horizontal line) in Figures (3c) and (3d) more often than in Figures (2c) and (2d). This increases the chances of loss of signal determined by the appearance of the envelope below the threshold when the mobile unit is in motion.

The envelope histogram and the Rayleigh fit to the envelope are shown in Figure 4. The Rayleigh density function was created by calculating the Rayleigh parameter from the moments of the envelope data corresponding to eqn. (9). The fit of the histogram of the data to Rician can be undertaken similarly.

Fig. 2. RF signals and envelopes for stationary mobile
 (a) Rayleigh faded signal (b) Rician faded signal (c) Rayleigh envelope (d) Rician envelope

C. Nakagami M-Distribution

It is possible to describe both Rayleigh and Rician fading with the help of a single model using the Nakagami distribution [6]. The fading model for the received signal envelope, proposed by Nakagami, has the pdf given by

$$f(r) = \frac{2m^m r^{2m-1}}{\Gamma(m)\Omega^m} \exp\left\{-\frac{mr^2}{\Omega}\right\}, \quad r \geq 0 \quad (17)$$

Fig. 3. RF signals and envelopes for mobile moving at a velocity 25 m/s

(a) Rayleigh faded signal (b) Rician faded signal
 (c) Rayleigh envelope (d) Rician envelope

Where $\Gamma(m)$ is the Gamma function and m is the shape factor (with the constraint that $m \geq 1/2$) given by

$$m = \frac{E^2\{r^2\}}{E\{r^2 - E(r^2)\}^2} \quad (18)$$

The parameter Ω controls the spread of the distribution and is given by

$$\Omega = E\{r^2\} \quad (19)$$

The corresponding cumulative distribution function can be expressed as

$$F(r) = P\left(\frac{mr^2}{\Omega}, m\right) \quad (20)$$

Where $P(\cdot)$ is the incomplete Gamma function. In the special case $m = 1$, Nakagami reduces to Rayleigh distribution. For $m > 1$, the fluctuations of the signal strength reduce compared to Rayleigh fading, and Nakagami tends to Rician.

No special simulation was necessary to test for the validity of Nakagami fading. Since Nakagami distribution encompasses both Rayleigh and Rician, the signal envelopes were tested against the Nakagami distribution using the chi-square test.

The Nakagami distribution seems to be a good fit for Rayleigh fading with an average value of the parameter $m = 1$ [6]. It also seemed to fit the Rician distribution between $1 < m < 2$. Results for the Rayleigh and Nakagami fit are shown in Fig. 4.

3. OUTAGE PROBABILITY

In a fading radio channel, it is likely that a transmitted signal will suffer deep fades that can lead a complete loss of the signal or outage of the signal. The outage probability is a measure of the quality of the transmission in a mobile radio channel. Outage is said to occur when the received signal power goes below a certain threshold level [3, 4]. It

can be calculated as the integral of the received signal power $p(t)$ as

$$P_{out} = \int_0^{P_{th}} p(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Where P_{th} is the threshold power.

The procedure to find the outage probability is as follows:

1. Calculate the received signal power as given in equation
- 2.

$$f(r) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{r}{\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \frac{1}{\sigma\lambda\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(\ln\sigma - \mu)^2}{2\lambda^2}\right\} d\sigma \quad (22)$$

Where σ is the mode or the most probable value of the Rayleigh distribution, λ is the shape parameter of the lognormal distribution.

3. Set a threshold power level for the received signal relative to the average signal power.
4. Count the number of times in the sample interval that the received signal power goes below this threshold.
5. Using the basic concept of probability, the outage is then calculated by taking the ratio of the count in step 3 to the total number of samples.

For one received signal, we calculated the outage probabilities for various thresholds, and compared these values to those calculated analytically. The outage probabilities calculated analytically and through simulations were found to tally quite well. Fig.5 shows the curves for the outage probability, calculated analytically and through simulations, for the Rayleigh fading case. As observed from Table I, the outage probability (averaged over 50 simulations) in a Rician channel is lower than that in a Rayleigh channel, which can be attributed to the presence of a line-of-sight path. Moreover, the probability of outage increases as the mobile velocity, or resulting Doppler shift, increases.

Mobile velocity M/se	Outage Probability (Rayleigh)	Outage Probability (Rician)
0	0.19149	0.09331
2	0.19193	0.09312
4	0.19246	0.09314
6	0.19303	0.09346
8	0.19339	0.09350

Table I. Comparison of outage probability for Rayleigh and Rician fading for a number of values of mobile velocities

Fig.4: The histogram of the simulated data and the correspondingly matched density functions

Fig. 5: Outage probability for Rayleigh fading and stationary mobile. Simulated values are compared against theoretically computed outage values.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we shows the simple and straightforward concept of multipath fading channels and it easy to visualize the intricacies and understand the relationship between the different parameters involved in fading. Reducing outage probability (Pout) is to improve system performance. The outage performance method is based on channel capacity and mutual information.

REFERENCES

- [1] Erik Dahlman, Stefan Parkvall, Johan Sköld. 4G LTE/LTE-Advanced for Mobile Broadband. Academic Press. 2011. ISBN: 978-0-123-85489-6.
- [2] Stefania Sesia, Issam Toufik, Matthew Baker. LTE The UMTS Long Term Evolution: From Theory to Practice. John Wiley & Sons, 1st Edition, 2009. ISBN:978-0-470-69716-0.
- [3] Farooq Khan. LTE for 4G Mobile Broadband. Cambridge University Press.2009. ISBN: 978-0-511-51666-5.
- [4] H. Hashemi, "The Indoor Radio Propagation Channel," Proceedings of the IEEE, Vol. 81, No. 7, pp. 943-968, July 1993.
- [5] A. Papoulis, Probability, Random Variables, and Stochastic Processes, 3rd Edition, McGraw Hill, New York, 1991.
- [6] M. Nakagami, "The m-distribution. A General Formula of Intensity Distribution of Rapid Fading," in Hoffman, W. C., Statistical Methods in Radio Wave Propagation, Pergamon Press, 1960.
- [7] H. Suzuki, "A Statistical Model for Urban Radio Propagation," IEEE Tran. on Communications, Vol. COM-25, No. 7, pp. 673-680, July 1977.
- [8] W. C. Y. Lee, "Estimate of Local Average Power of a Mobile Radio," IEEE Trans. on Vehic. Tech., Vol. VT-34, No. 1, pp. 22-27, February 1985.
- [9] P. M. Shankar and B. A. Eisenstein, "Project based Instruction in Wireless Communications at the Junior Level," IEEE Trans. on Education, Vol. 43, No. 3, August 2000, pp. 245-249

BIOGRAPHIES

Patteti Krishna: Completed B.Tech degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering and M.Tech degree with specialization of Digital Systems & Computer Electronics from JNT University, Hyderabad in 2005 and 2008. He is having 9 years of teaching experience and published papers in various International & National journals. At present Krishna is pursuing PhD in wireless Communications under the faculty of Electronics & Communication Engineering. His research interests are Signal processing for wireless communications, MIMO Communications and Multiuser MIMO Communications. He is a Member of IEEE, ISTE and IETE.

Tipparti Anil Kumar is currently a Professor in Electronics and Communication Engineering Department, SR Engineering College, Warangal. He received his B.E. Degree from Osmania University in 1995 and M.Tech degree from National Institute of Technology; Kurukshetra in 2002. He obtained his PhD from Osmania University in 2009. He a senior member of IEEE and fellow of IETE, His research interests are Signal processing for Communications, Signal Processing Applications and Image Processing.

Kanithkar.Kishan Rao is currently a Director in Viswambhara Educational Society and Professor in Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering. He received his B.E. and M.E. degrees from Osmania University in 1965 and 1967. He obtained his PhD degree from Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur in 1973. He worked as Director and Principal for National Institute of Technology, Warangal and Kakatiya Institute of Technology and Science, Warangal. He a senior member of IEEE and fellow of IETE, He guided 03 PhD scholars and 62 Master Projects. His research interests are Wireless Communications, Signal Processing Applications and Cooperative Mobile Communications.

Image Acquisition, Noise removal, Edge Detection Methods in Image Processing Using Matlab for Prawn Species Identification

G Nagalakshmi¹ and S Jyothi²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Computers and Science Engineering,

²Professor, Department of Computer and Science Engineering

^{1,2} SPMVV, Thirupati, India.

¹ agnl.lakshmi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Image acquisition is a very essential and primary work for any image classification. A digital image is produced by several image sensors, which besides various types of light-sensitive cameras. Depending on the type of sensor, the resulting image (prawn) data is an ordinary 2D prawn image, or an image sequence. The prawn pixel values typically correspond to light intensity in one or several spectral bands (gray images or color images), but we can also be related to various physical measures of structure, such as depth, absorption or reflectance of sonic or electromagnetic waves, or nuclear magnetic resonance. It has been studied extensively in computer vision and photogrammetric camera lens which may be used to focus light so that objects may be viewed brighter. In this paper we review the techniques proposed in the literature include those using 3D apparatus, 2D objects and lens improvement to increase the size of the prawn so that prawns in the distance can appear larger and clear by presenting various types of cameras and their comparisons. In this paper we also presenting that the image processing techniques such as gray scale conversion, noise removal, sharpening, edge detecting, image segmentation, etc., that are applied for the captured prawn image by using Matlab source code and displaying the results.

Key Words - Digital image, light sensitive, spectral brands, photogrammetric cameras, image processing, gray scale, noise removal, sharpening, segmentation

1. INTRODUCTION

It is very essential need to reduce the time involvement in image processing for the initial work of capturing the images which are very much used to implement the image processing techniques. Now a day's photographic cameras can deliver photographs in various formats, these formats are delivered in a required format simply by applying pre-processing techniques. Photographic cameras are available that can deliver photos without pre-processing hence, without pre-processing techniques it's very difficult to find the actual structure of a prawn. The format of delivering the prawn images without any pre-processing techniques is the Bayer format [9]. In this process we analysis that our camera is connected to a Frame Grabber which retrieves the image, converts it to RGB, changing it

to a scale of grays and subsequently carries out the necessary processing by applying image processing techniques. The pre-processing techniques of an image start by image acquisition system.

In image processing image acquisition is defined as the action of retrieving an image from some source as prawns. In image processing image acquisition is the first step in the task implementation because, without an image, no processing is possible. In this paper we have taken the prawn as the source of input that operates within such controlled and measured structure and divisions of that same image [15].

Depending upon the different categories of prawns, a major factor involved in image acquisition of image processing. Sometimes image acquisition is the initial setup and long-term maintenance of the

hardware used to capture the prawns. If the hardware is not properly configured and aligned, then visual artifacts can be produced that can complicate the image processing. Improperly setup hardware also may provide prawn images that are of such low quality that they cannot be salvaged even with extensive processing. All of these elements are vital to certain areas, such as comparative image processing, which looks for specific differences between prawn images [4].

One of the forms of image acquisition in image processing is known as real-time image acquisition. This usually involves retrieving images from a source that is automatically capturing prawn images. One common technology that is used with real-time image processing is known as background image acquisition, which describes both software and hardware that can quickly preserve the images flooding into a system and it specifies the difference between the prawns and backgrounds. The basic two-dimensional image is a monochrome (grayscale) image which has been *digitized*. If we consider an image is a two-dimensional light intensity function $f(x, y)$ where x and y are spatial coordinates and the value of f at any point (x, y) is proportional to the brightness or gray value of the image at that point.

A digitized image is one where Spatial and grayscale values have been made discrete, Intensity measured across a regularly spaced grid in x and y directions, Intensities sampled to 8 bits (256 values). For prawn structure analysis purposes, we can consider a prawn image as a two-dimensional array where x and y index an image point. Each element in the array is called a *pixel* (picture element). *Image processing* is in many cases concerned with taking one array of pixels as input and producing another array of pixels as output which in some way represents an improvement to the original array [12].

As per the definition of we are taking prawn as input and producing same prawn as output simply by making some improvements in the prawn image by using Matlab image processing programs. For example, this processing may remove noise, improve the contrast of the image i.e., sharpening, remove blurring caused by movement of the camera during image acquisition, it may correct for geometrical distortions caused by the lens.

2. IMAGE ACQUISITION

Based on the need to reduce the time complexity in image processing, it is necessary to use advanced

camera's to capture the images for improving the time response. In our paper, we presenting real time tracking of capturing different species which are needed for the study of aqua-culture, Nowadays, photographic cameras can deliver photographs in various formats, with different camera calibrations and lens intensities [5]. The need to acquire number of prawn species for our application it is very essential intention to capture different lager number of prawn images at very high transfer rates. Hence in this paper, we also concentrate on different cameras with their intensities for our application approaches.

Figure1: The effect of illuminating a Prawn with different directions (Front, Top, Side)

To capture an image we need some kind of energy source to illuminate the scene. If a prawn image will captured than there is nothing to do about the illumination, hence it is very important to carefully think about how the scene should be lit. In fact, for the field of Machine Vision it is a rule-of-thumb that illumination is 2/3 of the entire system design and only 1/3. The above figure visualize that the same prawn image captured by the camera with different direction of the light source and care must be taken when pointing the illumination directly towards the camera.

Digital Image Acquisition

Traditional photographs, transparencies or negatives can be scanned and cameras can directly record digital images are the two methods for acquiring a digital image. Digital cameras, in their simplest form, use the principle of lens, shutter and film as found in traditional cameras. However instead of silver halide based film, refer to Chemical Image Processing a digital camera uses a CCD or CMOS sensor to record the image. Please refer to the Camera Basics section for more information. The image capture process of a digital camera is almost instantaneous as all the sensors are exposed at the same time also the number of pixels is fixed; therefore the image captured has a fixed resolution [11].

Unlike a digital camera a scanner's image resolution can be controlled by adjusting the movement of the sensor, the main disadvantage is the time taken to record an image, but this is not necessarily an important factor with scanners but would greatly reduce the potential subject matter of a camera. Real-time radiography is generally less sensitive than film radiography. A number of factors contribute to this difference. These factors include (1) the difference in size between the silver halide grains of film and the cesium iodide needles of the RTR scintillation screen, (2) the phosphor bloom of the fluorescent screen, (3) the random pixel noise inherent in image intensifiers, and (4) the pincushion image distortion also inherent in these systems. Real-time radiography systems using an image intensifier tube have poorer resolution (2-4 line pairs per millimeter) [LP/mm] than film (10-20 LP/mm) does. Phosphor bloom, especially in the output conversion phosphor, is the principle cause of diminished resolution and various direction of an images shown in figure (1).

3. CAMERA STANDARDS

Compact cameras, sometimes also called point-and-shoot probably were your first camera. They are very convenient: cheap, small, light and fool proof. As the name suggests, just point it in the general direction of the subject and press the button. The camera does the rest.

Figure 2: Backlighting. The light source is behind the object of interest, which makes the object stand out as a black shadow.

A camera calibration is the process of finding the internal quantities to the camera that affect the image process. This internal quantity of a camera includes position of image center in the image, focal length, different scaling factors for the rows and column pixels, skew factor, lens distortion. For accurate vision applications, the protocol camera link [1], is best for communication interface, which is the basic technology of the channel link to provide more useful specification for vision applications figure (2). The absolute necessity of a standard

camera link is to concentrate on advanced data transmission signals and to increase the camera dissimilarities. One of the major advantages of camera Link interface is reduces both the support time and budges cost.

One of the major important requirements of the camera in the optical system is the lens. Lens is a piece of glass which focuses the incoming light onto the sensor, and by using lens we can increase the size of the object in the image. This process of increasing the size of the object in the image is called optical zoom. All stages of traditional chemical based photography can now be performed by electronic digital processing. Digital imaging includes recording the image, storing the image, manipulating the image and outputting the image. Digital imaging processes and traditional chemical methods are not mutually exclusive, they can be used together in a wide variety of combinations; and the principles of forming the image by light and lens are the same for chemical and digital processes.

Electronic photography has been in existence since the 1930's, the first television transmission being made by the BBC on the 2nd November 1936 from Alexandra Palace. The cameras the BBC used were based on imaging tubes using thermal valve principles. Imaging tubes were the standard television capture device until the 1970's when Charged Coupled Devices (CCDs) were first introduced. Although the CCDs designed for television cameras produce excellent video pictures their use for still images were greatly limited by the small amount of image information they could record. During the 1980's higher definition CCDs were developed for use in digital cameras. By the late 1990's CMOS (Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor) technology was also being used to make image sensors for cameras. A digital image is made up from a great number of pixels, each pixel having a specific numeric tonal value. Image contrast is determined by the number of tonal values available and image resolution is determined by the number of pixels available.

Digital Single Lens Reflex cameras (DSLRs) are the "serious" camera of choice these days. Though this comes at the price of a serious increase in weight and bulk (and, well, price), they are also much more inflexible on everything that matters. In particular, they have interchangeable lenses which allow you to

always have the best lens for the occasion. Even APS-C (DX) cameras have big enough sensors to allow shallow depth of field and good low light/dynamic range quality. The diagrammatic view of Digital Single Lens Reflex camera is shown in the below figure (3). There is an optical viewfinder, which allows framing in the worst light conditions and is generally more responsive than any electronic screen.

Figure 3: A DSLR camera sample view

The annoyances of compact cameras are also gone: shutter lag is virtually unknown, autofocus generally very fast (though this depends on the lens) and even entry-level cameras provide full manual control along with their scene modes. There are several different sensor sizes, commonly called “cropped sensor”, “APS-C” or “DX” for the smaller versions, and “full frame” or “FX” for the bigger ones, which correspond exactly to the size of 35mm film. High end cameras tend to use FX for a variety of reasons, mostly having to do with image quality in difficult light conditions. Concretely, the main difference has to do with the crop factor, which we will cover in tomorrow’s lesson.

In short, a DSLR will be better than a compact in every respect. There are DSLRs at all price points, from the entry level to full featured pro beasts. In 2014, entry level models would be the Canon T5i and Nikon D3200, while more advanced models are the Canon 7D and the Nikon D7100. Hence in our application we selected DSLR camera for capturing Prawn images to display accurate and noise less images.

4. IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES:

Image processing is a physical process used to convert an image signal into a physical image. The image signal can be either digital or analog. The actual output itself can be an actual physical image or the characteristics of an image. The most common type of image processing is photography. In this

process, an image is captured using a camera to create a digital or analog image. In order to produce a physical picture, the image is processed using the appropriate technology based on the input source type. In digital photography, the image is stored as a computer file. This file is translated using photographic software to generate an actual image. The colors, shading, and nuances are all captured at the time the photograph is taken the software translates this information into an image shown in the below figure(4).

Figure 4: Basic image processing techniques

4.1 Gray scale image:

In this we concentrate more on gray scale because it is usually the preferred format for image processing results also shown in below figure. Even in cases requiring color, an RGB color image can be decomposed and handled as three separate grayscale images. Indexed images must be converted to grayscale or RGB for most operations. To understand grayscale better, here we are using image representations in Matlab: A grayscale image m pixels tall and n pixels wide is represented as a matrix of double datatype of size $m \times n$. Element values (such as $img(m,n)$) denote the pixel grayscale intensities in $[0,1]$ with 0=black and 1=white. A first-order global characteristic of an image is its gray level histogram. The gray level histogram of an image is a chart, listing all of the gray levels (Shown in figure 5.1) that are used in the image on the horizontal axis and indicating the number of pixels having each level on the vertical axis. The gray level histogram of the image is shown as right inset. Gray level images usually consist of 256 levels of gray, so, the horizontal axis of the histogram runs from 0 to 255. The vertical axis varies in scale depending on the number of pixels in the image and the distribution of the gray level values. A set of techniques, called gray level histogram modifications, is used to improve the visual appearance of an image

4.2 Smoothing of noisy images:

Noise is the random variation in the pixel content caused by the acquisition, digitization and transmission process. An example of a original image is shown in Figure 7. As seen from the image, pixels which are affected by noise often appear markedly different from their neighbor pixels in Figure 7b. Noise cannot be eliminated altogether; it can be reduced by a process called smoothing. The simplest way of noise reduction is to analyze a few nearest neighbor pixels of each pixel in the image and to see if the difference between the gray value of the pixel and the gray values of its nearest neighbors is essential [3]. Often smoothing by averaging is applied. Here each pixel is replaced by the average of its neighbor pixels. Another effective way of noise reduction is median filtering when each pixel is replaced by the median of its neighbor pixels. The image, shown in Figure 7c is obtained by the median filtering of the image.

Digital images are prone to a variety of types of noise. Noise is the result of errors in the image acquisition process that result in pixel values that do not reflect the true intensities of the real scene. There are several ways that noise can be introduced into an image, depending on how the image is created. If the Prawn image is scanned from a photograph made on film, the film grain is a source of noise [14]. Noise can also be the result of damage to the film, or be introduced by the scanner itself. If the Prawn image is acquired directly in a digital format, the mechanism for gathering the data (such as a CCD detector) can introduce noise. Electronic transmission of image data can introduce noise.

Median filtering is similar to using an averaging filter, in that each output pixel is set to an average of the pixel values in the neighborhood of the corresponding input pixel. However, with median filtering, the value of an output pixel is determined by the median of the neighborhood pixels, rather than the mean. The median is much less sensitive than the mean to extreme values (called outliers). Median filtering is therefore better able to remove these outliers without reducing the sharpness of the image. The `medfilt2` function implements median filtering.

4.3 Sharpening

Similarly to smoothing there is a class of spatial filters called high-pass filters, which are often applied for image sharpening. Their application is also based on the discrete convolution of the original

image with a special mask [2]. To produce a sharpening effect the following filters can be used:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 5 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 9 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 & 1 \\ -2 & 5 & -2 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

An example of an image where a sharpening may be necessary is shown in Figure 6 The resulted image with enhanced edges. Another way of making an image sharper is to apply edge detection filters such as the Laplace, Roberts, Sobel filters, and to add the found edges to the original image.

4.4 Edge detection

Edge detection is one of the important pre-processing steps in image analysis. Edges characterize boundaries and edge detection is one of the most difficult tasks in image processing hence it is a problem of fundamental importance in image processing. Edges in images are areas with strong intensity contrasts and a jump in intensity from one pixel to the next can create major variation in the picture quality [6]. Edge detection of an image significantly reduces the amount of data and filters out useless information, while preserving the important structural properties in an image. Conventionally, mathematical morphology edge detection methods use single and symmetrical structure elements. But they are difficult to detect complex edge feature, because they are only sensitive to image edge which has the same direction of structure elements. Edge detection techniques transform images to edge images benefiting from the changes of gray tones in the image.

The most frequently used edge detection is Roberts edge detection, Prewit edge detection, Sobel edge detection and Canny edge detection methods [10]. In this paper, we are concentrating on sobel and canny edge detection methods which are suitable for our application because this edge method are give clear and perfect edges of the Prawn which are shown in the results part.

In an image, an edge is a curve that follows a path of rapid change in image intensity. Edges are often associated with the boundaries of objects in a scene. Edge detection is used to identify the edges in an image. The most powerful edge-detection method that edge provides is the Canny method Shown in figure 8. The Canny method differs from the other edge-detection methods in that it uses two different thresholds (to detect strong and weak edges), and

includes the weak edges in the output only if they are connected to strong edges [7]. This method is therefore less likely than the others to be fooled by noise, and more likely to detect true weak edges.

4.5 Image segmentation

Segmentation is one of the key problems in image processing. A popular method used for image segmentation is thresholding. After thresholding a binary image is formed where all object pixels have one gray level and all background pixels have another - generally the object pixels are 'black' and the background is 'white' [13]. Thresholding can be defined as mapping of the gray scale into the binary set {0,1}:

$$S(x,y)=\begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } g(x,y) < T(x,y) \\ 1, & \text{if } g(x,y) \geq T(x,y) \end{cases}$$

Where $S(x, y)$ is the value of the segmented image, $g(x, y)$ is the gray level of the pixel (x, y) and $T(x, y)$ is the threshold value at the coordinates (x, y) . It can be selected, for instance, on the basis of the gray level histogram. When the histogram has two pronounced maxima, which reflect gray levels of object(s) and background, it is possible to select a single threshold for the entire image. A method which is based on this idea and uses a correlation criterion to select the best threshold is described below. Sometimes gray level histograms have only one maximum. This can be caused, e.g., by inhomogeneous illumination of various regions of the image [8]. In such case it is impossible to select a single thresholding value for the entire image and a local binarization technique (described below) must be applied. General methods to solve the problem of binarization of in homogeneously illuminated images, however, are not available. Segmentation of images involves sometimes not only the discrimination between objects and the background, but also separation between different regions. One method for such separation is known as watershed segmentation the basic principles of which are Global thresholding using a correlation criterion, Local binarization using discrete convolution, and Segmentation based on watershed transform these segmentations are used in our future work.

5. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

This section presents the relative performance of various image processing techniques such as gray scale conversion, smoothing of noise images, sharpening, edge detection using sobel and canny methods by using Matlab source codes. We are

performing these techniques for the captured Prawn image. By using the resultant Prawn image of various images processing technique we are trying to find the difference between the prawn each other and specifying the category of Prawn. Hence the resultant prawn images of gray scale, sharpening, edge detection of sobel and canny methods are shown in the below figures.

5.1 Gray scale image: A grayscale image is also called gray-scale or gray-level) is a data matrix whose values represent intensities within some range. MATLAB supplies a grayscale Prawn image as a individual matrix, with each element of the matrix corresponding to one Prawn image pixel. By convention, this documentation uses the variable name I to refer to grayscale Prawn images. The result of converting the original image to gray scale Prawn image is shown in below figure

Figure 5: Gray scale image

5.2 Image Sharpening: To sharpen a Prawn color image, you need to make the luma intensity transitions are more accurate for sharpen the given Prawn color image. For this analysis we are converting an R'G'B' image into the Y'CbCr color space and apply a highpass filter to the luma portion of the Prawn image only. Then, you transform the image back to the R'G'B' color space to view the results. To blur an image, you apply a lowpass filter to the luma portion of the image which is shown in the below figure.

Figure 6: Image Sharpening

5.3 Noise Removal: Removing of noise in the captured Prawn image is the essential and primary work of our application. It can be done by implementing Median filtering by using Mat lab shown in the below figure (7). Wiener2 works best when the noise is constant-power ("white") additive noise, such as Gaussian noise. The example below

applies wiener2 to an image of Saturn that has had Gaussian noise added

Figure 7: Noise Removal

5.4 Edge Detection: The most powerful edge-detection method that edge provides is the Canny method. The Canny method differs from the other edge-detection methods in that it uses two different thresholds (to detect strong and weak edges), and includes the weak edges in the output only if they are connected to strong edges. This method is therefore less likely than the others to be fooled by noise, and more likely to detect true weak edges. We also show the output of Sobel edge detection method in the below figure and its comparisons for the same image.

Figure 8: Sobel and Canny Edge Detection

6. Conclusion

The image acquisition is a fundamental part of the image processing research because of its subsequent processes depends on it. To achieve this, departing from signals of camera link protocol, is very much important care on capturing of Prawn images. In analysis for this purpose of capturing different Prawns with clear and accurate Prawn structure we suggesting DSLR Cameras for our applications. This captured prawns are than used for implementing various image processing techniques like converting original image into gray scale converting, image sharpening , image noise removal, and identifying the Prawn image edges by applying canny and sobel edge detection their result in Matlab are also shown. In our future work, we are extending the same process of image processing techniques by applying image segmentation in which the given Prawn image is dividing into different division or blocks or

segments for identifying the difference of one Prawn with other Prawns.

REFERENCES

1. Specifications of camera link, interface standard for digital camera and frame grabbers, Camera Link, October 2000.
2. N. S. Jayant, "Average and median-based smoothing techniques for improving digital speech processing", ZEEE Trans. Acoust., Speech Signal Processing, vol. ASSP-23, pp.552-557, Dec .1975.
3. F. Luisier, T. Blu and M. Unser, "Image Denoising in Mixed Poission-gaussian Noise", IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, vol. 4, (1999) July.33.
4. Ajay Kumar Nain, Surbhi Singhania, Shailender Gupta and Bharat Bhushan , "A . Comparative Study of Mixed Noise Removal Techniques" International Journal of Signal Processing, Image Processing and Pattern Recognition Vol.7 -2014
5. SukHwan Lim and Abbas EI Gamal, "Integration of Image Capture and Processing – Beyond Single Chip Digital Camera", Proceedings of SPIVE , 2001
6. Rohan Kandwal, Ashok Kumar, Sajay Bhargava, "Review: Existing Image Segmentation Techniques", IJARCSSE, April – 2014, pp. 153-156
7. Ahmed R. Khalifa, "Evaluating the Effectiveness Of Region Growing And Edge Detection Segmentation Algorithms. -2010
8. A. M. Khan, Ravi. S, "Image Segmentation Methods: A Comparative Study", International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering ISSN: 2231-2307, Volume-3, Issue-4, September 2013.
9. N, Senrhilakumaran and R. Rajesh, "Edge Detection Techniques for Image Segmentation – A Survey of soft Computing Approaches", International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering, Vol.1, No.2, May 2009.
10. Ravi S and A M Khan, "Operators Used in Edge Detection: A Case Study", International Journal of Applied Engineering, ISSN 0973-4562 vol. 7 No 11, 2012.
11. S. Nagabhushana, "Computer Vision and Image Processing", New Age International Publishers, 2005.
12. R.C. Gonzalez and R.E. Woods, "Digital Image Processing", third edition, PHI publication, 2008.
13. Yong Yang, "Image Segmentation By Fuzzy C-Means Clustering Algorithm with A Novel Penalty Term", Computing And Informatics, Vol. 26, 17-31, 2007.
14. Yu-Hsiang Wang, "Tutorial: Image Segmentation", Natioanl Taiwan University, Taipei, ROC,
15. Fu., K.S., Mui, J.K., 1981. A Survey on image segmentation. Pattern Recognition13 (1), 3-16.

Resolution Enhancement and Denoising of Magnetic Resonance Images Using SWT

B Sridevi¹, Dr. T Anil Kumar² and Prof.K.Kishan Rao³

¹Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
¹²JNT University, Hyderabad, Telangana.

² Professor , Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

³ Director, Vaagdevi College of Engineering, Warangal, Telengana

¹ vaagvijj_1511@yahoo.co.in, ² tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in ³ prof_kkr@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

To analyze the human body, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has been playing an vital role since many years. MR images were used to find out the diseases in brain, lungs, liver, breast and etc., In order to detect the disease, the primary thing is that the image which is going to be diagnosis by the medical experts should be clean i.e., with out of any noise and the visual quality of image should be higher or enhanced quality from the original scanned images. For better diagnosis, we should improve the visual quality of the MR images, this process named as pre-processing techniques for MR images. Here in this thesis, we had introduced a denoising mechanism using various spatial filters to denoise the input MR images and improved the visual quality of image by enhancement using discrete wavelet transform (DWT). In this, the intensification is achieved by using a combination of discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and stationary wavelet transform augmented with Bicubic interpolation algorithm. The resultant sharpened high resolution images are used for better diagnosis.

Keywords: Denoising, DWT, SWT, MRI mage, SUSAN Filter.

Scaling Based Power Saving for Maximum Communication Path Lifetime in Wireless Sensor Networks

Kande. Srinivas ¹ and Dr. M. B. Raju ²

¹ Associate Professor, ² Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Computer Science & Engineering,

¹ SVS Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana.

² JNTUH College of Engineering, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

¹ sri.kande3697@gmail.com, ² drraju.jb@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The interest in Wireless Sensor Networks is rapidly increasing due to their interesting advantages related to cost coverage and network deployment. They are present in civil applications and in most Scenarios depend upon the batteries which are the exclusive power source for the tiny sensor nodes. The energy consumption is an important issue for research, and many interesting projects have been developed in several areas. They focus on topology topics, Medium Access Control or physical issues. In this paper, aim at the physical layer where the node's power consumption is optimized through scaling the modulation scheme used in node communications. Results show that an optimal modulation scheme can lead to the minimum power consumption over the whole wireless sensor network. A usual simplification in research is to target individual paths and not take into account the whole network.

Keywords: MAC, Power Consumption, WSN.

NETWORK CENTRIC COLLABORATIVE NAVIGATION FOR TARGET LOCALIZATION USING PSO TUNED UKF

J Ravichander¹, **Ch Balaswamy**² and **K Soundarajan**³

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
¹ SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India.

² Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
² QIS Engineering College, JNTUK, India

² Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
² KPES, JNTUH, India

¹ ravi_chander_j@srecewarangalac.in, ² ch.balaswamy7@gmail.com and
soudarajan_jntuecea@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Mobile Adhoc networks (MANET) are used in critical applications such as coordinated target localization. Centralized control of MANET nodes is not an attractive solution due to its high network utilization that can result in congestions and delays. In this paper, we consider the task of target localization using network-centric collaborative navigation. Kalman filter tracks the target by assuming the initial state and noise covariance. For efficient tracking by any filter like Kalman filter noise covariances must be optimized. We propose a computationally efficient localization algorithm by tuning of noise covariance of Unscented Kalman filter for localization of target using particle swarm optimization (PSO). The proposed algorithm computationally much more efficient and are resistant to errors in network-centric collaborative navigation for quick target localization.

Keywords: MANET, target localization, Unscented Kalmanfilter (UKF), network-centric collaborative localization, particle swarm optimization (PSO).

High Performance Implementation of FIR Filter for DSP Applications based on FPGA

Chetti Venkateswarlu¹ and Dr Tipparti Anil Kumar²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹Vaageswari Engineering College, Karimnagar, Telangana.

²Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

²SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana

¹venkatchece@gmail.com, ²tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

Signal processing ranks among the most demanding applications of digital design concepts. It is a mature technology domain wherein the demands for enhanced performance and reduced resource utilization have risen exponentially over the years. Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) design technology has becoming the preferred platform for evaluating and implementing signal processing algorithms. The advantages of the FPGA approach to digital filter implementation include higher sampling rates than are available from traditional DSP chips, lower costs than an application specific integrated circuit (ASIC) for moderate volume applications, and more flexibility than the alternate approaches. Since many current FPGA architectures are in-system programmable, the configuration of the device may be changed to implement different functionality if required. This paper describes an approach to the implementation of digital filter based on field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) which is flexible and provides performance comparable or superior to traditional approaches, low-power, area-efficient re-configurable digital signal processing architecture that is tailored for the realization of arbitrary response Finite impulse response (FIR) filters.

Keywords: FIR Filter, FPGA, DSP chips.

Capacity Limits and Estimation of Massive MIMO Systems

Gujjula Ramya¹, Satyavathi², Dr. Narasigh Yadav³ and Samineni Pedda Krishna⁴

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹²³Malla Reddy Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana.

² Assistant Professor , Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

¹ramyagujjula275@gmail.com, ²Krishna.saminen@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The use of large-scale antenna arrays can bring substantial improvements in energy and/or spectral efficiency to wireless systems due to the greatly improved spatial resolution and array gain. Recent works in the field of massive multiple input multiple-output (MIMO) show that the user channels decorrelate when the number of antennas at the base stations (BSs) increases, thus strong signal gains are achievable with little inter-user interference. Since these results rely on asymptotic, it is important to investigate whether the conventional system models are reasonable in this asymptotic regime. This paper considers a new system model that incorporates general transceiver hardware impairments at both the BSs (equipped with large antenna arrays) and the single-antenna user equipments (UEs). As opposed to the conventional case of ideal hardware, we show that hardware impairments create finite ceilings on the channel estimation accuracy and on the downlink/uplink capacity of each UE.

Keywords: Capacity bounds, channel estimation, energy efficiency, massive MIMO, pilot contamination

Performance of LTE Channel Estimation Algorithms for Different Interpolation Methods and Modulation Schemes

Patteti Krishna ¹, Indarjeeth Singh ² and Gabbeta Ramesh ³

^{1,3} Assoc. Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
^{1,3}SVS Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana.

² Assoc. Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
²Vivekananda Institute of Technology and Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana-INDIA

¹ kpatteti@gmail.com, ² indar_2020@yahoo.com, ³ ramesh.gabbeta@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present performance of pilot based channel estimation techniques such as Least Squares (LS) and Linear Minimum Mean Square Error (LMMSE) for different interpolation methods and modulation schemes. The performance is evaluated using the mean squared error (MSE) as the performance metric of interest for downlink Long Term Evolution (LTE) system. Simulation results show that for low SNR environment, applying QPSK modulation for any interpolation method produces the best MSE performance, but for high SNR environment, linear interpolation produces the worst MSE performance for QPSK and 16-QAM modulation schemes.

Keywords: Channel Estimation, LS, LMMSE, Interpolation, LTE.

Image Compression Algorithms using DCT Based Motion Recovery using 14-Bit Addition Techniques

Adicherla Prinyanka ¹, and G Surender²

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹² Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Image compression is the application of Data compression on digital images. The discrete cosine transform (DCT) is a technique for converting a signal into elementary frequency components. It is widely used in image compression. Here we develop some simple functions to compute the DCT and to compress images. An image compression algorithm was comprehended using Matlab code, and modified to perform better when implemented in hardware description language. The IMAP block and IMAQ block of MATLAB was used to analyze and study the results of Image Compression using DCT and varying co-efficient for compression were developed to show the resulting image and error image from the original images. Image Compression is studied using 2-D discrete Cosine Transform. The original image is transformed in 8-by-8 blocks and then inverse transformed in 8-by-8 blocks to create the reconstructed image. The inverse DCT would be performed using the subset of DCT coefficients. The error image (the difference between the original and reconstructed image) would be displayed. Video processing systems such as HEVC requiring low energy consumption needed for the multimedia market has lead to extensive development in fast algorithms for the efficient approximation of 2-D DCT transforms. In this paper, we introduce a novel 8-point DCT approximation that requires only 14 addition operations and no multiplications. The proposed DCT approximation is a candidate for reconfigurable video standards such as HEVC. The proposed transform and several other DCT approximations are mapped to systole carry digital architectures and physically realized as digital prototype circuits using FPGA Spartan 3 and it are implemented by verilog language.

Keywords: Approximate DCT, low-complexity algorithms, image compression, HEVC, low power consumption.

ENERGY EFFICIENT RESOURCE ALLOCATION IN OFDM SYSTEMS SIGNALS WITH SIGN ADJUSTMENT

Bommidi Venkata Ramana¹, and G Surender²

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹² Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we develop an energy efficient subcarrier assignment and power allocation in OFDM system. Our aim is to maximize energy efficiency (EE) under the constraints of the overall transmit power of each remote access unit (RAU), proportional fairness data rates, and bit error rates (BERs). Because of the non convex nature of the optimization problem, obtaining the optimal solution is extremely computationally complex. Low complexity algorithm is developed to convert the non convex optimization problem into convex optimization problem. So only we can get the tractable solution. Some of the barrier problem such as obstacles also affects the signal strength. So we can implement the fast barrier method. The fast barrier method converges very fast and can always work out the optimal solution. Some of the comparisons are given here to improve energy efficiency and avoid PAPR problems.

Keywords: OFDM-orthogonal frequency multiplexing, subcarrier assignment, power allocation, Energy efficiency, PAPR.

SURVEY ON ENERGY EFFICIENCY PROTOCOLS IN WIRELESS NETWORK

Bommati Mahesh ¹, and G Surender²

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹² Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The demand for high data-rate multimedia wireless communications has been growing rapidly. As standards are addressing higher capacity wireless links to meet increasing demands, device power consumption is also increasing. Although silicon technology is progressing exponentially, doubling about every two years, processor power consumption is also increasing by 150% every two years. In contrast, the improvement in battery technology is much slower, increasing a modest 10% every two years, leading to an exponentially increasing gap between the demand for energy and the battery capacity offered. Furthermore, the shrinking device sizes are also imposing an ergonomic limit on the battery capacity available. A wireless network consists of a large number of small sensor nodes with sensing, data processing, and communication capabilities, which are deployed in a region of interest and collaborate to accomplish a common task, a sensor network has many unique characteristics, such as denser node deployment, higher unreliability of sensor nodes, asymmetric data transmission, and severe power, computation, and memory constraints, which present many new challenges for the development and eventual application of wireless sensor networks. In particular, sensor nodes are usually battery-powered and should operate without attendance for a relatively long period of time. In most cases, it is very difficult and even impossible to change or recharge batteries for these sensor nodes. Thus, energy-saving routing protocol in wireless networks is necessary for increasing the network lifetime. In this paper we present a comparative study of different routing algorithms and analysis of same is presented in the paper. Different routing protocols have been proposed to improve the performance. All routing protocols have different behavior than others for improving and maintaining the routing performance. Routing protocols determines the route, which is required. The determination of route is done by the routing algorithm. The routing protocol first sends the packet to the nearest node and then that node sends the packet to next node. In this paper survey we find that what effects are given by different routing protocols (AODV, BATMAN, DSR, Proactive, Reactive and OLSR) in MANET for number of nodes, packet length and mobility. To give the answer of above question we check out the performance of these routing protocols. This electronic document is a "live" template. The various components of your paper [title, text, heads, etc.] are already defined on the style sheet, as illustrated by the portions given in this document

Keywords: MANET, Routing protocols, AODV, DSR, OLSR, Proactive, Reactive.

DESIGN AND MODELING OF INTELLIGENT TRAFFIC LIGHT CONTROLLER ON FPGA

Ch Abilash¹, and G Surender²

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹² Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The paper presents an adaptive traffic light controller customized to have user defined number of intersection lanes and counts of signals for various intersections. Conventional traffic systems can be installed for a non-dynamic number of intersections with fixed counts of signal durations and are typically microcontroller based. The proposed system prototype is implemented on FPGA which offers many advantages over microcontrollers such as fast speed, number of input/output ports and enhanced performance coupled with low cost than ASIC design. Typical TLCs are modeled using the finite state paradigm and rely heavily on software design flow. In this paper, the hardware design has been deployed using the structural style of VHDL programming and thus offers more robustness. The system has been successfully tested and implemented in hardware using Xilinx Cyclone III: EP3C10F256C6. The efficient design thus offers a dynamic way that allows the user to design a robust TLC and thus it breaks through the bottleneck of traditional traffic signal controller, and can accomplish the control in complicated and diversified traffic.

Keywords: TLC, FSM, Structural VHDL, Xilinx, FPGA

Cooperative Spectrum Sensing Technique using Multiple Energy Detectors for Cognitive Radio Networks

M Shyam Sunder¹ and Prof.E Venkat Reddy²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹²OPJ University, Rajasthan, India.

² Professor , Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

ABSTRACT

Cognitive Radio offers a solution by utilizing the spectrum holes that represent the potential opportunities for non-interfering use of spectrum. The electromagnetic spectrum is a natural scarce resource. Radio transmission involves the use of part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Cognitive radio is an evolving technology to solve the spectrum scarcity problem in wireless communication. This is based on the concept of opportunistic spectrum access. Spectrum sensing is one of the most important functions in cognitive radio (CR) implementation. An uncertain knowledge of the noise power level can severely limit the energy detector (ED) spectrum sensing capability. In some situations this uncertainty can cause signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) penalties. In this paper, we propose a multiple energy detectors (MEDs) based scheme with improved detection performance at low signal to noise ratio (SNR). We consider a framework of CR networks in which each CR node is equipped with MEDs and each energy detector with single antenna. An analytical model is developed for performance evaluation in terms of probability of false alarm P_f , and probability of detection P_d . Numerical results obtained in Rayleigh fading channel show that the proposed scheme performs better as compared to conventional energy detector (ED).

Keywords: CR ,ED, SNR, MED.

ENHANCEMENT THE SECURITY OF AES ALGORITHM FOR HIGH SPEED FAULT DETECTION

Adi Anusha¹, and G Surender²

¹PG Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹² Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cryptography is a method that has been developed to ensure the secrecy of messages and transfer data securely. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) has been made as the first choice for many critical applications because of the high level of security and the fast hardware and software implementations, many of which are power and resource constrained and requires reliable and efficient hardware implementations. Naturally occurring and maliciously injected faults reduce the reliability of Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and may leak confidential information. In this paper, a lightweight concurrent fault detection scheme for the AES is presented. In the proposed approach, the composite field S-box and inverse S-box are divided into blocks and the predicted parities of these blocks are obtained. For high speed applications, S-box implementation based on lookup tables is avoided. Instead, logic gate implementations based on composite fields are utilized. A compact architecture for the AES Mix-columns operation and its inverse is also presented. This parity-based fault detection scheme reaches the maximum fault coverage when compared to other methods of fault detection. The proposed fault detection technique for AES encryption and decryption has the least area and power consumption compared to their counterparts with similar fault detection capabilities. In the proposed approach, the composite field S-box and inverse S-box are divided into blocks and the predicted parities of these blocks are obtained. By using exhaustive searches We obtained the optimum solutions for the least overhead parity-based fault detection structures. It suggests both the ASIC and FPGA implementations of the fault detection structures using the obtained optimum composite fields, have better hardware and time complexities compared to their counterparts.

Keywords: AES, composite fields, parity prediction, fault detection, S-box.

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CHANNEL ESTIMATION FOR MULTICARRIER SYSTEM FOR QAM/QPSK MODULATION TECHNIQUES

G Surender¹

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,

¹ Sri Chaitanya Institutes of Technological Science, Karimnagar, Telangana.

¹ surender.g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Rapid changes and growth in mobile communication have inspired the researcher for the better performance of the high speed wireless communication systems. This paper proposes the comparative study of Channel Estimation for the Multicarrier system using various estimation techniques mainly for skirmishing fading effect; it improves the performance of the system. The problem such as Inter-Carrier Interference which is mainly due to the carrier offset effect is reduced to a considerable extent by applying different estimation algorithm. A new approach based on TDI has been presented. TDI is obtained by passing estimated channel to time domain through Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform and zero padding. The comparison between the LS, LS-Spine and MMSE for QPSK and QAM modulation techniques for different SNR and FFT vales has been carried out. It is investigated that by applying the DFT over estimated power of the channel for 16-QPSK modulation technique, the performance of the channel estimators becomes better.

Keywords: Multi Input Multi Output (MIMO), Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM), Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), Least Square Error (LSE), Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE)

A DC/DC Converter with Voltage Boost-Up Using Zero Voltage Switching Technique

D Kumaraswamy ¹ and Dr. B.V. Shanker Ram ²

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
¹SVS Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana.

² Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
²JNTUH college of Engineering, Hyderabad, Telangana

¹ dkswamy1213@gmail.com, ² bvsram@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

A ZVS dc/dc converter with voltage boost-Up is proposed in this paper. It provides a continuous inp current and high voltage gain. Moreover, soft-switching characteristic of the proposed converteruces switching loss of active power switches and raises the conversion efficiency. The reverse-recovery blem of output rectifiers is also alleviated by controlling the current changing rates of diodes with the of the leakage inductance of a coupled inductor.

Keywords: Boost converter, high voltage gain, soft switching..

Performance Study of PAPR Reduction Techniques in OFDM

Praveen¹,²Satyavathi and Dr. Narasigh Yadav²

¹PG Student, ²Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2} Malla Reddy Institute Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

¹praveen43ece@gmail.com, ²satyanarayana.ah@gmail.com, ³narasigh.mriet@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is considered to be a promising technique against the multipath fading channel for wireless communications. However, OFDM faces the Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) problem that is a major drawback of multicarrier transmission system which leads to power inefficiency in RF section of the transmitter. This paper present different PAPR reduction techniques and conclude an overall comparison of these techniques. We also simulate the selected mapping technique (SLM) for different route number which is most efficient technique for PAPR reduction when the number of subcarrier is large. Simulation shows that the PAPR problem reduced as the route number increases.

Keywords: Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM), Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR), Power Amplifiers (PAs), Selected Mapping (SLM), Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF).

Analytical Performance of Peak Spectral Efficiency in LTE systems

Patteti Krishna ¹ and Dr. N Satish Kumar ² and S. Subramanyam

¹ Associate Professor, ² Assocuat. Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

² Department of Computer Science & Engineering,

^{1,2} SVS Group of Institutions, Warangal, Telangana, India.

³ Jyothismathi Institute of Technological Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana, India

¹kpatteti@gmail.com, ²satish4info@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The spectral efficiency is a key performance indicator of wireless cellular networks. Maximizing the data rate and spectral efficiency are the main targets in Long Term Evaluation (LTE) cellular systems. However, any increase in data rate or spectral efficiency will result in an undesirable increase in energy consumption. The Peak Spectral Efficiency (PSE) is basically the highest theoretical data rate normalized by bandwidth assignable to a single mobile station assuming error-free conditions. In this paper evaluate the PSE for Long Term Evaluation Frequency Division Duplex (LTE-FDD) mode and Time Division Duplex (LTE-TDD) mode in Uplink (UL) and Downlink (DL).

Keywords: Peak Spectral efficiency, FDD, TDD and LTE.

Relay Selection for Coded Cooperative Networks over Nakagami- m Fading Channels

Rajanna¹

ABSTRACT

A relay selection for turbo coded cooperative networks subject to Nakagami- m fading is considered in this paper. It is assumed that the channel state information (may not be ideal) is known at the receiver. Further, feedback delay caused by the difference between the instantaneous channel state information during the transmission and the channel state information at the time of relay selection, resulting in outdated channel state information phenomena. The impact of the outdated channel state information on the proposed scheme is investigated in this paper. A closed-form expression for the outage probability is derived and its asymptotic expression in the high signal-to-noise (SNR) regime is studied. Further, upper bounds on the bit-error rate (BER) are presented. Study of the diversity order reveals that for ideal channel state information, full diversity in the number of relays and fading parameters m is achieved as opposed to outdated channel state information where the achievable diversity is equivalent to the diversity of a coded cooperative network with a single relay.

Keywords: Coded cooperation, diversity order, error rate, relay selection, turbo codes.

OFDM Channel Estimation using Wiener Filtering and its Implementation

Nalla Swetha¹ and Tipparti Anil Kumar²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

¹SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

²SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India

¹swathareddy47@gmail.com, ²tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

Today's wireless communication system Channel estimation and equalization is an essential part. Two main challenges exist in wireless channels which are multipath fading and doppler spread. Multipath fading represents the selectivity of the channel and as the delay spread of the channel increases, the frequency selectivity increases, and the channel changes rapidly between adjacent subcarriers. As the mobility of the user increases, the doppler shift increases, and the channel is less correlated in time. These effects are usually limiting the wireless systems and cause very high bit error rates if not estimated and equalized correctly. In this thesis, different channel estimation techniques for OFDM systems are examined. OFDM systems are dominating in wireless transmission. Simulations are made for many widely used channel estimation techniques and they are all compared with respect to their bit error rates and mean square errors. These methods are tested in different channel conditions to cover most of the states for wireless systems. From all of the compared techniques, the best algorithms are tested in WiMAX 802.16e as a real wireless system. A novel estimation technique is proposed for the WiMAX case. This technique is simple, and gives good performance compared to other techniques. This technique is based on Wiener Filtering and simple linear interpolations.

Study and Implementation of Energy Detection Algorithm for WLAN and WiMAX

Nuka Abhisek¹ and B Ujwala²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

¹abhiseknuka02@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The electromagnetic spectrum is a natural resource. The current spectrum licensing scheme is unable to accommodate rapidly growing demand in wireless communication due the static spectrum allocation policies. This allocation leads to increase in spectrum scarcity problem. Cognitive radio (CR) technology is an advanced wireless radio design which aims to increase spectrum utilization by identifying unused and under-utilized spectrum in dynamically changing environments. But in low signal to noise ratio (SNR) conditions, its performance is weak, which can be improved by signal processing algorithm. As energy detection is simple and easily implemented in hardware, so it is preferred in emerging standard like IEEE 802.22, In this paper energy detection technique is applied for WLAN and WiMAX under BPSK modulation method and Monte-Carlo simulations are performed to test the performance of received signals in WLAN and WiMAX. Following to this work VLSI implementation of spectrum sensing using energy detection have been implemented for pseudo random sequence generated signal and BPSK modulates signal. OFDM is used as modulation standard and it is implemented in VLSI for WLAN and WiMAX.

VLSI Implementation of real time Image Processing System Designs

Jawaji Abhilash¹ and Sandeep²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
¹SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.
¹jawajiabhis@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The electromagnetic spectrum is a natural resource. The current spectrum licensing scheme is unable to accommodate rapidly growing demand in wireless communication due the static spectrum allocation policies. This allocation leads to increase in spectrum scarcity problem. Cognitive radio (CR) technology is an advanced wireless radio design which aims to increase spectrum utilization by identifying unused and under-utilized spectrum in dynamically changing environments. But in low signal to noise ratio (SNR) conditions, its performance is weak, which can be improved by signal processing algorithm. As energy detection is simple and easily implemented in hardware, so it is preferred in emerging standard like IEEE 802.22, In this paper energy detection technique is applied for WLAN and WiMAX under BPSK modulation method and Monte-Carlo simulations are performed to test the performance of received signals in WLAN and WiMAX. Following to this work VLSI implementation of spectrum sensing using energy detection have been implemented for pseudo random sequence generated signal and BPSK modulates signal. OFDM is used as modulation standard and it is implemented in VLSI for WLAN and WiMAX.

A Robust Technique for Adaptive Noise Cancellation and its Implementation

Shankera Srivani¹ and K Kotaiah²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ABSTRACT

Adaptive Noise cancelling is a speech-specific filtering technique to suppress additive interference. It is a sensible choice for speech-orientated devices in situations where the designer has no knowledge of the properties of interference that could potentially corrupt the input speech to a point beyond intelligibility. However, constraints appear when implementing a noise-cancelling algorithm on such a portable device, and issues of power consumption and silicon area become prominent. This paper discusses an adaptive noise cancelling scheme and presents a VLSI implementation strategy. It then considers some of the benefits of the implementation and its potential area for improvement.

Keywords: Adaptive noise cancelling, VLSI design, speech enhancement.

Design of Modulo 2^n-2^k-1 Adder for Residue Number System

Unnam Veerendranath¹ and K Sandeep²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Veeru445@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Modular adder is one of the key components for the application of residue number system (RNS). Modulo set with the form of can offer excellent balance among the RNS channels for multi-channels RNS processing. In this paper, a novel algorithm and its VLSI implementation structure are proposed for modulo adder. In the proposed algorithm, parallel prefix operation and carry correction techniques are adopted to eliminate the re-computation of carries. Thus, we can get flexible tradeoff between area and delay with the proposed structure. Compared with same type modular adder with traditional structures, the proposed modulo adder offers better performance in delay and area.

Keywords: Carry correction, modular adder, parallel prefix, residue number system (RNS), VLSI.

A Robust Technique for Adaptive channel estimation

GunderkariPrashanth¹ and T Anil Kumar²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.
Veeru445@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) long term evolution (LTE) uses single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) in uplink transmission and orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) scheme for the downlink. A variable step size based least mean squares (LMS) algorithm is formulated for a single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) system channel estimation (CE). The weighting coefficients on the channel condition can be updated using this unbiased CE method. Channel and noise statistics information are not essential. Rather, it uses a phase weighting scheme to eliminate the signal fluctuations due to noise and decision errors. The convergence towards the true channel coefficient is guaranteed.

Keywords: Channel estimation, SC-FDMA, LMS

VLSI implementation of ofdm specified FFT architecture for software defined radio

K.Spandana¹, G.Yogeswararao²

^{1,2} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ABSTRACT

The challenge for new generations of software defined radio is to maintain pliability while simultaneously supporting programming. This paper presents a novel Software-defined radios (SDRs) architecture which is viable for wide varieties of communication protocols and physical data channels. It focus on OFDM transceiver styles due to their bandwidth scalability and standards, such as IEEE 802.11 is deliberated. This paper presents frameworks comprises of OFDM techniques, VLSI mapping of algorithms, Quadrature Phase shift keying (QPSK), Fast Fourier transform (FFT). Two modulations such as, Quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) and Quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) of OFDM baseband transceivers are implemented and compared. The architecture proposed is implemented using Verilog HDL Language. The proposed SDR system jointly minimizes power, maximize algorithm pliability, and enables rapid software re-programming which provides data rate reliability, and efficient throughput.

A Survey on Advances in Solar Energy: Nanotechnology

Amulya M

¹Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
¹²SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ABSTRACT

Renewable energy technologies have significant deployment potential as resources are spreading globally, in contrast to the conventional sources such as gas, coal and oil, which are more geographically concentrated. The solar cell industry has grown quickly in recent years due to strong interest in renewable energy and the problem of global climate change. Researches into a host of energy deployment options and creative policy initiatives continue in rest of solar energy and this paper highlights some of the recent advances observed and studied. It investigates the potentials of nanotechnology applicable in solar technology and also identifies workable options which can help in meeting energy demand particularly in the developing world.

VLSI implementation of FFT architecture optimization in MIMO OFDM Transreceivers

Burri Sandeep Reddy¹ and Gurubelli Yogeswararao²

¹Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,2}SR International Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to maximize the throughput by minimizing power as minimum as possible. Scores of optimization techniques such as FFT, IFFT and memory optimization are available reducing power of mobile Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) systems. An approach for achieving reduction in power of Multiple-Input Multiple-output (MIMO) OFDM systems by optimizing FFT architecture is addressed in this paper. The Proposed structure is combination of memory reference reduction method with binary scaling techniques and Radix -4 booth multiplier. Here multiplier in FFT is realized with shifter, adders and sub tractors. The Proposed systems structure is evaluated using performance parameters such as bit error rate (BER) and signal to noise ratio (SNR).

Keywords: MIMO, OFDM, BER, SNR, Booth Multiplier.

Ultrasonic Signal Coding and PIR Sensors to Enhance the Sensing Reliability of an Embedded Surveillance System

Ch Aruna and G Rajender

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

In this paper we design and implement an embedded surveillance system by use of ultrasonic signal coding of ultrasonic sensors with multiple pyroelectric infrared sensors (PIR) to detect an intruder in a home or a storehouse. The PIR sensors are placed on the ceiling, and the ultrasonic sensor module consists of a transmitter and a receiver which are placed in a line direction; however, ultrasonic sensors with the same frequency are subject to interference by crosstalk with each other and have a high miss rate. To overcome these disadvantages of the ultrasonic sensor, our design reduces the miss rate from the environmental interference by using an ultrasonic coding signal. Both ultrasonic sensors and PIR sensors are managed by the majority voting mechanism (MVM).

Keywords: Embedded Surveillance System; Majority Voting Mechanism; PIR Sensor; Ultrasonic Sensor.

Internet of Vehicles: From Intelligent Grid to Autonomous Cars and Vehicular Clouds

Amtul Fouzia Begum and G Rajender

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

Traditionally, the vehicle has been the extension of the man's ambulatory system, docile to the driver's commands. Recent advances in communications, controls and embedded systems have changed this model, paving the way to the Intelligent Vehicle Grid. The car is now a formidable sensor platform, absorbing information from the environment (and from other cars) and feeding it to drivers and infrastructure to assist in safe navigation, pollution control and traffic management. The next step in this evolution is just around the corner: the Internet of Autonomous Vehicles. Pioneered by the Google car, the Internet of Vehicles will be a distributed transport fabric capable to make its own decisions about driving customers to their destinations. Like other important instantiations of the Internet of Things (e.g., the smart building), the Internet of Vehicles will have communications, storage, intelligence, and learning capabilities to anticipate the customers' intentions. The concept that will help transition to the Internet of Vehicles is the Vehicular Cloud, the equivalent of Internet cloud for vehicles, providing all the services required by the autonomous vehicles. In this article, we discuss the evolution from Intelligent Vehicle Grid to Autonomous, Internet-connected Vehicles, and Vehicular Cloud.

Power Sensor Tag with Interference Reduction for Electricity Monitoring of Two-Wire Household Appliances

K Kavya and G Rajendar

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India

ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates a flexible nonintrusive power sensor tag with an interference reduction scheme for accurate electricity monitoring of the household appliances using typical SPT-2 18 AWG zip-cord power lines. Both current and voltage sensors with the design of a 50-turn inductive coil and two capacitive electrodes, respectively, in an area of $1.3 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ are fabricated on a $100\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -thick flexible polyethylene terephthalate substrate as a sensor tag. The tag exhibits a sensitivity of 271.6 mV/A and 0.38 mV/V via active low-pass filter circuits for the current and voltage detection. A compensation circuit inputted with the signals of the voltage sensor is applied for the interference reduction of the current sensor electrically coupled with the power cord so that the current sensor can achieve over a 40-dB signal-to-noise ratio for measuring the loaded current of 1 A, 60 Hz on the power line

Tracking limbs motion using wireless network of inertial measurement units

S Kondaiah and M A Shahid

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

Tracking the position and the orientation of human limbs to reconstruct postures and actions is becoming a crucial need in several application domains, including medicine, rehabilitation, sport, and games. However, most available solutions are expensive, imprecise, or require an instrumentation of the environment. This paper presents a low-cost tracking system based on a set of wearable inertial measurement units (IMUs) coordinated as a wireless body area network. After the system description, the characterization of the single node is provided through a set of experiments. Issues related to real-time processing, calibration, data synchronization, and energy consumption are introduced using a preliminary simplified setup with two nodes.

FPGA Implementation of High Speed Pipelined Log Multiplier for DSP MAC unit Applications

Mahendra and M A Shahid

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

In today's real world the computational speed of DSP processor is crucial factor to analyze the performance of any system. Since the processor has to deal with large magnitude data's, it becomes necessary to design high speed multiplier with accuracy required for MAC unit application of DSP processor. In this project, A new approach for logarithm based multipliers to improve accuracy and efficiency of multipliers is proposed for DSP MAC unit applications. The proposed solution is based on calculating the error correction terms iteratively to achieve high but arbitrary accuracy. The implementation of the sub stage pipelined concept & carry save adder to speed up the multiplication process that is achieved through parallel processing. After the initial latency, the products are calculated in each clock period, regardless the number of the error correction circuits used. The proposed multiplier and MAC unit has been synthesized and implemented on Spartan 6LX45 board and it is observed that it consumes less area, time and power as compared to basic MA based multipliers and ODMA error correction method with less error percentage.

A Novel Data Embedding Method Using Adaptive Pixel Pair Matching

Mallikarjun and M A Shahid

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a new data-hiding method based on pixel pair matching (PPM). The basic idea of PPM is to use the values of pixel pair as a reference coordinate, and search a coordinate in the neighborhood set of this pixel pair according to a given message digit. The pixel pair is then replaced by the searched coordinate to conceal the digit. Exploiting modification direction (EMD) and diamond encoding (DE) are two data-hiding methods proposed recently based on PPM. The maximum capacity of EMD is 1.161 bpp and DE extends the payload of EMD by embedding digits in a larger notational system. The proposed method offers lower distortion than DE by providing more compact neighborhood sets and allowing embedded digits in any notational system. Compared with the optimal pixel adjustment process (OPAP) method, the proposed method always has lower distortion for various payloads. Experimental results reveal that the proposed method not only provides better performance than those of OPAP and DE, but also is secure under the detection of some well-known analysis techniques.

Application of RFID Technology and the Maximum Spanning Tree Algorithm for Solving Vehicle Emissions in Cities on Internet of Things

A Sushma and G Rajendar

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India.

ABSTRACT

The proportion of air pollution which is caused by the cars is increasing. In order to solve this serious problem, many countries and regions have already presented a series of emissions standards, meanwhile some methods has been developed, include update motor engine or improve the quality of the gasoline. However, these actions have not brought about a striking effect as we expect. There are also some situations to fail implement these emissions standards. In this paper, a wireless inspection and notification system (WINS) through the concept of Internet of Things (IoT) is proposed. By applying the system, it is possible to smoothly realize a green traffic network. In this system, Radio frequency identification (RFID) technology as a low-cost and mature wireless communication method is adopted to collect and transmit emissions information of vehicles. Moreover, The RFID devices need to be installed on the traffic lights so that reliable reading of emissions signals from a vehicle can be interrogated when the vehicles stop in front of the red light. Taken into consideration the real environment, an efficient and innovative maximum spanning tree algorithm (MXAST) is also presented to select suitable traffic lights aim to reduce the number of RFID devices (more economy) and guaranteed the whole urban cars can be monitored (simple & safety).

An Adaptive Noise Canceller for DS-CDMA Systems

M A Himayath Shamshi¹, ²T Anil Kumar and ³K Kumar Naik

¹Research Scholar, ^{2,3}Professor,

^{1,2,3} Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,

^{1,3} KL University, Vaddeswaram, India.

² SR Engineering College, Warangal, India.

¹himayathshamshi@gmail.com, ²tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in, ³kumarnaik@kluniversity.in

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an adaptive noise cancelling scheme (a speech-specific filtering technique to suppress additive interference) and its VLSI implementation strategy. Adaptive noise cancelling scheme is a sensible choice for speech-orientated devices in situations where the designer has no knowledge of the properties of interference that could potentially corrupt the input speech to a point beyond intelligibility. Issues of power consumption and silicon area become prominent when implementing a noise-cancelling algorithm on such a portable device. Further, some of the benefits of implementation and its potential area for improvement are also addressed in this paper. Finally, the approach is corroborated with simulation results.

Keywords: Adaptive noise cancelling, VLSI design, speech enhancement

Optimum Channel Estimation Technique for SCFDMA Systems

K V Prasanna Lakshmi¹, and G Rajender²

^{1,2} Electronics and Communication Engineering, TRR College of Engineering, Patanchervu, India
¹ lakshmiprasanna449@gmail.com and ²raju3653@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper, an optimum channel estimation technique for single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) systems is addressed as 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) long term evolution (LTE) uses single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) in uplink transmission and orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) scheme for the downlink. Robustified least mean squares (LMS) algorithm is formulated for a single carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) system channel estimation. The weighting coefficients on the channel condition can be updated using an M-estimator. The convergence towards the true channel coefficient is guaranteed. Simulation results are provided to support the proposed technique.

Keywords: Channel estimation, SC-FDMA, LMS.

Robust frequency estimation for sampled sinusoidal signals without iteration

A DEEKSHA¹ and G. RAJENDER²

^{1,2} Electronics and Communication Engineering, TRR College of Engineering, Patancheru, India

¹ deekshaadula@gmail.com and ² raju3653@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a signal frequency estimation method for sampled sinusoidal signals, which requires no iteration for the frequency search. This paper robustifies the algorithm of Zhang *et al.* to maintain the same signal-to-noise ratio as with the traditional four parameter estimation method that requires iterations for the signal frequency search. Numerical simulation results show that the frequency estimation error when Gaussian noise is added to the input data is little higher than the square root of the Cramer–Rao bound. Further, it was shown that the effect of harmonic components on the frequency estimation error can be minimized when the phase interval is close to $(2/3)\pi$. Furthermore, Simulation results show that the frequency estimation with the proposed method is more accurate than that with the IEEE-1057 method when the harmonic components are added to the input signal.

Keywords: Cramer–Rao bound (CRB), frequency estimation, IEEE Standard 1057, least-square method.

Multiplexing Efficiency and Capacity limits of MIMO Systems

Soma Umamaheshwar¹ Tipparti Anil Kumar² and K Srinivas Rao³

¹Research Scholar, ECE Department, JNTUH College of Engineering, Hyderabad, India

²Professor, ECE Department, SR Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India

³Principal & Professor, ECE Department, TRR college of Engineering, Hyderabad, Telangana India

¹umamaheshwarsoma@gmail.com, ²tvakumar2000@yahoo.com, ³ksrinivasrao@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A simple and intuitive metric of multiplexing efficiency and capacity is proposed for evaluating the performance of multiple inputs multiple output (MIMO) systems. MIMO channels has a high signal to noise ratio slope that equal the minimum of number of transmit and receive antennas. Apart from gaining valuable insights into the impact of antenna efficiency, efficiency imbalance on multiplexing performance is particularly useful for antenna whose goal is to achieve the optimum antenna system. We prove analytically capacity limits of MIMO systems for any channel distribution and SNR.

Keywords: channel capacity, high SNR analysis, multiplexing efficiency and MIMO.

Optimum Design of Heat Sink for Natural Convection

¹P. Vinay Kumar,²T.VijayaSarathi, ³J. NaliniKumari,
⁴V. Nanda Kishore Reddy, ⁵Y. Mohan Krishna

^{1,2} Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, BVRIT, Narsapur,

³ Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, AVN, Hyderabad,

^{4,5} B.Techstudent, Department of Mechanical Engineering, SRIIT, Hyderabad,

¹vinaykumar.p@bvr.it.ac.in, vijayasarathi.t@bvr.it.ac.in,³nalinij_9@yahoo.co.in,

⁴vanga.nandakishore@gmail.com⁵mohankrishnayannam@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Heat sinks are widely used in various industrial applications such as electronic, power electronic, telecommunication, and automotive components respectively by dissipating heat to the surrounding medium. In this paper we have designed 30 Watts heat sink, natural convection to maintain the Junction temperature of 65 °C and temperature difference between the fin surface and the surrounding is 20°C. Space available for heat sink position is 210 * 150 * 30 mm. The rectangular heat sink was designed, but considering space available is as constriction, we have optimized the vertical length of heat sink by making rectangular fin to curved profile. Experimental examination is made to find the amount of the heat dissipated through the heat sink to the ambient temperature in comparison with natural convection process

Multiuser Detection in Gaussian Channels

V. Srinivasa Rao¹, Habibulla Khan² and T. Anil Kumar³

¹KITS for Women, Kodad, India

²KL University, Vaddeswaram, India

³SR Engineering College, Warangal, India

¹vempatisr@ieee.org, ²habibulla@rediffmail.com, ³tvakumar2000@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a robust multiuser detection technique for combating multiple access interference (MAI) and Gaussian noise in direct sequence – code division multiple access (DS-CDMA) communication systems. A robust M -decorrelating detector is proposed to demodulate binary phase shift keying (BPSK) signals. A closed-form expression for the asymptotic probability of error is derived. The approach is corroborated with simulation results. Simulation results show that the proposed approach yields significant performance gain over the Huber and the Hampel estimator based linear decorrelating multiuser detectors with little attendant increase in the computational complexity. The robust multiuser detection technique can be applied to both synchronous and asynchronous CDMA channels.

Keywords: CDMA, influence function, M -estimator, multiuser detection.